

Surveying the vascular flora of the Iberian Central Range: a critical checklist of the Ávila province flora

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Abstract. Despite its proximity to cities with prestigious botanical institutions such as Madrid and Salamanca, and its location between important mountain ranges (Gredos and Malagón mountain ranges), the flora of the province of Ávila had not been studied comprehensively until now. In this article, we present the first checklist of the vascular flora of this province, which is the result of a thorough critical bibliographic review, numerous field trips, and the study of materials preserved in Iberian herbaria, mainly those that house most of the collections made in the province. The taxonomic and nomenclatural treatment considers the results of the latest monographic works and, particularly, the molecular phylogenetic studies carried out during the last few decades. These studies have substantially changed the classification, aligning it with the evolutionary processes that have contributed to the current plant biodiversity. We have accepted 1977 taxa (species and subspecies), with 1810 considered native and 165 introduced. Additionally, we present the floristic spectrum of the province and the state of conservation of its flora. All of this is discussed considering the data provided by the complete checklists available from neighbouring provinces. For each taxon, we highlight its presence or absence in the three ecological regions into which we have divided the province (La Moraña region, Sierra de Gredos, and Sierra de Malagón). Where necessary, we provide observations regarding its distribution, taxonomy, or nomenclature. Notably, we included the genus *Exaculum* in *Schenkia*, leading us to propose a new nomenclatural combination.

Keywords. Checklist, conservation, new combination, province of Ávila, vascular flora.

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Introduction

The province of Ávila (Spain) has a remarkable habitats diversity, making it one of the most botanically rich areas in the Iberian Peninsula. Interestingly, neighbouring provinces as Madrid, Salamanca, and Segovia have conducted extensive studies on the flora, with Madrid even having comprehensive checklists of its flora. In contrast, research in Ávila has mainly concentrated on specific areas, including the eastern Gredos massif (Sánchez Mata, 1989), the Iruelas valley (Molina Moreno, 1992), the Amblés valley (Fuentes Lasala, 1989a,b), and the mountain ranges of Barco and Béjar (Sardinero Roscales, 2004). Alternatively, broader regions have also been explored (Rivas Martínez, 1963; Rivas Martínez *et al.*, 1989; Luceño & Vargas, 1990; Luceño & Vargas, 1991; Luceño *et al.*, 2016), all of which are linked to the Gredos mountains or the entire Central System. There are, indeed, numerous fragmentary works on chorological findings of interest in different parts of the province, although more numerous in the Gredos area and, to a lesser extent, in the La Moraña region.

For the purposes of this checklist, and for practical reasons, we have divided the province into three large zones based on their different environmental characteristics and, consequently, their distinct floral composition (Figure 1): 1) La Moraña region and adjacent areas in the northern part of the province; 2) Malagón and Ojos Albos mountain ranges; and 3) Sierra de Gredos in the broad sense. We are aware that the territorial division of the province into three zones does not reflect all the environmental diversity

of the province, as illustrated by: (1) The Sierra de Ávila, both from a lithological and climatological point of view, is quite different from the Paramera-Serrota-Villafranca axis and the three massifs of Gredos s.s. (presence of ultrabasic rocks and a notably drier climate). (2) The Tiétar valley, as noted, boasts a warmer and more humid climate compared to the rest of the Ávila mountains, with its soils exhibiting greater diversity. This is due to the presence of calcareous clays in certain areas, which support a basophilic flora not found in the other Gredos valleys.

1. La Moraña and other areas in the north of the Ávila province

La Moraña region is located in the southeast of the northern Iberian sub-plateau and encompasses a significant portion of the northern area of the Ávila province. It is a flat landscape, heavily influenced by human activity, with a substantial portion of its surface devoted to dryland cultivation, particularly cereals. The substratum is made up of sedimentary materials that were deposited horizontally because of the erosion of the ancient Duero river basin, giving rise to the current plains. These plains have been shaped by both river activity, which has carved canyons in certain sections of the Adaja River, and wind action, which has formed dunes by dragging materials deposited since the beginning of the Holocene.

Figure 1. Territories into which the province of Ávila is divided for the purposes of this checklist. Gr: Gredos in the broad sense; Ma: Malagón and Ojos Albos mountain ranges; Mo: north of the province, including the region of La Moraña.

As we have just pointed out, most of the territory has historically been subjected to intense agricultural use, shaping its current physiognomy, and forcing numerous species finding refuge in the few little altered areas that persist today. These areas include canyons and shallow depressions where seasonal endorheic lagoons were formed, although the latter have suffered a significant retreat due to artificial drainage in some of them. Despite human alteration, both the lagoons and canyons, along with some patches of uncultivated land on limestone substrate, harbour a very rare and unique calcicole and subhalophilous flora in the Ávila province.

The most extensive lagoon is known as “Laguna del Hoyo”, near the village of El Oso, where we can find species inhabiting saline or sub-saline soils such as *Camphorosma monspeliaca* subsp. *monspeliaca*, *Frankenia pulverulenta*, *Spergularia media*, *Plantago maritima* subsp. *serpentina*, *Trifolium gemellum*, *Lotus maritimus*, *Juncus gerardii*, *Oenanthe silaifolia*, *Cerastium dubium*, *Puccinellia fasciculata*, *P. festuciformis* subsp. *lagascana*, and *P. rupestris*. From the locality of Velayos, *Puccinellia pungens* is also known, considered as Endangered (EN) by the Junta de Castilla y León. Another noteworthy species in this region is *Carex lainzii*, an Iberian endemism of which only five populations are known, four of them in Castilla y León region (Anon., 2007). This species, which seems to have disappeared from other localities where it has been recorded in Ávila (Velayos and Fontiveros), is also listed as Endangered. Finally, it is worth highlighting the presence of some species in these temporary, basophilic wetlands, such as *Butomus umbellatus*, *Damasonium polyspermum*, *Lythrum tribracteatum*, *Cressa cretica* and three very rare sedge species in the province due to their soil requirements: *Bolboschoenus maritimus* (in the small lagoons of San Pascual), *B. glaucus* and *Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani*, whose populations have suffered a serious decline due to the artificial drainage.

In addition to its distinctive habitats, the northern part of the province is characterized by the canyons sculpted by the Adaja River. These canyons present basic soils that host non-existent or sporadic species in other areas of the province. Among these species, we highlight *Astragalus granatensis*, *Ephedra distachya* subsp. *distachya*, *Fumana procumbens*, *Helianthemum cinereum* subsp. *rotundifolium*, *H. ledifolium*, *Hippocrepis commutata*, *Linaria bipunctata* subsp. *bipunctata*, *L. caesia*, *Linum austriacum* subsp. *collinum*, *L. suffruticosum* subsp. *loefflingii*, *Lysimachia ephemerum*, *Ophrys speculum*, *Phlomis herba-venti*, *Prunus insititia*, *Saponaria glutinosa*, *Thymelaea pubescens* subsp. *pubescens* and *Umbilicus heylandianus*.

Finally, we should not forget the small, loamy, limestone-bedded hills to the north of Arévalo, in the area known as “Cantazorras”, which should be urgently protected as a micro-reserve. In addition to some of the species mentioned in the previous paragraph, there grow *Adonis aestivalis* subsp. *squarrosa*, *A. annua*, *A. flammea*, *Agropyron cristatum*, *Ammoides pusilla*, *Anthemis pedunculata* subsp. *tulrensis*, *Convolvulus meonanthus*, *Delphinium pubescens*, *Glaucium corniculatum*, *Haplophyllum linifolium* subsp. *linifolium*, *Malva setigera*, *Malvella sherardiana*, *Nonea micrantha*, *Nonea vesicaria*,

Peganum harmala, *Polycnemum arvense*, *Rochelia disperma* subsp. *disperma*, *Silene muscipula*, *Sternbergia colchiciflora*, *Turgenia latifolia* and *Vicia amphicarpa*.

2. Malagón and Ojos Albos mountain ranges

The Malagón mountain range is a hilly alignment located in the middle section of the Central System. Its northeastern end links with the Guadarrama mountain range via the Hornillo mountain pass and the course of the Arroyo Mayor, while its southwestern end connects with La Paramera mountain range through Altos de Valdelavía. Its southern branches reach the foothills of the eastern massif of Gredos in the municipalities of Hoyo de Pinares and Cebreros. As part of the Iberian Central System, its peaks divide the basins of the Duero and Tajo rivers, with the northern slopes carved out by tributary gorges of the Eresma and, primarily, the Voltoya rivers, and the southern slopes by streams that flow into the Alberche river. Its highest elevation, Cueva Valiente (1903 m asl), is in the northeastern part of the range, at the northern foot of which lie the towns of San Rafael and El Espinar, in Segovia. This orographic ensemble is administratively situated in the provinces of Madrid, Segovia, and primarily, Ávila. On the southern slopes are important municipalities such as Las Navas del Marqués, Peguerinos, Navalperal de Pinares and Hoyo de Pinares.

To the north of the Malagón mountain range, separated from it by the Voltoya river, lies the Ojos Albos mountain range, whose highest peak is the Cruz del Hierro (1660 m asl). Many geographers consider the Malagón and Ojos Albos mountain ranges as branches of the Guadarrama mountain range; however, others consider the Ojos Albos mountain range as an eastern satellite horst of the so-called Sierra de Ávila (Brandis & Troitíño, 1977).

From a lithological perspective, the Malagón mountain range is mainly made up of Palaeozoic soils dominated by granites, whereas in the Ojos Albos mountain range, quartzites, shales and slates predominate. In both ranges, soils are of an acidic nature, although in certain areas of the latter mountain range the soils are less acidic, probably due to alteration of the slates. The Malagón mountain range displays typical vegetation of the supramediterranean level of the Guadarrama mountain range, mainly consisting of Scots pine forests (*Pinus sylvestris*) that harbor an interesting biodiversity in terms of plant species, animals and fungi. From a floristic perspective, the presence of shrubs such as *Amelanchier ovalis* subsp. *ovalis* or *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi*, which are very rare or absent in the western sections of the Iberian Central System, stands out. Moreover, the numerous wetlands that have been preserved from intensive human activity host species that are already very rare in other peninsular areas. The most significant case is that of *Luronium natans*, a European endemism considered Endangered by the Junta de Castilla y León, and by the 2017 Addendum to the Atlas and Red Book of Threatened Vascular Flora of Spain (Moreno *et al.*, 2019). The only known central Iberian locality of this species is found in certain streams near Peguerinos. Since it is a plant with five widely dispersed Iberian

population nuclei and the Ávila population has few individuals, we believe it is imperative to carry out an urgent plan to ensure its protection in the Iberian Central System.

Furthermore, in Ojos Albos mountain range inhabits *Gymnocarpium dryopteris*, an exceptionally rare Euro-Siberian fern in the Iberian Central System, and *Galatella linosyris*, also rare and considered to be of preferential attention by the Junta de Castilla y León.

Another wetland species in need of effective protection is the tiny *Littorella uniflora* (of preferential attention), of which only two small populations in Ávila are known, both in the tailing communities of reservoirs – one in the municipality of Candeleda (Rosarito reservoir) and another in the Serones reservoir, at the southern foot of the Ojos Albos mountain range. Lastly, it is worth noting the possible provincial extinction of the white water lily (*Nymphaea alba*), which lived in a seasonal pond near the Guimorcondo railway station but was drained only few years ago.

3. Sierra de Gredos in a broad sense

Under this heading, we include the rest of the province of Ávila, encompassing all mountainous areas of Ávila, except for the aforementioned Malagón and Ojos Albos mountain ranges. From north to south, we find the three alignments that make up this mountainous region: the Sierra de Ávila, with its highest point being Cerro Gorriá (1772 m asl); the alignment formed by La Paramera (Zapatero peak, 2160 m asl), La Serrota (2294 m asl), and Villafranca (Cerro Moros, 2059 m asl) mountain ranges; and the southern chain, Sierra de Gredos in the strict sense, consisting of three massifs (eastern, central, and western, the latter also known as the Béjar mountain range). In this southern range are the main elevations, not only of the province, but also of the entire Iberian Central System, with the Almanzor peak (central massif, 2591 m asl) at the head. The eastern massif culminates at El Cabezo (2188 m asl), and the western massif at La Ceja (2425 m asl).

Between the Ávila mountain range and the Paramera-Serrota-Villafranca alignment lie two of the most important valleys in the province, separated by the Villatoro pass. The western valley is carved out by the Corneja river, which flows into the Tormes, and the eastern valley is carved out by the Adaja river, tributary of the Duero river. The climate of these valleys is of semi-arid continental like (except for the northern slopes of the mentioned Paramera-Serrota-Villafranca mountain axis) due to the high average altitude and the rain shadow cast by the high peaks of Gredos and those of the Paramera-Serrota-Villafranca. The substrates are quite diverse. While acidic rocks, particularly granite, prevail on the southern slopes of the valleys, significant diabase betas traverse the northern slopes. These diabase betas emerged due to the Alentejo-Plasencia fault. Additionally, in certain points, especially in the Amblés valley, small fragments of sub-saline soils can be observed.

The lithological diversity is reflected in the floristic composition of these valleys, where we can find numerous basophilic species absent in most other parts of the Ávila province. Among these species, we highlight *Minuartia hamata*, *Fumana*

procumbens, *Helianthemum salicifolium*, *Thapsia gummifera*, *Ajuga chamaepitys*, *Salvia aethiopis*, *Stipa iberica* and *Astragalus alopecuroides* subsp. *alopecuroides*. However, the most remarkable plant in these valleys, a true floral jewel, is *Astragalus devesae*, an endemism of the southern slope of the Ávila mountain range with only three known populations. This plant, together with *Centaurea avilae*, *Pseudomisopates rivas-martinezii*, *Festuca vettonica* and *Teucrium oxylepis* subsp. *gredense*, to which we will refer later, constitute the five endemic taxa of the province of Ávila. Current data indicate that the number of individuals of *A. devesae* barely exceeds 400, which justifies it being classified as Critically Endangered in the Atlas and Red Book of Threatened Vascular Flora of Spain, and as Endangered in the list of endangered species of the Junta de Castilla y León. Curiously, this endemism appears on both acidic and basic soils.

Conversely, in siliceous soils, especially on the slopes and summits of the northern sides of the Paramera, La Serrota, and Villafranca mountain ranges, the climate is notably more humid than in other regions. This humidity fosters the formation of peat bogs and other wetlands, providing habitats for plants like *Tephrosieris balbisiana* subsp. *coincyi* a subendemism of Gredos classified as Endangered in Castilla y León and Vulnerable at national level. Its most abundant populations are found on the northern slope of the Villafranca mountain range. Even rarer is *Delphinium fissum* subsp. *sordidum*, a highly localized Iberian endemism considered Endangered by both the Junta de Castilla y León and the Atlas and Red Book of Threatened Vascular Flora of Spain. The only population in Ávila has recently been discovered in the vicinity of the Villatoro pass. Other rare or threatened species include the carnivorous plants *Utricularia minor* and *U. australis*, both considered of preferential attention in the mentioned Castilla y León catalogue as well as *Sedum aetnense* subsp. *aetnense*, of which we only know two populations in Ávila, and *Nepeta multibracteata*, also very rare in the province that inhabits in oak forest edges in the headwaters of the Corneja river. Another interesting species from the humid and cold areas of the Paramera, La Serrota and Villafranca mountain ranges are *Huperzia selago*, *Botrychium lunaria*, *Centaurea janeri* subsp. *janerii*, *Trollius europaeus*, *Geum rivale*, *Potentilla micrantha*, *Alchemilla straminea* and *Cuscuta europaea*. To conclude this floristic journey through the Amblés and Corneja valleys, it seems relevant mentioning the presence of *Centaurea amblensis* subsp. *amblensis*. While it is not a threatened plant, this beautiful Iberian endemic species derives its specific name from the Amblés valley, where it was discovered.

Three other valleys of great interest are those carved out by the Alberche, Tormes and Tiétar rivers. On the one hand, the first two are bounded to the north by the Paramera-Serrota-Villafranca axis and to the south by the three massifs of Gredos. These valleys are separated by a ridge that connects the two mountain chains, with its lowest point in the vicinity of the National Parador of Gredos. On the other hand, for a large part of its course, the Tiétar river forms the border between the provinces of

Ávila and Toledo, and it has a distinctive flora due to the mild and humid climate originated by the Tiétar fault, which caused altitudinal differences of more than 2200 m asl between the peaks of Gredos and the southern lowlands.

The Alberche river originates in the municipality of San Martín de la Vega del Alberche, on the southern slope of the section that connects La Serrota with the Villafranca mountain range. From there, it flows eastwards to the village of Aldea del Fresno (Madrid), where it turns sharply, due to an ancient river catchment, and heads southwest to Talavera de la Reina, where it flows into the Tagus river after 177 km. The upper basin extends from its source to the San Juan reservoir, in the province of Madrid, and runs along the southern slope of La Serrota and the Paramera mountain ranges, as well as the northern slopes of the eastern Gredos massif. Between these two mountain chains, it has carved deep valleys with a sub-humid climate characterized by distinct seasonal patterns, featuring warm and dry summers and cold winters. The substratum of the upper Alberche is siliceous in nature, with a clear predominance of different types of granite. The potential vegetation is Pyrenean oak forest (*Quercus pyrenaica*), except for occasional patches (or larger extensions favoured by humans) of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), maritime pine (*P. pinaster*), and even Austrian black pine (*P. nigra* subsp. *salzmannii*). The pine forests are extraordinarily rich in plants that are very rare in such southern latitudes. This is especially the case of the Pinar de Hoyocasero pine forest or the pine forests of the Iruelas valley. Another unique forest in the upper Alberche is the chestnut forest called Castañar del Tiemblo, rich in Euro-Siberian elements and with a similar floristic composition to that of the Pinar de Hoyocasero. Human activity has modified the landscape, favouring open spaces where the pastures remain green for much of the year. In addition, in the tributary gorges and the backwaters of the river, it is possible to observe interesting peaty patches that are home to an extremely interesting flora.

The Pinar de Hoyocasero is a unique floristic enclave in the Iberian Central System. It is a native Scots pine forest surrounded by Pyrenean oak. Under its protection, we can find Eurosiberian species that are actually very rare in these latitudes (Luceño, 1991; López Sáez et al., 2016). Among them, we highlight *Convallaria majalis*, *Caltha palustris*, *Pulsatilla alpina* subsp. *apiifolia*, *Trollius europaeus*, *Geum rivale*, *Silene flos-cuculi*, *Primula intricata* subsp. *bergidensis*, *Valeriana officinalis* subsp. *officinalis*, *Pimpinella major*, *Sanicula europaea*, *Veronica officinalis*, *Lilium martagon*, the orchids *Neottia nidus-avis*, *Cephalanthera rubra* and *Gymnadenia conopsea*, the last two of which have not been observed for years, despite numerous searches. The species *Pyrola chlorantha* can definitely be considered extinct from this pine forest. It was collected on a single occasion by Bourgeau on July 24th, 1863, and the specimen is preserved in the herbarium of the Museum of Natural History in France (Paris). Other species that are also very rare include *Monotropa hypopitys* (presumably extinct), *Ajuga pyramidalis* subsp. *meonantha* (also probably extinct from the Pinewoods, although it can still be

found in the Trampales stream, in the neighbouring village of San Martín del Pimpollar), *Viburnum lantana*, *V. opulus*, *Paris quadrifolia*, *Actaea spicata*, *Galium rotundifolium*, *Carex disticha*, and *C. vesicaria*. The last two only present in the few peaty areas of this forest. It is interesting to note that in this pine forest, the previously mentioned *Tephrosia balbisiana* subsp. *coincyi* was discovered for science. This endemic taxon has only seven populations, one in Zamora (Sanabria area; Martínez García et al., 2015), another in the southwestern parts of the province of Salamanca (Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2019) and six in the province of Ávila (El Tiemblo, Piedralaves-Casavieja, Peña Negra pass, San Martín de la Vega del Alberche, pine forests of Navarredonda de Gredos and Pinar de Hoyocasero, where it became extinct and has been successfully reintroduced in recent years). The forest also hosts other interesting plants, some of which are Iberian endemics or species typical of the Mediterranean region. These include *Iris xiphium*, *Euphorbia nevadensis* subsp. *nevadensis* (classified as of preferential attention in Castilla y León), *Aristolochia castellana*, *Fritillaria pyrenaica* subsp. *falcata*, *Erysimum merxmulleri*, and *Rhaponticum exaltatum*, with spectacular purple flower heads. In total, around 500 species of vascular plants are known (Luceño, 1991), an impressive number for a forest mass of barely 140 hectares.

A second important forest in terms of its richness in Eurosiberian plants is the Castañar del Tiemblo. Paleoenvironmental studies have confirmed the autochthonous character of this chestnut forest (López Sáez et al., 2017), making it a relic from earlier times when chestnut forests covered larger areas in the Gredos mountains. In addition to some of the Eurosiberian species present in Pinar de Hoyocasero, such as *Lilium martagon* and *Cephalanthera rubra*, there are other plants absent from this pine forest. Among them we highlight *Ilex aquifolium*, *Pulmonaria longifolia*, *Allium scorzonerifolium*, *Veronica montana*, and *Limodorum abortivum*.

Other rare or threatened species in the upper Alberche are the Spanish juniper (*Juniperus thurifera*), of which only a small population is known in the vicinity of the village of El Barraco, *Succisella microcephala*, classified as Vulnerable by the Junta de Castilla y León, *Cardamine castellana*, *Aconitum napellus* subsp. *lusitanicum*, *Myosotis hervei*, and *Carex limosa*, a very rare sedge in the Iberian Peninsula, whose only locality in the Iberian Central System lives in deep peat bogs near the Gredos National Parador.

The Tormes river has its sources in the vicinity of the Cabrilla pass, in the municipality of Navarredonda de Gredos. Its upper course is bordered by the Villafranca mountain range to the north and the central massif of Gredos to the south. Its trajectory (from east to west) takes a northerly direction near the town of El Barco de Ávila, from where it heads towards the Duero river, leaving the western massif of Gredos (Sierra de Béjar) to the west. The predominant bedrock of all these mountain ranges is made up of various types of granite, some of which show large feldspar crystals. Consequently, the soils are mostly acidic. The relief is very abrupt in some sections, especially in the central massif, with deep valleys that

were carved by glaciers on the northern slope and even deeper ones formed by the torrential action of the waters that flow towards the Tiétar in the south. The climate is typical of the Mediterranean highlands, characterised by mild summers and cold winters, with precipitation levels increasing as we move further west. Thus, the western massif (Sierra de Béjar) accumulates more rainfall overall compared to the central massif, due both to its greater proximity to the Atlantic Ocean and the rain shadow generated by its high peaks. However, summers are dry in both massifs.

Given that the summits overlooking the Tormes valley are the highest in the entire Iberian Central System, they are habitats to a good number of alpine-boreal species, among which we can highlight *Athyrium distentifolium*, *Botrychium lunaria*, *Huperzia selago*, *Viscaria alpina*, *Omalotheca supina*, *Callitriche palustris*, *Epilobium anagallidifolium* and *Cerastium cerastioides*. The Iberian orophyte endemisms are represented, among other species, by *Carex lucennoiberica*, considered as Vulnerable by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN), *Androsace vitaliana* subsp. *aurelii*, *Betula pendula* subsp. *fontqueri*, *Gentiana boryi*, *Isoetes asturicense*, *Paradisea lusitanica*, *Ranunculus abnormis*, *R. amplexicaulis*, *R. cherubicus* subsp. *cherubicus*, *Sedum candolleianum*, *Sideritis lurida* subsp. *borgiae*, *Thymelaea procumbens* and *Veronica fruticans* subsp. *cantábrica*. Other species of interest in the valley are *Baldellia alpestris*, *Lycopodiella inundata*, *Menyanthes trifoliata*, *Spiranthes aestivalis* and *Rhynchospora alba*, all of which are quite rare in peat bogs. Lastly, we must not forget the Eurosiberian species that inhabit the Scots pine forests in the northern slopes of the central massif, such as those surrounding the Gredos National Parador. In these pine forests, interesting species find refuge, such as *Actaea spicata*, *Aconitum napellus* subsp. *lusitanicum*, *A. lycoctomum*, *Convallaria majalis*, *Paris quadrifolia*, *Pyrola minor* and *Tephrosieris balbisiana* subsp. *coincyi*.

Finally, the Tiétar river, which flows east to west along the southern slope of the main Gredos range, originates in the town of Rozas de Puerto Real in Madrid. However, it quickly enters Ávila, where it follows most of its course. It is tributary to all the southern gorges of Gredos, which are torrential in nature due to the enormous difference in altitude caused by the previously mentioned Tiétar fault. The lithology, and, therefore, the soils are very similar to those described for the Tormes and Alberche valleys. Nevertheless, in some areas of the municipalities of Arenas de San Pedro and Candeleda, there are outcrops of calcium carbonate and basic clays that give the soil a higher pH. This has allowed for the establishment of thermophilic, basophilic species that are absent from the rest of the province. The climate, however, differs markedly from that of the other two valleys, since these lands are protected from the north winds by the Gredos slopes. Furthermore, the orientation of the southern slopes promotes the collision of rain fronts against Gredos, so rainfall is significantly higher than in the northern slope. However, the degree of sunshine, especially in summer, is also higher, making it more difficult to retain humidity. All this, results in a mild and humid climate, which explains why much of the southern part of the mountain range has historically been

suited for the cultivation of thermophilic species such as olive trees, paprika, cotton, tobacco, fig fruit or citrus fruits.

The environmental conditions we have just mentioned, encourage the presence of an extraordinarily diverse flora. On acidic soils, a series of species stand out, living in Pyrenean oak forests, holm oak groves, cork oak forests, or *Pinus pinaster* woodlands. Among them is the recently discovered southern endemism of Gredos, *Linaria vettonica*, considered as Critically Endangered by the IUCN, with only one population known in Ávila. *Iberodes brassicifolia* is another noteworthy species, classified as Endangered by both the Junta de Castilla y León and Moreno (2008), with only two populations known in the Candeleda area. Other notable species in these forest environments are *Monotropa hypopitys*, *Neotinea lactea* subsp. *conica*, *Prunus lusitanica* subsp. *lusitanica*, which forms interesting relict forests in the tributary gorges of the Tiétar (López Sáez, 1995), *Rhaponticum exaltatum* and *Veronica micrantha*. In the wet meadows, riverside groves, reservoir tails, and ponds on sandy soils, there are also rare taxa such as *Anacamptis papilionacea* subsp. *expansa*, *Dictamnus albus*, *Epipactis tremolsii*, *Schenkia pusilla*, *Fuirena pubescens*, *Gratiola linifolia*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Isolepis fluitans*, *Littorella uniflora*, *Flueggea tinctoria*, *Narcissus jonquilla* subsp. *jonquilla* and *Succisella carvalhoana*, the latter classified as Vulnerable in Castilla y León.

Moreover, on the basic outcrops, especially in the municipalities of Arenas de San Pedro and Candeleda, there are very rare species in the province that need to be protected at local scale. This is the case of *Lysimachia ephemerum*, *Pentanema helenioides*, *P. salicinum*, *Magydaris panacifolia*, *Biarum arundanum* and several orchids of the genus *Ophrys*, such as *O. dyris*, *O. apifera*, *O. lutea* subsp. *lutea*, *O. sphegodes* and *O. tenthredinifera*. The survival of these species in Ávila depends on the implementation of measures to prevent the habitats in which they grow from being transformed, which is complex because many of them inhabit private areas.

Below, we present the annotated checklist of vascular plants in the Ávila province. The taxon names mainly follow the nomenclature adopted by Sáez & Aymerich (2021), in which the most recent works have been considered, both molecular phylogenies with a sufficient degree of consistency, and monographic morphological revisions published in recent years. In the many cases where names have changed recently, the synonym is given in parentheses after the accepted name.

Presented taxa are classified into four major groups 1) clubmosses (Lycopodiophytina subdivision), 2) ferns (Polypodiophytina subdivision), 3) gymnosperms (Coniferopsida class), and 4) angiosperms (Magnoliopsida class). This last group, following the results of molecular phylogenies (Stevens, 2001), has been further divided into three subgroups: primitive lineages of angiosperms, monocots, and dicots. Within each of the four groups, families, genera, and species are listed in alphabetical order.

After the taxon name (in italics and bold for native species), its presence or absence in each of the three areas into which we have divided the Ávila province (Figure 1) is indicated, as well as its chorological element. If the presence of the plant suggests reasonable doubt or we have not been able

to confirm it, we have placed a question mark (?) after the abbreviation of the territory (Gr: Gredos in the broad sense, Ma: Malagón range, and Mo: La Moraña and adjacent areas). When the taxon is included in any of the red lists, both regional (Catalogue of Protected Flora of Castilla y León; C and L) and national (Moreno, 2008; Bañares *et al.*, 2010; Moreno *et al.*, 2019; LRE), its degree of threat is indicated and, especially, when it is considered with any of the categories of threatened plants of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN): Near Threatened (NT), Vulnerable (VU), Endangered (EN) or Critically Endangered (CR). Finally, where appropriate, some aspects of their taxonomic identity, uncertainties regarding their presence in the province, etc., are discussed. When the name of a taxon appears only in italics and in quotation marks, we intend to convey that the plant has been recorded from Ávila, but we think that the citation was a mistake and, therefore, we reject the presence of that taxon in Ávila.

Materials and Methods

To compile this checklist, numerous field trips were conducted throughout the province of Ávila, during which the search and collection of taxa with taxonomic issues or uncertain presence in the province were carried out. Specimens resulting from these collections have been deposited at UPOS herbarium (Thiers, 2023). We have also consulted the provincial materials mainly those kept in the MA, MACB, MAF, SALA, and UPOS herbaria, which house the most significant collections in the Ávila region. Additionally, images available on the GBIF (www.gbif.org) and iNaturalist (www.inaturalist.org) platforms were also reviewed.

We have also carried out an intensive bibliographic search to obtain the provincial references of the different taxa, with special emphasis on those whose presence is doubtful. For this purpose, we relied on the GBIF and ANTHOS (www.anthos.es) databases, the essential work of *Flora iberica*, and other more locally focused floristic monographs that include the province (doctoral theses, botanical guides, etc.). On more than a few occasions, when the only provincial reference for a given taxon comes from its inclusion in *Flora iberica*, we have consulted, when possible, the authors of the syntheses involved.

For the elaboration of the floristic spectrum, we have basically followed the elements proposed by Aizpuru *et al.* (1999) and used by Bariego (2016), critically checking the global distribution in all cases using POWO (2024). In order to include a given taxon in a chorological element we have not considered the regions where it is considered introduced. It is worth noting that we are dealing with chorological elements in a broad sense. For example, we include in the Eurasian element taxa that are distributed over a large part of Europe, and temperate and cold regions of Asia (Eurosiberian), even if they also marginally inhabit North Africa and tropical regions of Asia. We have another example in the Iberian endemic element, in which we include the Iberian orophytes. In the Mediterranean element, we incorporate not only the taxa living in the Mediterranean basin, but also those extending into the Iranian-Turanian region. When a given taxon is distributed over wide areas of Europe, Asia, North Africa and some regions of

tropical and/or southern Africa, it has been included in the pluriregional element.

Results

Floristic checklist

Lycopodiophytina (clubmosses)

ISOETACEAE

Isoetes asturicensis (M. Laínz) M. Laínz (*I. velata* A. Braun subsp. *asturicensis* (M. Laínz) Rivas-Mart. & Prada)

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L)

Isoetes histrix Bory

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Isoetes longissima Bory (*I. velatum* A. Braun)

Gr / Mediterranean / NT (IUCN at European level)

LYCOPODIACEAE

Huperzia selago (L.) Schrank & C.F.P. Mart.

Gr / Boreo-alpine / VU (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Notes: According to the taxonomic treatment of the *Huperzia* genus by Björk (2020), the majority of the Iberian populations of this clubmoss belong to the species *H. europaea* Björk; however, populations in Gredos (La Serrota (Luceño *et al.*, 2000) and Laguna del Duque (UPOS11321) have a good fit for *H. selago* (Curtis Björk, pers. comm.).

Lycopodiella inundata (L.) Holub

Gr / Circumboreal / VU (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Notes: Only five populations are known for Gredos, four of them from Ávila (Navalguijo (Castroviejo *et al.*, 1983); Trampal gorge (Luceño *et al.*, 2000); Duque lagoon and Prao Puerto gorge (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019), and one from Salamanca (Hoyamoros cirque (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

SELAGINELLACEAE

Selaginella denticulata (L.) Spring.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Polypodiophytina (ferns)

ASPLENIACEAE

Asplenium adiantum-nigrum L. subsp. ***adiantum-nigrum***

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Asplenium billotii F.W. Schultz

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Asplenium ceterach L. subsp. ***ceterach*** (*Ceterach officinarum* DC. subsp. *officinarum*)

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Asplenium oopteris L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Asplenium quadrivalens (D.E. Meyer) Landlot (*A. trichomanes* L. subsp. *quadrivalens* D.E. Meyer)

Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Asplenium septentrionale (L.) Hoffm.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Asplenium trichomanes L.

Gr, Ma / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

ATHYRIACEAE

Athyrium distentifolium Opiz

Gr / Boreo-alpine / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A species commonly found in the Pyrenees and the Cantabrian Mountains. From the Central System, it is only known from very isolated locations in the central massif of Gredos (Rivas Martínez, 1985; Luceño & Vargas, 1990), making it a plant deserving of special protection.

Athyrium filix-femina (L.) Roth

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

BLECHNACEAE

Struthiopteris spicant (L.) F.W. Weiss subsp. ***spicant*** (*Blechnum spicant* (L.) Roth subsp. *spicant*)

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

CYSTOPTERIDACEAE

Cystopteris dickieana R. Sim

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Cystopteris fragilis (L.) Bernh. subsp. ***fragilis***

Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Gymnocarpium dryopteris (L.) Newman

Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Despite not being included in the list of threatened species in Castilla y León, this fern is extremely rare in the province, as only one population is known in the Ojos Albos mountain range (Martín Gil *et al.*, 2017), and therefore, it should be protected.

DENNSTAETIDIACEAE

Pteridium aquilinum (L.) Kuhn subsp. ***aquilinum***

Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

DRYOPTERIDACEAE

Dryopteris affinis (Lowe) Fraser-Jenk. subsp. ***affinis***

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Dryopteris borrieri (Newman) Oberh. & Tavel (*D. affinis* subsp. *borrieri* (Newman) Fraser-Jenk.)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Dryopteris dilatata (Hoffm.) A. Gray subsp. ***dilatata***

Gr?, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The presence of this species in the province was reported by Aldasoro (1975) from the Trampal gorge (Western massif of Gredos), but without herbarium evidence. However, it has been recently confirmed from Peguerinos (Bernal González, 2023). "*Dryopteris expansa* (C. Presl) Fraser-Jenk."

Notes: This species is distributed across the mountains of the northern half of the Iberian Peninsula. The records from Ávila (Rivas Martínez, 1981) have not been confirmed due to the absence of herbarium specimens. They were also not considered by Salvo & Arrabal (1986).

Dryopteris filix-mas (L.) Schott

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Dryopteris oreades Fomin

Gr / European orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Polystichum aculeatum (L.) Roth

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Polystichum lonchitis (L.) Roth

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Polystichum setiferum (Forssk.) Woyнар

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

EQUISETACEAE

Equisetum arvense L.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

"*Equisetum hyemale* L."

Notes: The records from Ávila of this taxon (Carrasco & Estrada, 1988; Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a) are actually confusions with sparsely branched forms of *E. ramosissimum* (J.A. Alejandre, pers. comm.).

Equisetum ramosissimum Desf. subsp.

ramosissimum

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

OPHIOGLOSSACEAE

Botrychium lunaria (L.) Swartz

Gr / Boreo-alpine / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province (Hoyo Malillo cirque (Rico Hernández & Romero Martín, 1984), Barco lagoon (Giráldez *et al.*, 1986), Zapatero peak (Luceño & Vargas, 1986), and the head of Los Conventos gorge (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Ophioglossum azoricum C. Presl

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very uncommon in the province (Castroviejo *et al.*, 1983).

Ophioglossum lusitanicum L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Ophioglossum vulgatum L.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very uncommon in the province (Martín Ballesteros *et al.*, 1994).

OSMUNDACEAE

Osmunda regalis L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

POLYPODIACEAE

Polypodium interjectum Shivas

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Polypodium vulgare L.

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

PTERIDACEAE

Adiantum capillus-veneris L.

Gr, Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Anogramma leptophylla (L.) Link

Gr, Ma / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Cryptogramma crista (L.) R. Br.

Gr / Boreo-alpine / LC (IUCN)

Oeosporangium hispanicum (Mett.) Fraser-Jenk. & Pariyar (*Cheilanthes hispanica* Mett.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Oeosporangium pteridioides (Reichard) Fraser-Jenk. & Pariyar (*Cheilanthes maderensis* Lowe)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Oeosporangium tinaei (Tod.) Fraser-Jenk. (*Cheilanthes tinaei* Tod.)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

SALVINIACEAE***Azolla filiculoides*** Lam. (*A. caroliniana* Willd.)

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to America which has naturalised in ponds and edges of eutrophic watercourses in the southern half of the province, where it behaves as a dangerous invasive species. It is included in the Spanish catalog of exotic invasive species.

Gymnosperms (class Coniferopsida)**CUPRESSACEAE*****Juniperus badia*** (H. Gay) Rivas Mart., Molero Mesa, Marfíl & G. Benítez (*Juniperus oxycedrus* subsp. *badia* (H. Gay) Debeaux)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Juniperus communis L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Juniperus thurifera L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A common species in the eastern areas of the Central System, which only reaches the province of Ávila in the municipality of El Barraco (Martín Gil *et al.*, 2017) and Sanchidrián (UPOS17435).

EPHEDRACEAE***Ephedra distachya*** L. subsp. *distachya*

Mo / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province was indicated by Arce Castilla (2002) from the municipality of Orbita. We now added the material collected in Blascosancho (UPOS12669).

PINACEAE***Pinus nigra*** J.F. Arnold subsp. *salzmanii* (Dunal)

Franco

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A relatively common species in the central and eastern massifs of Gredos, where it forms relict forests, sometimes alongside *P. sylvestris* (López Sáez *et al.*, 2016). It was recorded from the Sierra de Malagón by López Sáez *et al.* (2019) in the municipality of Hoyo de Pinares and it is also known from Las Navas del Marqués.

Pinus pinaster Aiton

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Pinus pinea L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Pinus ponderosa Douglas ex Lawson & C. Lawson

Gr / introduced

Pinus radiata D. Don

Gr / introduced

Pinus sylvestris L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

TAXACEAE***Taxus baccata*** L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Angiosperms (class Magnoliopsida)**Primitive angiosperm lineages****ARISTOLOCHIACEAE*****Aristolochia castellana*** (E. Nardi) A. Costa (*A. pallida* subsp. *castellana* E. Nardi)

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Aristolochia paucinervis Pomel (*A. longa* L. subsp. *paucinervis* (Pomel) Batt.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

NYMPHAEACEAE***Nymphaea alba*** L.†

Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: This water lily used to grow a few years ago in a pond near the train track in Guimorcondo (García Muñoz, 2004; UPOS16934), but it has disappeared because the pond was drained.

Monocots**ALISMACEAE*****Alisma lanceolatum*** With.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Alisma plantago-aquatica L.

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Baldellia alpestris (Coss.) M. Laínz

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Baldellia repens (Lam.) Ooststr. subsp. *cavanillesii* (J.A. Molina, A. Galán, J.M. Pizarro & Sardinero)

Talavera

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Damasonium polyspermum Coss.

Mo / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Luronium natans L.

Ma / Atlantic / Endangered (C and L), EN (LRE), EN (IUCN)

Notes: The presence of this nationally Endangered species in Ávila is limited to a small population in the municipality of Peguerinos (García Adá *et al.*, 1996). In 2019, we visited this population, which is in good health, although its extent is confined to a small section of a stream.

AMARYLLIDACEAE***Acis autumnalis*** (L.) Sweet (*Leucojum autumnale* L.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Allium guttatum subsp. *sardoum* (Moris) Stearn

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Allium dentiferum Webb & Berthel. (*A. paniculatum* auct., p.p.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Allium massaesylum Batt. & Trab.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Allium oleraceum L.

Gr, Mo / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Allium pallens L. (*A. stearnii* Pastor & Valdés)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / DD (IUCN)

Allium polyanthum Schult. & Schult. fil. (*A. ampeloprasum* subsp. *polyanthum* (Schult. & Schult. fil.) O. Bolòs, Vigo, Masalles & Ninot)
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Allium porrum L. (*A. ampeloprasum* auct., non L. p.p.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Allium roseum L.
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Allium sativum L.
Mo / introduced

Allium schoenoprasum L.
Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Allium scorzonerifolium DC.
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
Notes: In the province, it is known only from the eastern massif of Gredos (MA448952).

Allium sphaerocephalon L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Allium vineale L.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Narcissus bulbocodium L. subsp. *graellsii* (Webb ex Graells) K. Richt.)
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Narcissus bulbocodium L. subsp. *nivalis* (Graells) K. Richt.
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / DD (IUCN)

Narcissus cantabricus DC.
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Narcissus confusus Pugsley (*N. pseudonarcissus* L. subsp. *portensis* (Pugsley) A. Fern.)
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Narcissus coronatus DC. subsp. *coronatus* (*N. triandrus* L. subsp. *pallidulus* (Graells) Rivas Goday)
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Narcissus jonquilla L. subsp. *jonquilla*
Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Narcissus minor L. subsp. *minor* (*N. asturiensis* (Jord.) Pugsley; *N. minor* subsp. *asturiensis* (Jord.) Barra & G. López)
Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)
Notes: From Ávila, only one population is known in the western massif of Gredos (Palacios de Becedas).

Narcissus rupicola Schult. & Schult. fil.
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Sternbergia colchiciflora Waldst. & Kit.
Mo / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)
Notes: A rare species in the Iberian Peninsula, which in Ávila is found exclusively in Cantazorras (Arévalo; UPOS17026).

Sternbergia lutea (L.) Spreng.
Ma, Mo / introduced

ARACEAE

Arisarum simorrhinum Durieu (*A. vulgare* O. Targ.-Tozz. subsp. *simorrhinum* (Durieu) Maire & Weller)
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Arum cylindraceum Gasp.
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Arum italicum L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Biarum arundanum Boiss. & Reut.

Gr / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)
Notes: A very rare species in the province. Known only from the red soils of a basic nature in the Arenas de San Pedro area (SALA81886).

Lemna gibba L.
Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Lemna minor L.
Gr, Ma / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Spirodela polyrhiza (L.) Schleid.
Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)
Notes: We only know one locality for Ávila, on the border with Toledo (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

ASPARAGACEAE

Anthericum liliago L.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Asparagus acutifolius L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Asparagus officinalis L.
Mo / introduced

Cathissa concinna (Salisb.) Speta (*Ornithogalum concinnum* Salisb.)
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Convallaria majalis L.
Gr / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Dipcadi serotinum (L.) Medik. subsp. *serotinum*
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Hyacinthoides hispanica (Mill.) Rothm.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Loncomelos narbonense (L.) Raf. (*Ornithogalum narbonense* L.)
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Rare in the province. Found in San Pascual (UPOS16942), Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18343) and Arévalo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Loncomelos pyrenaicum (L.) J. Holub subsp. *pyrenaicum* (*Ornithogalum pyrenaicum* L. subsp. *pyrenaicum*)
Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Muscari comosum (L.) Mill.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Muscari matritense Ruiz Rejón, L. Pascual, C. Ruiz Rejón, Valdés & J.L. Oliv.
Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Muscari neglectum Ten.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ornithogalum bourgaeum Jord. & Fourr.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Paradisea lusitanica (Cout.) Samp.
Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Polygonatum odoratum (Mill.) Druce
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Prospero autumnale (L.) Speta (*Scilla autumnalis* L.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Ruscus aculeatus L.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / With regulated use (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Scilla verna subsp. *ramburii* (Boiss.) K. Richt.
Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Scilla verna Huds. subsp. *verna*
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Squilla maritima (L.) Steinh. (*Urginea maritima* (L.) Baker; *Charybdis maritima* (L.) Speta)
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Streptopus amplexifolius (L.) DC.
Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

ASPHODELACEAE

Asphodelus aestivus Brot.

Gr?, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Notes: There is not vouchers confirming the presence of this taxon in Gredos, although it is quite likely, as it has been confirmed in very nearby areas of the province of Madrid.

Asphodelus fistulosus L.

Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: We only know it from the urban area of Hoyo de Pinares (photographic evidence by A. Arribas in UPOS).

Asphodelus macrocarpus Parl. subsp. ***macrocarpus*** (*A. albus* Miller subsp. *villarsii* (Billot) I.B.K. Richardson & Smythies)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from Candeleda (MA487641).

Asphodelus oblongicarpus Luceño & García Muñoz (*A. bentorainhae* P. Silva subsp. *salmanticus* Z. Díaz & Valdés)

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN).

Notes: This is the most common species in the genus in Gredos, although it has frequently been confused with *A. albus* Mill. The name was published in Luceño *et al.* (2016).

Asphodelus serotinus Wolley-Dod

Ma, Mo? / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Confirmed in the province by Díaz Infante & Valdés (SEV129925), on the border of the Ojos Albos mountain range with La Moraña, between Aldeavieja and Villacastín.

Simethis mattiazzi (Vand.) Sacc. (*S. planifolia* (L.) Gren. & Godr.)

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: As far as we know, its presence in Ávila is limited to isolated locations within the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro.

BUTOMACEAE

Butomus umbellatus L.

Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province (Hernansancho; UPOS16775).

COLCHICACEAE

Colchicum montanum L. (*Merendera montana* (L.) Lange)

Gr, Ma, Mo / European orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Colchicum multiflorum Brot.

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. Its presence is only documented in the Castañar del Tiemblo (García Muñoz, 2009) and the Pescadores's Trail (Arenas de San Pedro; (photographic evidence in UPOS).

COMMELINACEAE

Commelina communis L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Frequently naturalised in gorges, irrigation ditches, and small streams within the municipality of Candeleda (J.L. Robles, pers. comm.).

Tradescantia fluminensis Vell.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in the Tiétar valley (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.).

Tradescantia pallida (Rose) D.R. Hunt

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in Casavieja y Lanzahíta (J.A. López Sáez, comm. pers.).

Tradescantia zebrina Heynh. ex Bose

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in Arenas de San Pedro (J.A. López Sáez, comm. pers.).

CYPERACEAE

Bolboschoenus glaucus (Lam.) S.G. Smith

Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Bolboschoenus maritimus (L.) Palla

Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Carex binervis Sm.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Carex caryophyllea Latourr.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Carex demissa Hornem. subsp. ***demissa***

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex depauperata Curtis ex Woodw.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Carex depressa Link

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Carex distachya Desf.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Carex distans L.

Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex disticha Huds.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex divisa Huds.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Carex divulsa Stokes

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex echinata Murray

Gr, Ma? / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Carex flacca Schreb. (incl. *C. flacca* subsp. *erythrostachys* (Hoppe) Holub (*C. flacca* subsp. *serrulata* (Spreng.) Greuter)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Carex hallerana Asso

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Carex hirta L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex lainzii Luceño, E. Rico & T. Romero

Mo / Iberian endemism / Endangered (C and L), EN

(LRE), EN (IUCN)

Notes: Endemic to the northern Iberian plateau, for which three populations have been recorded in La Moraña, two of which (Fontiveros and Velayos) appear to have become extinct due to anthropogenic habitat transformation. Currently, only population in El Oso remains (cf. Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Carex leporina L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex limosa L.

Gr / Circumboreal / Preferential attention (C and L),

VU (LRE), VU (IUCN)

Notes: A rare species in the whole of the Iberian Peninsula, which in Ávila has only one population in the vicinity of the Parador Nacional de Gredos.

Carex lucennoiberica Maguilla & M. Escudero (*C. furva* auct. hisp., non Webb)

Gr / Iberian endemism / VU (IUCN)

Notes: An Iberian mountain endemism with its most numerous populations in Gredos. It exclusively inhabits snow patches, snowmelt basins, and other locations where snow persists for a long time, between 1920 and 2520 m asl. Its easternmost population is located at the head of Los Conventos gorge, and the westernmost one is in the cirque of Hoyo Malillo.

Carex nigra subsp. *intricata* (Tineo ex Guss) Rivas-Mart.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Carex otrubae Podp. (*C. cuprina* auct., non (Heuff.) A. Kern.)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex pairae F.W. Schultz (*C. muricata* subsp. *pairae* (F.W. Schultz) Celak.; *C. muricata* auct., non L.; *C. muricata* subsp. *lamprocarpa* auct., non Celak.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex paniculata L. subsp. *lusitanica* (Schkuhr ex Willd.) Maire

Gr / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Carex pendula Huds.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The only reference to this species in the province was published by Sánchez-Villegas *et al.* (2019). Recently it has also been collected in Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18340).

“*Carex pseudocyperus* L.”

Notes: The only reference to this species in the province of Ávila is an old and imprecise record (“mountains near Ávila”) by Willk. & Lange (1861–1862). The nearest population to the province is located in the Cáceres part of the Tiétar valley (Talayueta; UPOS12416).

Carex remota L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Carex reuteriana Boiss. subsp. *reuteriana*

Gr, Ma? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Carex spicata Huds.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Carex vesicaria L.

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Cyperus brevifolius (Rottb.) Hassk.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to the tropics. Naturalised in the vicinity of Candeleda (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

Cyperus eragrostis Lam.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to America which is expanding in the province.

Cyperus flavescens L. (*Pycnus flavescens* (L.) Rchb.)

Gr, Ma? / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Cyperus fuscus L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Cyperus longus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / (IUCN)

Cyperus michelianus (L.) Link

Gr / Pluriregional / NT (IUCN at European level)

Eleocharis acicularis (L.) Roem. & Schult.

Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Notes: In the region, it is known only from the western massif of Gredos (Aldasoro, 1975; Luceño *et al.*, 2000).

Eleocharis multicaulis (Sm.) Desv.

Gr / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Eleocharis palustris (L.) Roem. & Schult. subsp. *palustris*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Eleocharis palustris subsp. *waltersii* Bures & Danihelka (*E. palustris* subsp. *vulgaris* Walters)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Eleocharis quinqueflora (Hartmann) O. Schwarz

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Eriophorum latifolium Hoppe

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Fimbristylis bisumbellata (Forssk.) Bubani

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Fuirena pubescens (Poir.) Kunth

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Isolepis cernua (Vahl) Roem. & Schult.

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Isolepis fluitans (L.) R. Br.

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A very rare hydrophyte in the province, with its presence limited to only one population located in the municipal area of Candeleda (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Isolepis setacea (L.) R. Br.

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Rhynchospora alba (L.) Vahl

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Schoenoplectiella supina (L.) Lye

Mo / Pluriregional / NT (IUCN-Mediterranean level)

Notes: Very rare in the province, known only from the municipality of Madrigal de las Altas Torres (SALA36538).

Schoenoplectus lacustris (L.) Palla

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani (C.C. Gmel.) Palla (*Schoenoplectus lacustris* subsp. *glaucus* (Sm. ex Hartm.) Bech)

Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Scirpoides holoschoenus (L.) Soják subsp. *holoschoenus* (incl. *Scirpoides holoschoenus* subsp. *australis* (L.) Soják)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Trichophorum cespitosum (L.) Hartm.

Gr / Boreo-alpine / LC (IUCN)

DIOSCOREACEAE

Dioscorea communis (L.) Caddick & Wilkin (*Tamus communis* L.)

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

IRIDACEAE

Crocus carpetanus Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

“*Crocus nevadensis* Amo & Campo ex Amo”

Notes: The only information we have about the presence of this basophilic saffron in the province is the reference to “Av” in *Flora iberica* (Guillén, 2013). We have contacted the author responsible for the treatment of the genus in the aforementioned work, but it has not been possible to locate the herbarium specimen that served as evidence, so we

provisionally rule out the presence of the species in Ávila.

Crocus serotinus Salisb.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Gladiolus communis L. (incl. *Gladiolus illyricus* W.D.J Koch)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Iris germanica L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Iris pseudacorus L. (*Limniris pseudacorus* (L.) Fuss)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Iris xiphium L. (*Xiphion vulgare* Mill.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Romulea bulbocodium (L.) Sebast. & Mauri

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Romulea ramiflora Ten. subsp. *ramiflora*

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

JUNCACEAE

Juncus acutiflorus Hoffm.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Juncus acutus L. subsp. *acutus*

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The presence of this species in the province is confirmed by the specimen collected in 1915 by Delesert in the Amblés valley (G147132; Romero Zarco, pers. comm.).

Juncus alpino-articulatus Chaix subsp. *alpino-articulatus*

Gr / Circumboreal / (IUCN)

Notes: It has been confirmed for the province only from Los Barrerones, in the central massif of Gredos (MA467303).

Juncus articulatus L. subsp. *articulatus*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Juncus bufonius L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Juncus bulbosus L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Juncus capitatus Weigel

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Juncus compressus Jacq.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Juncus conglomeratus L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Much rarer than the following species, with which it has often been confused. We are only aware of it from Los Llanos de Tormes (UPOS13160).

Juncus effusus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Juncus foliosus Desf.

Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in Ávila is confirmed for the specimen collected in San Pascual and identified by C. Romero Zarco (UPOS18423)

Juncus fontanesii Laharpe subsp. *fontanesii*

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province, known only from El Oso (SALA33522).

Juncus gerardi Loisel.

Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Juncus heterophyllus Dufour

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Juncus hybridus Brot.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Juncus inflexus L. subsp. *inflexus*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Juncus minutulus Prain

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Juncus pygmaeus Thuill.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Juncus ranarius Songeon & E.P. Perrier

Mo / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only known voucher confirming the presence of this halophilic taxon in the province comes from Rasueros (MACB25020; Romero Zarco, pers. comm.).

Juncus squarrosus L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Juncus striatus E. Mey.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Juncus tenageia L. f.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Juncus tenuis Willd.

Gr / introduced

Notes: A native plant from North America that shows stable populations at various locations in the central and western massifs of Gredos.

Luzula campestris (L.) DC.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian/ NE (IUCN)

Luzula forsteri (Sm.) Lam. & DC. subsp. *forsteri*

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Luzula lactea (Link) E. Mey.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Luzula multiflora (Ehrh.) Lej. subsp. *multiflora*

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Luzula spicata (L.) DC.

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Luzula sylvatica (Huds.) Gaudin subsp. *sylvatica*

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

LILIACEAE

Fritillaria lusitanica Wikstr. subsp. *lusitanica*

Ma / Iberian endemism/ NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only populations that we know for Ávila are located in Santa María del Cubillo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Fritillaria pyrenaica L. subsp. *falcata* (E. Rico) R. Alonso, de Paz & M.E. García (*F. caballeroi* F.M. Vázquez)

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Gagea bohemica (Zauschn.) Schult. & Schult. f.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Gagea ellyptica (A. Terracc.) Prain

Gr / Mediterranean / DD (IUCN)

Gagea pratensis (Pers.) Dumort.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Gagea reverchonii Degen

Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Gagea soleirolii F.W. Schultz

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Lilium martagon L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Tulipa sylvestris L. subsp. *australis* (Link.) Pamp.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

MELANTHIACEAE

Paris quadrifolia L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Veratrum album L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

ORCHIDACEAE

Anacamptis coriophora (L.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase subsp. **coriophora** (*Orchis coriophora* L.)

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Anacamptis laxiflora (Lam.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase (*Orchis laxiflora* Lam. subsp. *laxiflora*)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A rare orchid in the province. Known only from the southern slope of the main Gredos mountain range (MA706251; UPOS17640).

Anacamptis morio (L.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase (*Orchis morio* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NT (IUCN)

Anacamptis papilionacea (L.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase subsp. **expansa** (Ten.) Amard. & Dusa (*Orchis papilionacea* L.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in Ávila. Known only from the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Cephalanthera longifolia (L.) Fritsch

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Cephalanthera rubra (L.) Rich.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare. It has been found only in two locations in Ávila, the Pinar de Hoyocasero (Luceño & Vargas, 1987) and the Castañar del Tiemblo (MA562387).

Dactylorhiza elata (Poir.) Soó subsp. **sesquipedalis** (Willd.) Soó

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Dactylorhiza insularis (Sommier) Landwehr

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Dactylorhiza maculata (L.) Soó subsp. **maculata** (*Orchis maculata* L. subsp. *maculata*)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Epipactis phyllanthes G.E. Sm. (*E. fageticola* (C.E. Hermos.) Devillers-Tersch. & Devillers)

Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / Preferential attention (C and L), VU (LRE), LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. We are aware of only a few individuals in the municipality of Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022).

Epipactis tremolsii Pau (*E. helleborine* (L.) Crantz subsp. *tremolsii* (Pau) E. Klein)

Gr / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Gymnadenia conopsea (L.) R. Br.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only record of this orchid in the Central System comes from the Pinar de Hoyocasero (Luceño & Vargas, 1987; MA321755); however, we have made persistent efforts over the past 20 years and have not succeeded in locating it again, so it may have become extinct.

Himantoglossum robertianum (Loisel.) P. Delforge

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in Villanueva de Gómez and the surrounding of the city of Ávila (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Limodorum abortivum (L.) Sw.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Neotinea lactea (Poir.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase subsp. **conica** (Willd.) J. Ponert, P. Trávníček & Chumová (*Orchis conica* Willd.)

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Neotinea maculata (Desf.) Stearn

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The first record of this species (quite common in the Tiétar valley) for the province of Ávila was reported by Vargas (1987).

Neotinea ustulata (L.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase (*Orchis ustulata* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Neottia nidus-avis (L.) Rich.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Ophrys apifera Huds.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the basic clays of the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Ophrys dyris (= *O. fusca* Link subsp. *dyris* (Maire) Soó)

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known exclusively from the basic clays of the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Ophrys lutea Cav.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the basic clays in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Ophrys speculum Link subsp. **speculum**

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. It has been collected recently in the San Pascual area (UPOS17433).

Ophrys sphegodes Mill.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the basic clays in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019) and the limestones of Cantazorras, near Arévalo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Ophrys tenthredinifera Willd.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known from various localities in the Tiétar valley, on both acidic and basic soils (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Orchis langei K. Richt.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Orchis mascula L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Serapias cordigera L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Municipality of Candeleda (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Serapias lingua L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Serapias parviflora Parl.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Spiranthes aestivalis (Poir.) Rich.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / Preferential attention (C and L), DD (IUCN)

Spiranthes spiralis (L.) Chevall.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

POACEAE

Achnatherum bromoides (L.) P. Beauv. (*Stipa bromoides* (L.) Dörfli.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Aegilops geniculata Roth

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

- Aegilops neglecta*** Bertol.
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Aegilops triuncialis*** L.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Aeluropus littoralis*** (Gouan) Parl.
Mo / Pluriregional / Preferential attention (C and L)
Notes: A halophilic species known exclusively in the endorheic lagoon of San Pascual (UPOS16953).
- Agropyron cristatum*** (L.) Gaertn.
Mo / introduced
Notes: Rare in the Arévalo area (UPOS16950).
- Agrostis canina*** L. subsp. ***canina***
Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Agrostis capillaris*** L. subsp. ***capillaris***
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Agrostis castellana*** Boiss. & Reut.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Agrostis nebulosa*** Boiss. & Reut. (*Neoschischkinia nebulosa* (Boiss. & Reut.) Tzvelev)
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
Notes: A very rare basophilic species in the province; in fact, it is only known from the Amblés valley, the classic locality of this species.
- Agrostis pourretii*** Willd. (*Neoschischkinia pourretii* (Willd.) Valdés & H. Scholz)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Agrostis rupestris*** All.
Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)
- Agrostis stolonifera*** L.
Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)
- Agrostis tenerrima*** Trin. (*Neoschischkinia elegans* (Thore) Tzvelev)
Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NT (IUCN)
Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed by the voucher SALA162314.
- Agrostula truncatula*** (Parl.) P.M. Peterson, Romasch., Soreng & Sylvester subsp. ***truncatula*** (*Agrostis truncatula* Parl.)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
“*Aira caryophyllea* L.”
Notes: This taxon has been abundantly cited in the province due to confusion with *A. multiculmis*, but it has not been considered for Ávila by Sáez *et al.* (2020). We provisionally discarded its presence in the province.
- Aira cupaniana*** Guss.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Aira multiculmis*** Dumort. (*A. caryophyllea* L. subsp. *multiculmis* (Dumort.) Bonnier & Layens)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Aira praecox*** L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Airopsis tenella*** (Cav.) Coss. & Durieu
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Alopecurus aequalis*** Sobol.
Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)
- Alopecurus arundinaceus*** Poir.
Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Alopecurus geniculatus*** L.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Alopecurus myosuroides*** Huds.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Andropogon distachyos*** L.
Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)
- Anthoxanthum ovatum*** Lag. subsp. ***aristatum*** (Boiss.) Litard. (*A. aristatum* Boiss.)
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Anthoxanthum odoratum*** L.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Antinoria agrostidea*** (Lam. & DC.) Parl. subsp. ***agrostidea***
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Antinoria agrostidea*** subsp. ***natans*** (Hack.) Rivas Mart.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Apera interrupta*** (L.) P. Beauv.
Gr, Ma? / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Arrhenatherum album*** (Vahl) W.D. Clayton subsp. ***album*** (incl. *A. elatius* subsp. *erianthum* (Boiss. & Reut.) Trab.)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Arrhenatherum elatius*** subsp. ***bulbosum*** (Willd.) Schübl. & G. Martens
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Arrhenatherum elatius*** (L.) J. Presl & C. Presl subsp. ***elatius***
Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Arundo donax*** L.
Gr / introduced
Notes: Native to Asia, it has been cultivated since ancient times and has naturalized in much of the Iberian Peninsula. Relatively common in the Tiétar valley.
- Avena barbata*** Pott ex Link
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Avena castellana*** (Romero Zarco) Romero Zarco
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: We know it only from the locality of Poyales del Hoyo (UPOS11842).
- Avena fatua*** L. subsp. ***fatua***
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Avena lusitanica*** (Tab. Morais) Baum
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Avena sativa*** L.
Mo / introduced
- Avena sterilis*** subsp. ***ludoviciana*** (Durieu) Gillet & Magne (*A. ludoviciana* Durieu)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The characteristics used to distinguish this subspecies from the previous one refer to the length of the spikelets, lemma, and awns. In the territory, there are populations with individuals whose measurements fall within the lower limit of subsp. *sterilis* and the upper limit of subsp. *ludoviciana*, making them difficult to categorise as either race.
- Avena sterilis*** L. subsp. ***sterilis***
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
- Avenella flexuosa*** (L.) Drejer (*Deschampsia flexuosa* (L.) Trin.)
Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / DD (IUCN)
- Avenula pubescens*** (Huds.) Dumort. subsp. ***pubescens***
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: This species is known in the province from the municipalities of Junciana (Sánchez Villegas *et al.*, 2019) and Navalperal de Tormes (UPOS18336).
- Brachypodium distachyon*** (L.) P. Beauv.
Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)
- Brachypodium phoenicoides*** (L.) Roem. & Schult.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Brachypodium sylvaticum*** (Huds.) P. Beauv. subsp. ***sylvaticum***
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Briza maxima L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Briza media L. subsp. ***media***

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Briza minor L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Bromus catharticus Vahl

Gr / introduced

Notes: A native species from South America that we have recently collected in the vicinity of El Barco de Ávila (UPOS17581).

“*Bromus commutatus* Schrad.”

Notes: Even though this species has been reported for the province by Sánchez Mata (1989) and Acedo & Llamas (2021), all Iberian materials identified as *B. commutatus* actually belong to *B. racemosus* (Romero Zarco, 2023). Therefore, we rule out the presence of this species in the province.

Bromus diandrus Roth

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Bromus hordeaceus L. subsp. ***hordeaceus*** (*B. mollis* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Bromus intermedius Guss.

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only reference to this species in the province is provided by *Flora iberica* (Acedo & Llamas, 2021), but we have not been able to locate the reference specimen.

Bromus madritensis L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Bromus pseudothominei P.M. Sm. (*B. hordeaceus* subsp. ***pseudothominei*** (P.M. Sm.) H. Scholz)

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only evidence of the presence of this species in the province is the specimen LEB49086 from Moraleja de Matcabras, which we have not had the opportunity to study.

Bromus racemosus L. subsp. ***racemosus***

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Bromus ramosus Huds.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

“*Bromus rigidus* Roth”

Notes: This species has been reported for the province by Fuertes Lasala (1989b) and Acedo & Llamas (2021), but all materials we have collected belong to similar *B. diandrus*. Therefore, the presence of *B. rigidus* in Ávila should be confirmed (cf. Romero Zarco, 2023).

Bromus rubens L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Bromus scoparius L.

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Bromus squarrosus L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Bromus sterilis L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Bromus tectorum L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Catapodium rigidum (L.) C.E. Hubb. (*Desmazeria rigida* (L.) Tutin subsp. ***rigida***)

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Celtica gigantea (Link) F.M. Vázquez & Barkworth (*Stipa gigantea* Link)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Corynephorus canescens (L.) P. Beauv.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Corynephorus divaricatus (Pourr.) Breistr. (*C. fasciculatus* Boiss. & Reut.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Cynosurus cristatus L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Cynosurus echinatus L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Cynosurus effusus Link (*C. elegans* auct., non Desf.)

Gr, Ma? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Dactylis glomerata L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Danthonia decumbens (L.) DC. subsp. ***decumbens***

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Deschampsia cespitosa (L.) P. Beauv. subsp. ***cespitosa*** (*D. caespitosa* subsp. ***hispanica*** Vivant)

Gr, Ma / Subcosmopolitan / NE (IUCN)

Digitaria ischaemum (Schreb.) Muhl.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province (El Raso; UPOS10118).

Digitaria sanguinalis (L.) Scop.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Echinaria capitata (L.) Desf.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Echinochloa crus-galli (L.) P. Beauv.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Elymus caninus (L.) L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Elymus repens (L.) Gould subsp. ***repens***

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Eragrostis barrelieri Daveau

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Eragrostis cilianensis (All.) Janch.

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Eragrostis curvula (Schrad.) Nees

Gr / introduced

Eragrostis minor Host

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Eragrostis pilosa (L.) P. Beauv.

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Eragrostis virescens J. Presl

Gr / introduced

Notes: A native plant from South America. Its presence in Ávila is confirmed from Villafranca mountain range (UPOS14279) and El Barco de Ávila (UPOS14278).

Festuca albaredae (Paunero) G. López (*Micropyrum patens* (Brot.) Pilg.)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Festuca ambigua Le Gall subsp. ***ambigua*** (*Vulpia ciliata* Dumort.)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Festuca ampla Hack.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The numerous records of this species in Ávila (Sardinero Roscales, 1994) were not considered by *Flora iberica* (Devesa et al., 2020); however, its presence in Ávila has been recently confirmed (Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2022a).

Festuca arundinacea Schreb. subsp. ***arundinacea*** (*Schedonorus arundinaceus* (Schreb.) Dumort. subsp. ***arundinaceus***)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Festuca bromoides L. (*Vulpia bromoides* (L.) Gray) Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Festuca delicatula Lag. (*Ctenopsis delicatula* (Lag.) Paunero)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Festuca durandoi Clauson subsp. **capillifolia** (Willk.) Rivas Ponce, Cebolla & M.B. Crespo (*Patzkea durandoi* (Clauson) G.H. Loos subsp. *capillifolia* (Willk.) H. Scholz)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / (IUCN)

Festuca elegans Boiss.
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Festuca geniculata (L.) Lag. & Rodr. (*Vulpia geniculata* (L.) Link)
Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Festuca incurva (Gouan) Gutermann (*Psilurus incurvus* (Gouan) Schinz & Thell.)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Festuca inops De Not. subsp. **inops**
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Festuca interrupta Desf. (*Schedonurus interruptus* (Desf.) Tzvelev)
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Rare in the province. Collected in San Pascual (UPOS18547), Rinconada and San Pedro del Arroyo (de la Fuente & Ortuño Rubio (1996).

Festuca lachenalii (C.C. Gmel.) Spenn. (*Micropyrum tenellum* (L.) Link)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Festuca lambinonii Kerguelen (*F. rivasmartinezii* Fuente & Ortúñez)
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Festuca maritima L. subsp. **maritima** (*Vulpia unilateralis* (L.) Stace subsp. *unilateralis*)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Festuca membranacea (L.) Druce subsp. **membranacea** (*Vulpia membranacea* (L.) Dumort.; *V. pyramidata* (Link) Rothm.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Festuca myuros L. (*Vulpia myuros* (L.) C.C. Gmel.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Festuca paniculata (L.) Schinz & Thell. subsp. **multispiculata** Rivas Ponce & Cebolla (*Patzkea paniculata* (L.) G.H. Loos subsp. *multispiculata* (Rivas Ponce & Cebolla) H. Scholz)
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Festuca perennis (L.) Columbus & J.P. Sm. (*Lolium perenne* L.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Festuca rivularis Boiss.
Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Festuca romerozarcoi Devesa & Martínez-Sagarra (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.)
Gr / introduced
Notes: Although Ruiz de Clavijo & Devesa (2020) considered this species for Ávila, we do not know the materials on which they were based, so, given that it is a rare species in the province, we now confirm its presence in it with the voucher collected in Candeleda (UPOS18342).

Festuca rothmaleri (Litard.) Markgr.-Dann.
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Festuca trichophylla subsp. **iberica** (Hack.) E. López & Devesa (*F. iberica* (Hack.) K. Richt.)
Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Festuca vettonica Fuente, Ortúñez & Ferrer
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Festuca willkommii Devesa & Martínez-Sagarra (*Lolium rigidum* Gaudin)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Festuca yvesii subsp. **summilusitana** (Franco & Rocha Afonso) Mart.-Sagarra & Devesa (*F. granitcola* Kerguelen & Morla; *F. gredensis* Fuente & Ortúñez)
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Gastridium phleoides (Nees & Meyen) C.E. Hubb.
Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Gaudinia fragilis (L.) P. Beauv.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Glyceria declinata Bréb.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Glyceria fluitans (L.) R. Br.
Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Helictochloa albinervis subsp. **gaditana** (Romero Zarco) Romero Zarco
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Helictochloa bromoides (Gouan) Romero Zarco subsp. **bromoides** (*Avenula bromoides* (Gouan) H. Scholz subsp. *bromoides*)
Gr / Mediterranean / (IUCN)

Helictochloa marginata (Lowe) Romero Zarco (*Avenula sulcata* (Boiss.) Dumort.)
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Helictotrichon thorei Röser (*Pseudarrhenatherum longifolium* (Thore) Rouy)
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The only evidence of the presence of this species in Ávila is the voucher MA186150, whose label exclusively states “Sierra de Gredos”. This specimen has been the basis for the inclusion of Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Romero Zarco, 2021a).

Holcus annuus subsp. **setiglumis** (Boiss. & Reut.) M. Seq. & Castrov.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Holcus gayanus Boiss.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Holcus lanatus L. subsp. **lanatus**
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Holcus mollis L.
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Holcus reuteri Boiss.
Gr, Ma? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Hordeum geniculatum All. (*H. hystrix* Roth)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Hordeum glaucum Steud. (*H. murinum* L. subsp. *glaucum* (Steud.) Tzvelev)
Gr, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Since this species is very similar to *H. murinum* –very difficult to distinguish in the field– and has been frequently confused with it, its distribution in Ávila requires intensive collections to be accurately determined. So far, we know it from the municipalities of San Bartolomé de Tormes (UPOS18307), Junciana (UPOS18344) and El Barco de Ávila (UPOS18309).

Hordeum marinum Huds.
Gr?, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
Notes: A species common in saline and subsaline soils, often found in the endorheic lagoons of La Moraña. The records from the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989b) might correspond to *H. geniculatum*.

Hordeum murinum subsp. **leporinum** (Link) Arcang. (*H. leporinum* Link)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Hordeum murinum L. subsp. **murinum**
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Hordeum secalinum Schreb.

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Since this species, as well as *H. glaucum*, is very similar to *H. murinum* and has been frequently confused with it, its distribution in Ávila still needs to be determined precisely.

Hyparrhenia sinaica (Delile) G. López (*H. hirta* subsp. *pubescens* (Vis.) Paunero)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Imperata cylindrica (L.) Raeusch.

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Koeleria crassipes Lange

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Koeleria vallesiana (Honck) Gaudin

Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: recently found in Cantazorras, near Arévalo (SALA178858).

Lamarckia aurea (L.) Moench

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Melica ciliata L. subsp. *ciliata*

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only reference to this taxon in the province (Estrada Sánchez, 1986) indicates its presence in the Villafranca mountain range, but Cantó *et al.* (2020) have not seen any voucher from Ávila province. Its presence in Ávila is now confirmed from Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS12232).

Melica ciliata subsp. *magnolii* (Gren. & Godr.) K. Richt.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Melica minuta L. subsp. *minuta*

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: As far as we know, there are no records of this species in the province; however, *Flora iberica* (Cantó *et al.*, 2020) considers it as present. This species prefers limestone crevices and scree.

Melica uniflora Retz.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Mibora minima (L.) Desv. subsp. *minima*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Milium vernale subsp. *montianum* (Parl.) K. Richt.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Milium vernale M. Bieb. subsp. *vernale*

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Molineriella laevis (Brot.) Rouy

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Molineriella minuta (L.) Rouy

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Molinia arundinacea Schrank

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Nardus stricta L.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Oloptum miliaceum (L.) Röser & Hamasha (*Piptatherum miliaceum* (L.) Coss.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Panicum capillare L. subsp. *capillare*

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to North America. In the province of Ávila, it is known only from the Burguillo reservoir (UPOS17047).

Panicum miliaceum L. subsp. *miliaceum*

Gr / introduced

Parapholis cylindrica (Willd.) Romero Zarco (*Hainardia cylindrica* (Willd.) Greuter)

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Parapholis incurva (L.) C.E. Hubb. (*Lepturus incurvus* (L.) Druce; *Pholiurus incurvus* (L.) Schinz & Thell.)

Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Paspalum dilatatum Poir.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to South America. Sporadically naturalised in the Tiétar valley.

Paspalum distichum L. (*P. paspalodes* (Michx.) Scribn.)

Gr, Mo / introduced

Periballia involucrata (Cav.) Janka

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Phalaris arundinacea L.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Phalaris canariensis L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A species only known in the province from the vicinity of El Barco de Ávila (UPOS17642).

Phalaris coerulescens Desf.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Sporadic in the Tiétar valley.

Phalaris paradoxa L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Sporadic in the Tiétar valley.

Phleum phleoides (L.) H. Karst.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Phleum pratense L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Pholiurus pannonicus (Host) Trin.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Phragmites australis (Cav.) Steud. subsp. *australis*

Gr, Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Poa annua L. subsp. *annua*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Poa bulbosa L. subsp. *bulbosa*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Poa cenisia All.

Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The high-altitude populations are not typical forms of *P. cenisia* (Ortega Olivencia, pers. comm.) but exhibit intermediate characteristics between this species and *P. nemoralis*. We are conducting a morphological and molecular study to clarify the taxonomic status of these populations, which are distributed in rock crevices in the high peaks of the Iberian Central System.

Poa infirma Kunth

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Poa legionensis (M.Laínz) Fern.-Casas & M.Laínz

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Poa ligulata Boiss.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18348).

Poa nemoralis L. subsp. *nemoralis*

Gr, Mo / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Poa pratensis L. subsp. *pratensis*

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Poa supina Schrad.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Poa trivialis L. subsp. *trivialis*

Gr, Ma, Mo? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Polypogon maritimus Willd. subsp. *maritimus*

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Polypogon monspeliensis (L.) Desf.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Puccinellia fasciculata (Torr.) E. P. Bicknell

Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Puccinellia festuciformis subsp. ***lagascana*** M.A. Juliá & J.M. Monts.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Puccinellia hispanica Juliá & J.M. Monts.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Puccinellia pungens (Pau) Paunero

Mo / Iberian endemism / Endangered (C and L), VU (LRE), VU (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the vicinity of Velayos (SALA58106).

Puccinellia rupestris (With.) Fernald. & Weath.

Gr, Mo / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A halophytic taxon frequently found in La Moraña, and that we have surprisingly collected it in ditches at the Pico mountain pass, an area with acid soils. This is likely due to the salt applications made to clear the road of snow.

Rostraria cristata (L.) Tzvelev (*Lophochloa cristata* (L.) Hyl.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Schismus barbatus (L.) Thell.

Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A rare taxon in the province (Adaja hills; MACB12162 and SALA335538, and Riocabado; SALA65832).

“*Sclerochloa dura* (L.) P. Beauv.”

Notes: Cited in the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989b), but there does not appear to be any other provincial references or herbarium evidence justifying the presence of this species in the province. Therefore, we provisionally exclude its presence in the area.

Secale cereale L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crops break.

Secale strictum (C. Presl) C. Presl (*S. montanum* Guss.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Setaria parviflora (Poir.) Kerguélen (*S. geniculata* P. Beauv.)

Gr / introduced

Setaria verticillata (L.) P. Beauv.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Setaria viridis (L.) P. Beauv.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Sorghum halepense (L.) Pers.

Gr / introduced

Sphenopus divaricatus (Gouan) Rchb. subsp. ***divaricatus***

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare taxon in the province. Known from El Oso (SALA21066).

Sporobolus alopecuroides (Piller & Mitterp.) P.M. Peterson (*Crypsis alopecuroides* (Piller & Mitterp.) Schrad.)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Sporobolus indicus (L.) R. Br.

Gr / introduced

Notes: A species native to certain tropical and subtropical regions, which has not been recorded in the province, and for which we do not have seen vouchers. However, it is considered in *Flora iberica* (Muñoz Rodríguez, 2021) as present in the province, probably in the Candeleda area, as we are aware of its presence in the eastern part of the La Vera region (UPOS16479).

Sporobolus schoenoides (L.) P.M. Peterson (*Crypsis schoenoides* (L.) Lam.)

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Stipa iberica Martinovský (*S. pennata* auct., non L.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Stipa juncea L. (*S. lagascae* auct., non Roem. & Schult.; *S. celakovskyi* Martinovský)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Stipellula capensis (Thunb.) Röser & Hamasha (*Stipa capensis* Thunb.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Taeniatherum caput-medusae (L.) Nevski

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Thinopyrum intermedium (Host) Barkworth & D.R. Dewey (*Elymus hispidus* (Opiz) Melderis)

Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known from Flores de Ávila (SALA164854) and Crespos (SALA164841).

Thinopyrum obtusiflorum (DC.) Banfi (*Elymus obtusiflorus* DC.)

Gr, Ma / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in Salobral (SALA164832 and 184836) and Berrocalejo de Aragona (SALA s/n).

Trisetaria ovata (Pers.) Paunero

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Trisetum flavescens (L.) P. Beauv. subsp. ***flavescens***

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Triticum aestivum L. subsp. ***aestivum***

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Triticum boeoticum Boiss.

Mo / introduced

Notes: We thank E. Luengo for informing us of the discovery of this wheat in Cantazorras (Arévalo), whose presence in the province is supported by the voucher SALA168931.

Triticum turgidum L. subsp. ***durum*** (Desf.) Husn.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Triticum turgidum L. subsp. ***turgidum***

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Ventenata dubia (Leers) Coss.

Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. San Bartolomé de Pinares (SALA49982).

Zea mays L. subsp. ***mays***

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in the south of the province (Hontanares and Lanzahita).

POTAMOGETONACEAE

Groenlandia densa (L.) Fourr. (*Potamogeton densus* L.)

Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, it is only known from Guimorcondo in the Sierra de Ojos Albos (García Muñoz, 2009; MA732971).

Potamogeton berchtoldii Fieber

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare, found in isolated locations in the central and eastern massifs of Gredos (Sánchez Mata, 1989).

Potamogeton crispus L.

Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the Las Cogotas reservoir, near the city of Ávila (García Muñoz, 2004).

Potamogeton natans L.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Potamogeton polygonifolius Pourr.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Potamogeton trichoides Cham. & Schtdl.

Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from Guimorcondo, in the Sierra de Ojos Albos (García Muñoz, 2009).

Zannichellia pedunculata Rchb.

Mo / Pluriregional / NE

Notes: This halophilic hydrophyte has been collected only once in the province (SALA43885).

TYPHACEAE**Sparganium angustifolium** Michx.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Sparganium erectum subsp. *microcarpum*

(Neuman) Domin

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Typha domingensis Pers.

Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Typha latifolia L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Dicots**AMARANTHACEAE****Amaranthus albus** L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Amaranthus blitum L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Amaranthus deflexus L.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Amaranthus emarginatus Uline & W.L. Bray (A.*blitum* subsp. *emarginatus* (Uline & W.L. Bray)

Carretero, Muñoz Garm. & Pedrol)

Gr / introduced

Amaranthus graezicans subsp. *sylvestris* (Vill.)Brenan (*A. angustifolius* auct., non Lam.)

Mo / Pluriregional / (IUCN)

Amaranthus hybridus L. (*A. cruentus* auct., non L.)

Gr, Mo / introduced

Amaranthus powellii S. Watson (incl. *A. bouchonii* Thell.)

Gr, Mo / introduced

Amaranthus retroflexus L.

Gr, Mo? / introduced

Atriplex patula L. (*A. littoralis* auct.)

Gr, Mo / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Atriplex prostrata DC. (*A. hastata* auct.)

Mo / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Atriplex rosea L.

Mo? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not found any voucher supporting the presence in Ávila as indicated by *Flora iberica* (Castroviejo, 1990).**Blitum bonus-henricus** (L.) Rchb. (*Chenopodium bonus-henricus* L.)

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Blitum petiolare Link (*Chenopodium exsuccum* (Losc.) Uotila)

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not seen records or herbarium specimens from the province; however, it is

considered present in Ávila according to *Flora iberica* (Uotila, 1990).**Camphorosma monspeliaca** (L.) Voss subsp. *monspeliaca*

Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Chenopodium murale (L.) S. Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch (*Chenopodium murale* L.)

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Chenopodium album L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Chenopodium opulifolium W.D.J. Koch & Ziz

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Chenopodium vulvaria L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Dysphania ambrosioides (L.) Mosyakin & Clemants (*Chenopodium ambrosioides* L.)

Gr / introduced

Dysphania botrys (L.) Mosyakin & Clemants (*Chenopodium botrys* L.)

Gr, Mo? / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Dysphania multifida (L.) Mosyakin & Clemants (*Chenopodium multifidum* L.)

Gr / introduced

Dysphania pumilio (R. Br.) Mosyakin & Clemants (*Chenopodium pumilio* R. Br.)

Gr, Mo / introduced

Oxybasis chenopodioides (L.) S. Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch (*Chenopodium chenopodioides* (L.) Aellen;*Ch. rubrum* subsp. *crassifolium* (Hornem.) Maire)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Oxybasis rubra (L.) S. Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch (*Chenopodium rubrum* L.)

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Oxybasis urbica (L.) S. Fuentes, Uotila & Borsch (*Chenopodium urbicum* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Polycnemum arvense L. (*P. majus* auct., non A. Braun)

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known in the province exclusively from Arévalo (SALA168928).

Salsola tragus L. (*S. kali* subsp. *tragus* (L.) Čelak.; *S. kali* subsp. *ruthenica* auct.)

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: This should be the correct name of the plants growing in ruderal inland areas of the Iberian Peninsula (cf. Mosyakin, 2017).

ANACARDIACEAE**Pistacia terebinthus** L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

APIACEAE**Ammoides pusilla** (Brot.) Breistr.

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A rare species in Ávila. Its presence in the province is confirmed by the voucher UPOS17434, collected from Cantazorras (Arévalo).

Angelica laevis Fisch., C.A. Mey. & Avé-Lall. (*A. major* sensu auct. iber., non Lag.)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Angelica sylvestris L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Anthriscus caucalis M. Bieb.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Anthriscus sylvestris* L.**

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Bupleurum gerardi* All. (incl. *B. virgatum* Cav.)**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Bupleurum rigidum* subsp. *paniculatum* (Brot.) H. Wolff**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Species cited by Ladero *et al.* (1985) in Carrascalejo. Its presence in the province is accepted by Neves (2003). There is also an herbarium voucher at HSS from Los Pescadores pathway (Arenas de San Pedro) that we have not seen.

***Bupleurum rotundifolium* L.**

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the vicinity of Arévalo (Cantazorras; UPOS17444).

***Bupleurum semicompositum* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known from El Oso (SALA90388) and Papatrigo (SALA90401).

***Bupleurum tenuissimum* L.**

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Recently collected in El Oso (UPOS16955).

***Caucalis platycarpus* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Chaerophyllum hirsutum* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Species known in the province only from the Villafranca mountain range (Castroviejo *et al.*, 1983).

***Chaerophyllum temulum* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Conium maculatum* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Conopodium bunioides* (Boiss.) Calest.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Conopodium majus* subsp. *marizianum* (Samp.) López Udias & Mateo**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Conopodium pyrenaicum* (Loisel.) Miégev.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Conopodium subcarneum* (Boiss. & Reut.) Boiss. & Reut.**

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Daucus carota* L. subsp. *carota

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Daucus carota* subsp. *sativus* (Hoffm.) Schübl. & G. Martens**

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break throughout the province.

***Daucus crinitus* Desf.**

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Daucus durieua* Lange**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Daucus junceus* (Willk.) Mart. Flores & M.B. Crespo (*Daucus setifolius* sensu *Flora iberica*, non Desf.)**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Reported from various points at the base of Gredos (Martínez-Flores *et al.*, 2019).

***Epikeros pyrenaicus* (L.) Raf. (*Selinum pyrenaicum* (L.) Gouan)**

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Eryngium bourgatii* Gouan**

Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Eryngium campestre* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Eryngium galioides* Lam.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / EN (IUCN)

***Eryngium tenue* Lam.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Ferula communis* subsp. *catalaunica* (C. Vicioso) Sánchez Cuxart & Bernal**

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Ferulago capillaris* (Spreng.) Cout.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Helosciadium inundatum* (L.) W.D.J. Koch (*Apium inundatum* (L.) Rchb. f.)**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Helosciadium nodiflorum* (L.) W.D.J. Koch (*Apium nodiflorum* (L.) Lag.)**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Helosciadium repens* (Jacq.) W.D.J. Koch (*Apium repens* (Jacq.) Lag.)**

Gr / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), VU (IUCN, at Mediterranean level)

Notes: Species known in the province only from the vicinity of Navarredonda de Gredos (Molina Abril, 1996).

***Heracleum sphondylium* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NT (IUCN)

***Hohenackeria exscapa* (Steven) Koso-Pol.**

Mo / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), NT (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Notes: A plant characteristic of steppe areas. Known in the province only from Arévalo (MA629377, SALA103105).

***Hohenackeria polyodon* Coss. & Durieu**

Mo / Mediterranean / VU (C and L), VU (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Notes: Like the previous species, this is a plant characteristic of steppe areas and known in the province only from Arévalo (SALA98416, BCN124349).

***Imperatoria ostruthium* L. (*Peucedanum ostruthium* (L.) W.D.J. Koch)**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province, only known from Barranco de las Cinco Villas (Tiétar valley; MA357237 and MA357313).

***Magydaris panacifolia* (Vahl) Lange**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, this taxon has been only found in the basic clays of the town of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

***Meum athamanticum* Jacq.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Myrrhoides nodosa* (L.) Cannon**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Oenanthe crocata* L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

***Oenanthe lachenalii* C.C. Gmel.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recorded from the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989b; Molina, 1996). Also known from Solosancho (MAF158559).

Oenanthe pimpinelloides* L. subsp. *pimpinelloides

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in Candeleda (UPOS18346)

***Oenanthe silaifolia* M. Bieb.**

Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Oreoselinum nigrum* Delarbre (*Peucedanum oreoselinum* (L.) Moench)**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the municipality of El Arenal (SALA32522).

"*Orlaya platycarpus* W.D.J. Koch (*O. daucooides* (L.) Greuter)"

Notes: Recorded for the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989b), but there are no herbarium records confirming the presence of this species in the province. Due to its similarity to *Caucalis platycarpus*, we believe there might have been a confusion.

Petroselinum crispum (Mill.) Fuss.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break.

Physospermum cornubiense (L.) DC.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Pimpinella major (L.) Huds.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Pimpinella tragium Vill. (incl. *P. tragium* subsp. *litophila* (Schischk.) Tutin)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, it only inhabits the municipality of Hoyocasero (Rico Hernández, 1985).

Pimpinella villosa Schousb.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Prangos trifida (Mill.) Herrnst. & Heyn (*Cachrys trifida* Mill.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Sanicula europaea L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Scandix australis subsp. *microcarpa* (Lange) Thell.

Gr?, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cited by Fuertes Lasala (1989b) in the mountain passes of Menga and Villatoro, but not considered by *Flora iberica* (Pujadas Salvá, 2003a). We have seen a voucher from Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS16928). It is also present in Arévalo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Scandix pecten-veneris L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Smyrniolum olusatrum L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Uncommon on the southern slopes of Gredos (Sánchez Mata *et al.*, 1988).

Smyrniolum perfoliatum L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Thapsia foetida L. (*Elaeoselinum foetidum* (L.) Boiss.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only known population in the province is located in Guisando (García Muñoz, 2009).

Thapsia gummifera (Desf.) Spreng. (*Margotia gummifera* (Desf.) Lange)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Thapsia minor Hoffmanns. & Link

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Thapsia nitida Lacaita

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: After the phylogenetic study by Weitzel *et al.* (2014) it seems to be clear that the two varieties of *Thapsia nitida* Lacaita accepted by Pujadas Salvá (2003b) deserve to be considered in the species range; however, Weitzel *et al.* (o.c.) described *Th. simittii* to include populations with glabrous or barely hairy petioles and pinnatifid leaves, which correspond, according to these same authors and Pujadas Salvá (o.c.), with var. *nitida*, so the correct name at the species level, according to the priority

principle, must be *Thapsia nitida* Lacaita, which makes *Th. simittii* Simonsen *et al.* a superfluous name. On the other hand, Pujadas Salvá (o.c.), probably relying on what was published by Bayer & López González (1996), considers that *Thapsia maxima* Mill. could be based on a specimen of unknown origin cultivated by Miller, so it does not consider this name as attributable to an Iberian plant. However, the neotypification of Miller's name carried out by Weitzel *et al.* (o.c.) on Portuguese materials morphologically ascribable to var. *meridionalis* Pujadas (more or less densely hairy petioles and pinnatisect leaves), converts *Th. maxima* and *Th. nitida* var. *meridionalis* in synonyms. The presence of *Th. nitida* in the province is supported by the vouchers MA721522, collected in Mombeltrán, and SALA128759 from the surrounding of Ávila city.

Thapsia villosa L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Tordylium maximum L.

Gr, Ma?, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Torilis africana Spreng. (*T. arvensis* subsp. *purpurea* (Ten.) Hayek)

Gr, Ma? / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Torilis arvensis (Huds.) Link subsp. *neglecta* (Spreng.) Thell.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Torilis arvensis subsp. *recta* Jury

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Torilis elongata (Hoffmanns. & Link) Samp.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Torilis japonica (Houtt.) DC.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Torilis leptophylla (L.) Rchb. f.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Torilis nodosa (L.) Gaertn.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Trocodaris verticillatum (L.) Raf. (*Carum verticillatum* (L.) W.D.J. Koch)

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Turgenia latifolia (L.) Hoffm.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Uncommon in La Moraña (SALA137119).

APOCYNACEAE

Vinca difformis Pourr. subsp. *difformis*

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently collected in Candeleda (UPOS16900).

Vinca major L. subsp. *major*

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recorded from the southern slope of Gredos (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Vincetoxicum nigrum (L.) Moench

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

AQUIFOLIACEAE

Ilex aquifolium L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

ARALIACEAE

Hedera helix L. subsp. *helix*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Hedera hibernica (G. Kirchn.) Bean

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

ASTERACEAE

Achillea filipendulina Lam.

Gr / introduced

Achillea millefolium L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Achillea odorata L.

Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not found specific records of this taxon for the province, nor herbarium specimens, although it is considered for the province in *Flora iberica* (Soriano, 2019).

Adenostyles alliariae (Gouan) A. Kern. subsp. ***alliariae***

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Anacyclus clavatus (Desf.) Pers.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Andryala arenaria* (DC.) Boiss. & Reut.”

Notes: The citation by Molina Moreno (1992) could be based on a confusion with *A. rothia*. *Flora iberica* (Talavera & M. Talavera, 2017) does not include it as present in the province, although it is known from Toledo and Salamanca.

Andryala integrifolia L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Andryala ragusina L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Andryala rothia Pers. (*A. laxiflora* DC.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Anthemis alpestris (Hoffmanns. & Link) R. Fern.

Gr, Ma? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Anthemis arvensis L. subsp. ***arvensis***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Anthemis cotula L.

Gr, Ma?, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Anthemis pedunculata subsp. ***turoleensis*** (Pau ex Caball.) Oberpr.

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Basiphyle species recently found in Cantazorras (Arévalo; SALA178841).

Arctium minus (Hill) Bernh.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Arctotheca calendula (L.) Levyns

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to South Africa, it has been recently found at the mouth of the Arbillas gorge on the Tiétar river (photographic testimony by L. Sánchez Benz in UPOS).

Arnoseris minima (L.) Schweigg. & Körte

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Artemisia absinthium L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Artemisia campestris L. (incl. *A. campestris* subsp. *glutinosa* (Besser) Batt.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Artemisia verlotiorum Lamotte

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to China, it has been recently recorded from the southern slopes of Gredos (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Artemisia vulgaris L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Asteriscus aquaticus (L.) Less.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Asteriscus spinosus (L.) Schulz Bip. subsp.

spinosus (*Pallenis spinosa* (L.) Cass. subsp. *spinosus*)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Atractylis humilis* L.”

Notes: Although this taxon has been cited in the province (Molina & Izco, 1986; Fuertes Lasala, 1989b), it appears that there are no vouchers to support these records. We provisionally rule out the presence of this species in the province.

Bellis annua L. subsp. ***annua***

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A thermophilic species known exclusively from the southern slope of Gredos (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Bellis perennis L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Bellis sylvestris subsp. ***pappulosa*** (DC.) Coste

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Bellis sylvestris Cirillo subsp. ***sylvestris***

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We only know it from the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS13752).

Bidens aurea (Aiton) Sheriff

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in several places of the Tiétar valley. Recently collected in Candeleda (UPOS17639).

Bidens frondosa L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in the Tiétar valley (Lazaro Bello, 2012).

Bidens pilosa L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: We only know it as naturalised in the Fuentes Claras reservoir (UPOS17046).

Bidens tripartita L.

Gr, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Bombycilaena discolor (Pers.) M. Laínz

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Bombycilaena erecta (L.) Smoljan. (*Micropus erectus* L.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Calendula arvensis (Vaill.) L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Calendula officinalis L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Carduus bourgeanus Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma?, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Carduus carpetanus Boiss. & Reut. subsp. ***carpetanus***

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Carduus platypus subsp. ***granatensis*** (Willk.) Nyman

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Carduus platypus Lange subsp. ***platypus***

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Carduus pycnocephalus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Carduus tenuiflorus Curtis

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Carlina corymbosa subsp. ***hispanica*** (Lam.) O. Bolòs & Vigo

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Carlina racemosa L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Carlina vulgaris L. subsp. ***spinosa*** (Velen.) Vandas

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Presence confirmed in the province by the voucher MA640721, collected from the Pico mountain pass.

- Carthamus lanatus*** L.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea alba*** L. subsp. ***alba***
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea amblensis*** Graells subsp. ***amblensis***
Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea aristata*** Hoffmanns. & Link
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea aspera*** L. subsp. ***aspera***
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea avilae*** Pau
Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), VU (LRE), EN (IUCN)
- Centaurea benedicta*** (L.) L. (*Cnicus benedictus* L.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / DD (IUCN)
- Centaurea calcitrapa*** L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea cyanus*** L. (*Cyanus segetum* Hill)
Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced
- Centaurea graminifolia*** (Lam.) Muñoz Rodr. & Devesa
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea jacea*** subsp. ***angustifolia*** (DC.) Gremli
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Cited by Rico Hernández (1985).
- Centaurea janeri*** Graells subsp. ***janeri***
Gr / Iberian endemism / DD (IUCN)
- Centaurea langei*** subsp. ***kheilii*** (Pau) E. López, Devesa & Arnelas
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea melitensis*** L.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea nigra*** subsp. ***carpetana*** (Boiss. & Reut.) Nyman
Gr, Ma? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea ornata*** Willd.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Centaurea solstitialis*** L. subsp. ***solstitialis***
Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Collected in Cabizuela (UPOS14293) and photographed around Arévalo.
- Chamaemelum fuscatum*** (Brot.) Vasc.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Chamaemelum nobile*** (L.) All.
Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)
- Chondrilla juncea*** L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Cichorium intybus*** L. subsp. ***intybus***
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Cirsium arvense*** (L.) Scop.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Cirsium odontolepis*** DC.
Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Abundantly cited for the province, most of these references are confusions with *C. vulgare*. We only know it from Las Navas del Marqués (photographic evidence in UPOS).
- Cirsium palustre*** (L.) Scop.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Cirsium pyrenaicum*** (Jacq.) All.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Cirsium vulgare*** (Savi) Ten.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Cladanthus mixtus*** (L.) Chevall.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Coleostephus myconis*** (L.) Rchb. f.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Cota triumfettii*** (L.) J. Gay (*Anthemis triumfetti* (L.) DC.)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Crepis albida*** Vill.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Crepis capillaris*** (L.) Wallr. (*C. virens* subsp. *capillaris* (L.) Cout.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Crepis lampsanoides*** (Gouan) Tausch
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Crepis pulchra*** L. subsp. ***pulchra***
Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: This basophile species has been recently found in El Oso (UPOS16936) and Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18341).
- Crepis taraxacifolia*** Thuill. (*C. vesicaria* auct., non L.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Crupina vulgaris*** Cass.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Dittrichia graveolens*** (L.) Greuter
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Dittrichia viscosa*** (L.) Greuter subsp. ***viscosa***
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: A thermophilic and nitrophilic species recently introduced to the province, where it is becoming increasingly common in ditches.
- Doronicum carpetanum*** Willk. subsp. ***carpetanum***
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Doronicum carpetanum*** subsp. ***kuepferi*** (R. Chacón) Alv. Fern.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Doronicum plantagineum*** L.
Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Erigeron acris*** L.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Erigeron bonariensis*** L. (*Conyza bonariensis* (L.) Cronq.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced
- Erigeron canadensis*** L. (*Conyza canadensis* (L.) Cronq.)
Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced
- Erigeron karvinskianus*** DC.
Gr / introduced
- Eupatorium cannabinum*** L. subsp. ***cannabinum***
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Filago arvensis*** L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Filago carpetana*** (Lange) Chrtek & Holub (*Evax carpetana* Lange)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Filago lutescens*** Jord.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Filago pygmaea*** L. (*Evax pygmaea* (L.) Brot.)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Filago pyramidata*** L.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Galactites tomentosus*** Moench
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Galatella aragonensis*** (Asso) Nees (*Aster aragonensis* Asso)
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Galatella linosyris*** (L.) Rchb. f. (*Aster linosyris* (L.) Bernh.)
Ma / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)
Notes: Very rare in the province. Cited from the Sierra de Ojos Albos (Martín Gil *et al.*, 2017).

“Galatella sedifolia (L.) Greuter”

Notes: Recorded from Navalperal de Tormes (Luceño et al., 2000), but this was a confusion with *G. aragonensis*.

Galinsoga parviflora Cav

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to South America. It has been recently found in Junciana (UPOS12559) and Candeleda.

Glebionis segetum (L.) Fourr. (Chrysanthemum segetum L.)

Gr / introduced

Gnaphalium uliginosum L. (Filaginella uliginosa (L.) Opiz)

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Hedypnois rhagadioloides (L.) F.W. Schmidt subsp. rhagadioloides

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Helianthus tuberosus L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break (Lázaro Bello, 2012).

Helichrysum serotinum (DC.) Boiss. subsp. serotinum

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Helichrysum stoechas (L.) Moench

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Helminthotheca echioides (L.) Holub (Picris echioides L.)

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Hieracium amplexicaule L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Common in granite crevices of the high Gredos.

“Hieracium aragonense Scheele subsp. aragonense”

Notes: Despite its presence being indicated in the province (Mateo et al., 2017; Mateo et al., 2023), we have contacted Dr. G. Mateo, and he has not found a voucher that confirms it as a plant native to Ávila. Furthermore, since it is a taxon specific to limestone crevices and scree, which are scarce in Ávila, we tentatively discarded its presence in the territory.

Hieracium festinum Jord.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Confirmed by the specimen UPOS16920, collected in the Villatoro mountain pass, and identified by Gonzalo Mateo.

Hieracium glaucinum Jord. (H. praecox Schultz.-Bip.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The specimen UPOS16935 (cement on the wall of the Duque lake dam) is the only testimony we have of the presence of this taxon in the province.

Hieracium jurassicum Griseb.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Mateo et al. (2023) include under this binomial the plants that were described from Pinar de Hoyocasero as *H. gredense* Rouy, although they have not been observed again since the 1980s.

Hieracium lachenalii Suter

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The specimens VAL69148 (Cuevas del Valle) and MA553604 (between Candeleda and Arenas de San Pedro), identified by G. Mateo, confirm the presence of this species in Ávila.

Hieracium maculatum Schrank

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: G. Mateo (pers. comm.) includes under this binomen the population from Pinar de Hoyocasero that was identified as *H. laevigatum* Willd. by other

authors (Ladero et al., 1985) or as *H. saxifragum* (LEB1982, identified by G. Mateo).

Hieracium sabaudum L. (incl. H. carpetanum Freyn, non Willk.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: This is the most common species in the province, although it does not seem to extend beyond the limits of Gredos.

“Hieracium saxifragum Fr.”

Notes: Despite its recorded presence in Ávila (Mateo et al., 2017; Mateo et al., 2023) based on materials from Pinar de Hoyocasero, all the specimens we have collected in the mentioned forest have been identified by G. Mateo as *H. maculatum*. However, the specimen LEB1982, from the same population, was identified by this specialist as *H. saxifragum*. G. Mateo has recently indicated to us that he considers the individuals from Hoyocasero to be closer to the species of Schrank than to *H. saxifragum*, so we discard the presence of the latter in the province.

Hieracium schmidtii Tausch

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Common in the high areas of Gredos.

Hieracium vestitum Gren. & Godron (incl. H. carpetanum willk.)

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A species belonging to the *H. schmidtii* group, known in the province from the summits of the Sierra de Béjar (UPOS16910; specimen identified by G. Mateo).

Hispidella hispanica Lam.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Hypochaeris glabra L.

Gr, Ma?, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Hypochaeris radicata L. subsp. radicata

Gr, Ma, Mo? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Jacobaea adonidifolia (Loisel.) Mérat (Senecio adonidifolius Loisel.)

Gr, Ma / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Jacobaea erucifolia (L.) G. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb. subsp. erucifolia (Senecio erucifolius L.)

Gr?, Ma? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not found any voucher nor record for this species, although Calvo & Aedo (2019) consider it as present in Ávila.

Jacobaea minuta (Cav.) Pelsner & Veldkamp (Senecio minutus (Cav.) DC.)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Jacobaea vulgaris Gaertn. (Senecio jacobaea L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Jurinea humilis (Desf.) DC.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Klasea integrifolia subsp. integrifolia (Vahl) Greuter

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

“Lactuca perennis L. subsp. perennis”

Notes: We have not found any voucher that confirms the record of this species for the province (Villatoro pass; Fuertes Lasala, 1989b). Mejías (2017) has doubts regarding its presence in Ávila.

Lactuca sativa L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break.

Lactuca serriola L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

- Lactuca tenerrima** Pourr.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Lactuca viminea** (L.) J. Presl & C. Presl subsp. **viminea**
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Lactuca virosa** L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Lapsana communis** L.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Leontodon hispidus** subsp. **bourgaeanus** (Willk.) Rivas Mart. & Sáenz de Rivas
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Leucanthemopsis boissieri** Pedrol
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: This species was recently reported for Ávila (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).
- Leucanthemopsis pallida** (Mill.) Heywood subsp. **pallida**
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Leucanthemopsis pulverulenta** (Lag.) Heywood
Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Leucanthemum ircutianum** DC.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Leucanthemum pallens** (Perreyem.) DC.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Leucanthemum pseudosylvaticum** (Vogt) Vogt & Oberpr.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Leucanthemum vulgare** Lam.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Logfia gallica** (L.) Coss. & Germ. (*Filago gallica* L.)
Gr, Ma? / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Logfia minima** (Sm.) Dumort. (*Filago minima* (Sm.) Pers.)
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Mantiscalca salmantica** (L.) Briq. & Cavill.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
- Matricaria chamomilla** L. (*Chamomilla recutita* (L.) Rauschert)
Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
- Matricaria discoidea** DC.
Gr / introduced
- Omalotheca supina** (L.) DC. (*Gnaphalium supinum* L.)
Gr / Boreo-alpine / NE (IUCN)
- Omalotheca sylvatica** (L.) Sch. Bip. & F. W. Schultz (*Gnaphalium sylvaticum* L.)
Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)
- Onopordum acanthium** L. subsp. **acanthium**
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Onopordum illyricum** L. subsp. **illyricum**
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Onopordum nervosum** Boiss.
Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Recently collected in Arévalo (UPOS18347).
- Pentanema helenioides** (DC.) D. Gut. Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E. Rico & M. M. Mart. Ort. (*Inula helenioides* DC.)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Recently cited from basic clay soils in Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).
“*Pentanema montanum* (L.) D. Gut. Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E. Rico & M. M. Mart. Ort.” (*Inula montana* L.)
Ma? / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Santos-Vicente *et al.*, 2019) is based on a specimen collected in San Bartolomé de Pinares; however, the authors of the treatment believe that it could be a labelling error on the specimen (E. Rico, pers. comm.).
- Pentanema salicinum** (L.) D. Gut. Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E. Rico & M. M. Mart. Ort. (*Inula salicina* L.)
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Pentanema squarrosus** (L.) D. Gut. Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E. Rico & M. M. Mart. Ort. (*Inula conyzae* (Griess.) DC.); *Pentanema conyzae* (Griess.) D. Gut. Larr., Santos-Vicente, Anderb., E. Rico & M. M. Mart. Ort.)
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: We only know it from the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (SALA166857; UPOS18060).
- Phagnalon saxatile** (L.) Cass.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Picnomon acarna** (L.) Cass. (*Cirsium acarna* (L.) Moench)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Picris hieracioides** L.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella argyrocoma** F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella capillata** (Arv.-Touv.) Mateo (*Hieracium pseudopilosella* subsp. *tenuicaule* Nägeli & Peter)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella castellana** (Boiss. & Reut.) F.W. Sch. & Sch. Bip. (*Hieracium castellanum* Boiss. & Reut.)
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella pseudopilosella** (Ten.) Soják (*Hieracium pseudopilosella* Ten.)
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella saussureoides** Arv.-Touv. (incl. *P. tardans* (Peter) Soják)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella subtardans** (Nägeli & Peter) Soják (*Hieracium tardans* subsp. *subtardans* Nägeli & Peter)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Pilosella vahlii** (Froel.) F. W. Schultz & Sch. Bip.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Podospermum laciniatum** (L.) DC.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum** (L.) Hilliard & B. L. Burt (*Helichrysum luteoalbum* (L.) Rchb.; *Gnaphalium luteoalbum* L.)
Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)
- Pseudopodospermum hispanicum** (L.) Zaika, Sukhor. & N. Kilian (*Scorzonera hispanica* L.)
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
- Pulicaria arabica** (L.) Cass. subsp. **hispanica** (Boiss.) Murb. (*Pulicaria paludosa* Link)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Rhagadiolus edulis** Gaertn.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Rhagadiolus stellatus** (L.) Gaertn.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Less common in the province than the previous species. Its distribution is likely restricted to the southern slopes of the central Gredos massif. A voucher from the Pelayo river, between Arenas de San Pedro and Poyales del Hoyo, serves as evidence (MACB77934).
- Rhaponticum coniferum** (L.) Greuter subsp. **coniferum** (*Leuzea conifera* (L.) DC.)
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Rhaponticum exaltatum (Willk.) Greuter (*Leuzea exaltata* Willk.)
Gr / Mediterranean / VU (C and L)

Santolina oblongifolia Boiss.
Gr / Iberian endemism / With regulated use (C and L), NT (IUCN)

Santolina rosmarinifolia L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Scolymus hispanicus L. (incl. *S. hispanicus* L. subsp. *occidentalis* F.M. Vázquez)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Scorzonera angustifolia L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Scorzoneroides carpetana (Lange) Greuter subsp. *carpetana* (*Leontodon carpetanus* Lange)
Gr, Ma? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Senecio altissimus Mill. (*S. doria* auct., non L.)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Senecio gallicus Vill.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Senecio lividus L.
Gr, Ma? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Senecio nebrodensis L.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Senecio pyrenaicus L.
Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Senecio sylvaticus L.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Senecio vulgaris L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Silybum marianum (L.) Gaertn.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Solidago virgaurea L.
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Soliva sessilis Ruiz & Pav. (*S. pterosperma* (Juss.) Less.)
Gr / introduced
Notes: Native to South America. It has been recently cited from the southern part of the province (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Sonchus asper (L.) Hill
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Sonchus oleraceus L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Sonchus tenerrimus L.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Recently observed in Fuentes Claras reservoir (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Staehelina dubia L.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: In the province, it is only known from basic soils in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (García Muñoz, 2009).

Symphotrichum squamatum (Spreng.) G. L. Nesom (*Aster squamatus* (Spreng.) Hieron.)
Gr, Ma?, Mo / introduced

Tagetes minuta L.
Gr / introduced
Notes: Native to South America. Sporadically crop break.

Tanacetum corymbosum (L.) Sch. Bip.
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Tanacetum mucronulatum (Hoffmanns. & Link) Heywood
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Tanacetum parthenium (L.) Sch. Bip.
Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to the Eastern Mediterranean and the Caucasus. Frequently garden break.

Taraxacum braun-blanquetii Soest
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The only evidence we have of the presence of this taxon in Ávila are the vouchers UPOS16811, collected in the Plataforma de Gredos, and UPOS16795, from Navalperal de Tormes, both identified by A. Galán.

Taraxacum castellanum Sonk
Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Microspecies of the *T. marginellum* H. Lindb. group recorded in *Flora iberica* (Galán-de-Mera, 2017) for Ávila, but for which we have not found precise citations in the province.

Taraxacum dubium Soest
Gr? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The presence of this species in Ávila is probable, since we have found it in the province of Salamanca, a few meters from the provincial border with Ávila. (UPOS14393).

Taraxacum ekmanii Dahlst.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: We know this taxon from Pinar de Hoyocasero (UPOS16917) and Navalperal de Tormes (UPOS16807). The materials have been identified by A. Galán.

Taraxacum fontanum Hand.-Mazz.
Gr / euroasiático / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Known until now from the provinces of León and Orense, we have found a population on stream banks in the municipality of Navarredonda de Gredos (UPOS16921).

Taraxacum hispanicum H. Lindb.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The only testimony of its presence in Ávila we know is the specimen UPOS16808, collected in Navacepeda de Tormes and identified by A. Galán.

Taraxacum horridifrons Rail.
Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The only testimony in the province we have is the specimen (UPOS18357), collected in Candeleda and identified by A. Galán.

Taraxacum infidulum G.E. Haglund & Saarsoo
Gr / Eurasian / (IUCN)
Notes: The only testimony we know is the specimen UPOS16809, collected in the Plataforma de Gredos and identified by A. Galán.

Taraxacum malato-belizii Soest
Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: We do not know other provincial references apart from the mention of Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Galán-de-Mera, 2017).

Taraxacum mimuloides H. Lindb.
Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The only provincial reference we are aware of is the mention of Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Galán-de-Mera, 2017).

Taraxacum nevadense H. Lindb.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Taraxacum obovatum (Willd.) DC.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Taraxacum pinto-silvae Soest
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The specimens from Hoyocasero (UPOS16813), Hoyos del Espino (UPOS16817), and Navalperal de Tormes (UPOS16799) have been identified by A. Galán.

Taraxacum schroeterianum Hand.-Mazz.

Gr? / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We are not aware of any other provincial citations besides the mention of Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Galán-de-Mera, 2017).***Tephroseris balbisiana*** (DC.) Holub subsp. ***coincyi*** (Rouy) P. Vargas & Luceño (*T. elodes* (DC.) Holub subsp. *coincyi* (Rouy) Aedo; *Senecio coincyi* Rouy)

Gr / Iberian endemism / VU (C and L), VU (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Thrinicia hispida Roth (*Leontodon taraxacoides* (Vill.) Mérat subsp. *hispidus* (Roth) Kerguélen)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Thrinicia saxatilis (Lam.) Holub & Moravec (*Leontodon saxatilis* Lam.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Thrinicia tuberosa (L.) DC. (*Leontodon tuberosum* L.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Tolpis barbata (L.) Gaertn.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Tolpis umbellata Bertol. (*T. barbata* subsp. *umbellata* (Bertol.) Jahand. & Maire)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Tragopogon angustifolius Willd.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently recorded from the basic clays of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).***Tragopogon castellanus*** Levier

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Tragopogon dubius Scop.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Tragopogon lamottei Rouy

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Tragopogon porrifolius L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Tripleurospermum inodorum (L.) Sch. Bip.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A rare plant that in the province is only known from the surroundings of Ávila city (García Muñoz, 2004) and Cerro de la Cruz del Hierro (Alberto Arribas, pers. comm.).

Urospermum picroides (L.) F.W. Schmidt

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Vogtia microphylla (DC.) Oberpr. & Sonboli (*Tanacetum microphyllum* DC.)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Xanthium orientale L. (incl. subsp. *italicum* (Moretti) Greuter)

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Xanthium spinosum L. (*Acanthoxanthium spinosum* (L.) Fourr.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Xanthium strumarium L. (incl. subsp. *brasilicum* (Vell.) O. Bolòs & Vigo)

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Xeranthemum inapertum (L.) Mill.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

BALSAMINACEAE***Impatiens balfourii*** Hook. F.

Gr / introduced

BETULACEAE***Alnus lusitanica*** Vít, Douda & Mandák

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / DD (IUCN)

Betula celtiberica Rothm. & Vasc. (*B. pubescens* subsp. *celtiberica* (Rothm. & Vasc.) Rivas Mart.)

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Betula pendula subsp. ***fontqueri*** (Rothm.) G. Moreno & Peinado

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), CR (LRE), EN (IUCN)

Corylus avellana L.

Gr, Ma? / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

BIGNONIACEAE***Catalpa bignonioides*** Walter

Mo / introduced

Notes: A species native to the southeastern United States, which is frequently cultivated in the Iberian Peninsula. In Ávila, it has become naturalised on the banks of the Cardeña river in Aldeavieja del Cubillo.

BORAGINACEAE***Amsinckia calycina*** (Moris) Chater

Mo / introduced

Amsinckia lycopsoides (Lehm.) Lehm.

Gr / introduced

Anchusa arvensis (L.) M. Bieb. subsp. ***arvensis*** (*Lycopsis arvensis* L.)

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Anchusa azurea Mill.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Anchusa undulata L. subsp. ***undulata***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Asperugo procumbens L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Borago officinalis L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Buglossoides arvensis (L.) I. M. Johnst. subsp. ***arvensis*** (*Lithospermum arvense* L. subsp. *arvense*)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Cerintho major L. subsp. ***major*** (*C. gymnandra* Gasp.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Cynoglossum creticum Mill.

Gr, Ma?, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Cynoglossum dioscoridis Vill.

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not found any voucher nor record from Ávila for this taxon. However, it is considered to be present in Ávila by *Flora Iberica* (Aizpuru, 2012).***Cynoglossum officinale*** L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Echium asperrimum L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Uncommon in La Moraña (UPOS16903).

Echium flavum Desf.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Echium plantagineum L.

Gr, Ma? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Echium salmanticum Lag.

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Echium vulgare subsp. ***pustulatum*** (Sm.) Bonnier & Layens (*Echium pustulatum* Sm.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Echium vulgare L. subsp. ***vulgare***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Glandora prostrata (Loisel.) D.C. Thomas subsp. ***prostrata***
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Iberodes brassicifolia (Lag.) M. Serrano, R. Carbajal & S. Ortiz (*Omphalodes brassicifolia* (Lag.) Sweet)
Gr / Iberian endemism / Endangered (C and L), EN (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Lithospermum officinale L.
Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis arvensis (L.) Hill. subsp. ***arvensis***
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis balbisiana Jord.
Gr? / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The BCN22886 herbarium specimen, collected in the Laguna Grande de Gredos, seems to be the only testimony of its presence in Ávila (Valdés, 2012). However, this work attributes a maximum altitude of 1700 m asl to the species, while the mentioned lagoon is located at 1920 m asl. Furthermore, as it is a species of gall oak forests and their replacement shrubs, we believe its presence in the province should be confirmed.

Myosotis debilis Pomel
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)
Notes: Species recently cited for the province (Sánchez-Villegas, 2020).

Myosotis decumbens subsp. ***teresiana*** (Sennen) Grau
Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis discolor Pers. Subsp. ***discolor***
Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis discolor subsp. ***dubia*** (Arrond.) Blaise
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis discolor subsp. ***rosmatina*** Valdés
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis hervei Sennen (*M. tuxeniana* (O. Bolòs & Vigo) O. Bolòs & Vigo)
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: A very rare species in the province, recently cited from the Chía mountain pass (Sánchez-Villegas, 2020).

Myosotis laxa subsp. ***cespitosa*** (Schultz) Hyl. ex Nordh.
Gr? / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)
Notes: Although *Flora iberica* (Valdés, 2012) does not consider the records of this taxon for the province (Estrada Sánchez, 1986; Fuertes Lasala, 1989b; Molina, 1996; Molina Moreno, 1992; Sardinero Roscales, 2004), its presence in the province cannot be discarded, as we have confirmed it in the neighboring town of Hervás, in the province of Cáceres (SALA101178).

Myosotis persoonii Rouy
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis ramosissima subsp. ***gracillima*** (Loscos & J. Pardo) Rivas Mart.
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis ramosissima Rochel subsp. ***ramosissima***
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis secunda Al. Murray
Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Myosotis sicula Guss.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Species recently confirmed for the province (Sánchez-Villegas, 2019).

Myosotis stolonifera (A. DC.) Leresche & Levier
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Myosotis stricta Roem. & Schult.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Neatostema apulum (L.) I.M. Johnst.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Nonea micrantha Boiss. & Reut.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE
Notes: Basophile species only known from the municipality of Arévalo (SALA178854).

Nonea vesicaria (L.) Rchb.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE
Notes: Basophile species only known from Cantazorras, Arévalo (SALA1788478).

Pardoglossum cheirifolium (L.) E. Barbier & Mathez subsp. ***cheirifolium*** (*Cynoglossum cheirifolium* L. subsp. *cheirifolium*)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Pentaglottis sempervirens (L.) Tausch
Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Pulmonaria longifolia (Bastard) Boreau
Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Very rare in some cool forests in the eastern massif of Gredos (Molina Moreno, 1992).

Rochelia disperma (L. f.) K. Koch subsp. ***disperma***
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Known only from the Arévalo area (SALA58103, 58104, 136733, 168992).

Symphytum tuberosum L. subsp. ***tuberosum***
Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

BRASSICACEAE

Alliaria petiolata (M. Bieb.) Cavara & Grande
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Alyssum fastigiatum Heywood (*A. montanum* auct., non L.)
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Recently cited from the Pico mountain pass (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Alyssum granatense Boiss. & Reut.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Alyssum minutum Schldt. ex DC.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Alyssum simplex Rudolphi
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Recently cited from Junciana (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Arabidopsis thaliana (L.) Heynh.
Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Arabis alpina L. subsp. ***alpina***
Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Arabis auriculata Lam. (*A. recta* Vill.)
Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Arabis nova subsp. ***iberica*** Rivas Mart. ex Talavera
Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Arabis parvula Dufour
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Known exclusively from the limestone terrains in the Arévalo area (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Arabis stenocarpa Boiss. & Reut.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Barbarea intermedia Boreau
Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / DD (IUCN)

Biscutella auriculata L.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Biscutella gredensis Guinea
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Biscutella lusitanica Jord. (*Biscutella valentina* (L.) Heywood p.p.)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Brassica barrelieri (L.) Janka
Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Brassica napus L.
Gr / introduced

“*Brassica nigra* (L.) W.D.J. Koch”

Notes: The only provincial record (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a) is not supported by herbarium specimens.

Calepina irregularis (Asso) Thell.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Camelina microcarpa DC. (*C. sativa* subsp. *microcarpa* (DC.) Hegi & Em. Schmid)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Capsella bursa-pastoris (L.) Medik.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Capsella rubella Reut.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recent molecular studies (Neuffer *et al.*, 2014) indicated that this diploid species ($2n=16$) is genetically well differentiated from *C. bursa-pastoris* (tetraploid; $2n=32$), although they inhabit the same environments and are easily confused. *Capsella rubella* is usually smaller than *C. bursa-pastoris*, its sepals are more or less tinted with purple, and the margins of the silicule are frequently concave (sepals green and silicule margins straight to slightly convex in *C. bursa-pastoris*). When both taxa grow together it is quite common to find individuals with intermediate characters.

Cardamine castellana Lihová & Marhold

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Cardamine flexuosa With.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Herbarium specimens MA321390 (Pinar de Hoyocasero) and UPOS16923 (Hernansancho) confirm the presence of this species in the province.

Cardamine hirsuta L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

“*Cardamine pratensis* L.”

Notes: Lihová *et al.* (2003) stated that all populations from Ávila belong to *C. castellana*. However, the vouchers SALA12478, from Navascurial, and SALA125374, from Hoyos del Espino, show intermediate characters between *C. pratensis* and *C. castellana* (E. Rico pers. com.). Pending further studies, we do not consider for the moment that *C. pratensis* is part of the flora of Avila.

Coincya monensis (L.) Greuter & Burdet subsp.

cheiranthos (Vill.) Aedo, Leadlay & Muñoz Garm. (*C. cheiranthos* (Vill.) Greuter & Burdet)

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Coincya monensis subsp. ***orophila*** (Franco) Aedo, Leadlay & Muñoz Garm. (*C. hispida* (Cav.) Greuter & Burdet)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Conringia orientalis (L.) Dumort.

Mo / introduced

Descurainia sophia (L.) Prantl

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Diplotaxis catholica (L.) DC.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Diplotaxis virgata (Cav.) DC. subsp. ***virgata***

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Draba verna (L.) DC. (*Erophila verna* (L.) DC.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Drabella muralis (L.) Fourr. (*Draba muralis* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Eruca vesicaria (L.) Cav.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Erysimum cheiri (L.) Crantz (*Cheiranthus cheiri* L.)

Gr / introduced

Erysimum lagascae Rivas Goday & Bellot (*E. linifolium* (Pers.) J. Gay subsp. *lagascae* (Rivas Goday & Bellot) G. López)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Erysimum linifolium (Pers.) J. Gay

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE

Notes: recently found in the municipality of Cabezas de Alambre (UPOS18361). Its presence in the north of Ávila was expected, since it is known from the area of Olmedo, province of Valladolid (Bariego *et al.*, 2005).

Erysimum merxmulleri Polatschek

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Erysimum repandum L.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Hesperis laciniata All. subsp. ***laciniata***

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Hirschfeldia incana (L.) Lagr.-Foss.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Hornungia alpina* (L.) O. Appel subsp. *alpina* (*Pritzelago alpina* (L.) Kuntze subsp. *alpina*)”

Notes: The reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Morales, 1993b) appears to be based on the vouchers 42576, 42577, 42578, and 42579 from the Finca La Orden-Valdequesera herbarium (HSS), which we have not had the opportunity to study. We have visited the exact location of this collection (at km. 26 of the La Herguijuela to Peña Negra mountain pass road) on several occasions and have not found anything similar or the appropriate habitat (rock crevices). Furthermore, it is surprising that a taxon known from the Pyrenees-Cantabrian axis in the Iberian Peninsula has not been explicitly cited from this location, as it would represent a significant biogeographic disjunction. For these reasons, and considering what Romero Zarco (2021b) has stated, we believe it may be a labelling error.

Hornungia petraea (L.) Rchb. subsp. ***petraea***

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: It was considered for Ávila by Morales (1993a). Its presence in the province, confirmed by the voucher SALA178852, is not surprising since it inhabits nearby areas of Valladolid (Burgaz Moreno, 1983) and Madrid (Fernández Cancio, <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/70686744>).

Hornungia procumbens (L.) Hayek (*Hymenolobus procumbens* (L.) Nutt.)

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ionopsidium abulense (Pau) Rothm.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Ionopsidium glastifolium (L.) M. Koch (*Cochlearia glastifolia* L.)

Mo / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited in the province (Sánchez-Villegas, 2022a).

Isatis tinctoria L. subsp. ***tinctoria***

Ma / introduced

Lepidium campestre (L.) R. Br.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A species very similar to *L. heterophyllum*, although much rarer in the province.

Lepidium coronopus (L.) Al-Shehbaz (*Coronopus squamatus* (Forssk.) Asch.)
Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lepidium draba L. subsp. **draba** (*Cardaria draba* (L.) Desv. subsp. *draba*)
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Lepidium heterophyllum Benth. subsp. **heterophyllum**
Gr, Ma, Mo / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Lepidium latifolium L.
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lepidium perfoliatum L.
Gr, Mo / introduced

Lepidium villarsii Gren. & Godr. subsp. **villarsii**
Gr / European orophyte / LC (IUCN)
Notes: A species recently discovered in the municipality of Navarredonda de Gredos (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Lunaria annua L. subsp. **annua**
Gr / introduced

Marcus-Kochia triloba (L.) Al-Shehbaz (*Malcolmia triloba* (L.) Spreng.)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Matthiola fruticulosa (L.) Maire subsp. **fruticulosa**
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Microthlaspi perfoliatum (L.) F.K. Mey. (*Thlaspi perfoliatum* L.; *Noccaea perfoliata* (L.) Al-Shehbaz)
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Moricandia arvensis (L.) DC.
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Murbeckiella boryi (Boiss.) Rothm.
Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Nasturtium officinale R. Br. (*Rorippa nasturtium-aquaticum* (L.) Hayek subsp. *nasturtium-aquaticum*)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Neslia paniculata (L.) Desv. subsp. **thracica** (Velen.) Bornm.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Noccaea stenoptera (Boiss. & Reut.) F.K. Mey. (*Thlaspi stenopterum* Boiss. & Reut.)
Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Raphanus raphanistrum subsp. **raphanistrum**
Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Raphanus raphanistrum subsp. **sativus** (L.) Domin
Gr / introduced

Rorippa palustris (L.) Besser
Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)
Notes: Rare in the province (Sánchez-Villegas, 2019).

Rorippa pyrenaica (All.) Rchb.
Gr, Ma? / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Rorippa sylvestris (L.) Besser subsp. **sylvestris**
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Sinapis alba subsp. **mairei** (H. Lindb.) Maire
Gr?, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Photographic evidence in UPOS confirms its presence in Arévalo. It was cited from Solosancho (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a), but without herbarium evidence.

Sinapis arvensis L. subsp. **arvensis**
Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Sisymbrella aspera (L.) Spach subsp. **aspera**
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Sisymbrium chrysanthum Jord. (*S. austriacum* subsp. *chrysanthum* (Jord.) Rouy & Foucaud)
Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Sisymbrium crassifolium Cav.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in Ávila is confirmed by the voucher SALA178842, collected in Cantazorras (Arévalo).

Sisymbrium hispanicum Jacq. (*S. austriacum* subsp. *hispanicum* (Jacq.) P.W. Ball & Heywood; *S. contortum* Cav.; *S. austriacum* subsp. *contortum* (Cav.) Rouy & Foucaud)
Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Sisymbrium irio L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Sisymbrium officinale (L.) Scop.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Sisymbrium runcinatum DC.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Considered as present in Ávila by *Flora iberica* (Pujadas Salvá, 1993), the only specimen we have confirmed comes from the Arévalo area (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Subularia aquatica L. subsp. **aquatica**

Gr / Circumboreal / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Notes: Species very rare in the province (Trampal lagoons; Aldasoro, 1975).

Teesdalia coronopifolia (J.P. Bergeret) Thell.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Teesdalia nudicaulis (L.) R. Br.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Thlaspi arvense L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Turritis glabra L. (*Arabis glabra* (L.) Bernh.)

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

CACTACEAE

Opuntia phaeacantha Engelm.

Ma, Mo / introduced

Opuntia ficus-indica (L.) Mill. (incl. *O. maxima* Mill.)

Gr, Ma / introduced

CAMPANULACEAE

Campanula erinus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Campanula herminii Hoffmanns. & Link

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Campanula matritensis A. DC.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Campanula rapunculus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Campanula rotundifolia L. subsp. **hispanica** (Willk.) O. Bolòs & Vigo

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Jasione crispa subsp. **centralis** (Rivas Mart.) Rivas Mart.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Jasione laevis subsp. **carpetana** (Boiss. & Reut.) Rivas Mart. (*J. laevis* subsp. *gredensis* Rivas-Mart. & Sancho)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Jasione montana L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Jasione sessiliflora Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Legousia falcata (Ten.) Janch. (*L. scabra* (Lowe) Gamisans)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

"*Legousia speculum-veneris* (L.) Chaix"

Notes: We have not found any records nor vouchers confirming the presence of this plant in the province, despite the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Sales & Hedge, 2001a).

***Lobelia urens* L.**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Phyteuma hemisphaericum* L.**

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Phyteuma pyrenaicum* Rich. Schulz (*Ph. Spicatum* L. subsp. *pyrenaicum* (Rich. Schulz) A. Bolòs)**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

"*Trachelium caeruleum* L. subsp. *caeruleum*"

Notes: Despite the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Sales & Hedge, 2001b), we have not found any bibliographic records or herbarium testimonies of this species in the province or its vicinity. Therefore, we believe that this reference could be an error, especially considering that it is primarily a calcicolous plant.

***Wahlenbergia hederacea* (L.) Rchb.**

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / (IUCN)

CANNABACEAE

Celtis australis* L. subsp. *australis

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Humulus lupulus* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

CAPRIFOLIACEAE

***Lonicera etrusca* Santi**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. We confirm its presence with the specimen UPOS12756 collected in Cardeñosa.

***Lonicera implexa* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Lonicera periclymenum* subsp. *hispanica* (Boiss. & Reut.) Nyman**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

CARYOPHYLLACEAE

***Agrostemma githago* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Arenaria grandiflora* L. subsp. *grandiflora

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Arenaria leptoclados* (Reichenb.) Guss.**

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from some walls of El Barco de Ávila (UPOS18035, 18335).

Arenaria montana* L. subsp. *montana

Gr, Ma, Mo / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Arenaria querioides* Pourret ex Willk.**

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Arenaria serpyllifolia* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Bufonia macropetala* Willk.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Bufonia tenuifolia* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Presence confirmed by the specimen SALA168960 collected in Riocabado.

***Cerastium arvense* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Cerastium brachypetalum* Pers. subsp. *brachypetalum

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium cerastoides* (L.) Britton**

Gr / Boreo-alpine / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium dichotomum* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium diffusum* Pers.**

Gr, Mo / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium dubium* (Bastard) Guépin**

Mo / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), NT (LRE), NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium fontanum* Baumg. subsp. *vulgare* (Hartm.) Greut. & Burdet**

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium glomeratum* Thuill.**

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium pumilum* Curtis**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium ramosissimum* Boiss.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cerastium semidecandrum* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Chaetonymchia cymosa* (L.) Sweet**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Corrigiola litoralis* L. subsp. *litoralis

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Corrigiola telephiifolia* Pourret**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Dianthus armeria* L. subsp. *armeria

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Dianthus deltoides* L. subsp. *deltoides

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Dianthus gredensis* Pau ex Caballero**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Dianthus laricifolius* Boiss. & Reut. subsp. *laricifolius

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Dianthus legionensis* (Willk.) F.N. Williams**

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Dianthus lusitanus* Brot.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Dianthus nudiflorus* Griff. (*Velezia rigida* L.)**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Dianthus pungens* L. subsp. *brachyanthus* (Boiss.) Bernal, Fern. Casas, G. López, M. Laínz & Muñoz Garm.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Dianthus pungens* L. subsp. *hispanicus* (Asso) O. Bolòs & Vigo**

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Eudianthe laeta* (Aiton) Willk. (*Silene laeta* (Ayton) Godr.)**

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Gypsophila vaccaria* (L.) Sm. (*Vaccaria hispanica* (Mill.) Rauscher)**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the limestones of the Arévalo area (UPOS17447).

***Herniaria cinerea* DC.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known from the Arévalo area (photographic evidence in UPOS). It is likely that this species is more widespread in the province than previously assumed (cf. Chaudhri, 1990a).

***Herniaria glabra* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Herniaria hirsuta* L. subsp. *hirsuta

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province (Iruelas valley; UPOS14122).

***Herniaria latifolia* Lapeyr.**

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in the Villatoro mountain pass (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).***Herniaria lusitanica* Chaudhri subsp. *lusitanica***Notes: Cited from the Iruelas valley (Molina Moreno, 1992), although without herbarium evidence. Given the abundance of *Herniaria hirsuta* in the locality, we suspect it might be a misidentification.***Herniaria scabrada* subsp. *gadarramica* Chaudhri**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in the vicinity of the Tremedal mountain pass (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).***Herniaria scabrada* Boiss. subsp. *scabrada***

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Holosteum umbellatum* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Illecebrum verticillatum* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

***Loeflingia hispanica* Lag.**

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Arévalo (SALA168909) and Henansancho (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Minuartia campestris* L. subsp. *campestris

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only evidence we have for the province is the specimen SALA46449, collected in Riocabado.

***Minuartia dichotoma* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Minuartia hamata* (Hauskn. & Bornm.) Mattf.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Minuartia recurva* (All.) Schinz & Thell**

Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Moehringia pentandra* Gay**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Moehringia trinervia* (L.) Clairv.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed by the specimen SALA45734, collected in Pedro Bernardo.

Moenchia erecta* (L.) G. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb.*subsp. *erecta***

Gr, Ma, Mo? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Ortegia hispanica* Loefl.**

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Paronychia argentea* Lam.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Paronychia capitata* (L.) Lam. subsp. *capitata

Gr?, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Collected in Mingorria (UPOS16943). We have not had the opportunity to examine the specimen BC22583, collected by Font Quer between the town and the Mijares mountain pass.

***Paronychia polygonifolia* (Vill.) DC.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Paronychia rouyana* Coincy**

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We do not know the material that served as the basis for the inclusion of Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Chaudhri, 1990b).***Petrorhagia nanteuillii* (Burnat) P.W. Ball &**

Heywood Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE

(IUCN) *Petrorhagia prolifera* (L.) P.W. Ball &

Heywood Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Polycarpon tetraphyllum* (L.) L. subsp. *tetraphyllum

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Rabelera holostea* (L.) M.T. Sharples & E. Tripp*(*Stellaria holostea* L.)**

Gr?, Ma? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Listed for Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Romo, 1991), but we have not been able to find the specimen in which Romo (o.c.) was based. Its presence in the province should be confirmed.***Sabulina mediterranea* (Ledeb ex Link) Rchb.****(*Minuartia mediterranea* (Ledeb ex Link) K. Malý)**Notes: The reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Favarger & Montserrat, 1991) is based on specimen MA392092, identified by P. Montserrat under this binomial. However, this is a confusion with *S. tenuifolia*.***Sabulina tenuifolia* (L.) Rchb. subsp. *tenuifolia*****(*Minuartia hybrida* (Vill.) Schischk. subsp. *hybrida*)**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Sagina apetala* Ard.**

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

“*Sagina marítima* Don”Notes: We do not know herbarium evidence supporting the records for Ávila by Estrada Sánchez (1986) and Barrera *et al.* (1986).***Sagina procumbens* L.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Sagina sabuletorum* Gay ex Lange**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only testimony confirming its presence in Ávila is the voucher MA407088, collected in El Arenal.

Sagina saginoides* (L.) H. Karst. subsp. *nevadensis**(Boiss. & Reut.) Greuter & Burdet**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Saponaria glutinosa* M. Bieb.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Saponaria officinalis* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Scleranthus annuus* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Scleranthus delortii* Gren.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Scleranthus perennis* L.**

Gr? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only explicit provincial citation indicates its presence on Cerro Hervero (Ávila city; Ceballos, 1935). This citation appears to be based on Willkomm & Lange (1874–1880). If it was ever there, it seems to have disappeared. The plant is known, however, in the Sierra de Guadarrama (Fernández-González, 1988; García Adá, 1995).

***Scleranthus polycarpus* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Scleranthus verticillatus* Tausch**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Silene baccifera* (L.) Roth (*Cucubalus baccifer* L.)**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Silene boryi* Boiss.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Silene ciliata* Pourret subsp. *ciliata

Gr, Mo (European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Common in the summits of Gredos and rare in La Moraña (UPOS12709).

***Silene colorata* L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Silene conica* L. subsp. *conica

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Silene conoidea* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only voucher that confirm the presence of this species in the province is SALA177019.

***Silene coutinhoi* Rothm. & P. Silva**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Silene flos-cuculi* (L.) Clairv. subsp. *flos-cuculi* (*Lychnis flos-cuculi* L. subsp. *flos-cuculi*)**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Silene gallica* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Silene inaperta* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Only found between Cardeñosa and Monsalupe (SALA148255).

***Silene latifolia* Poiret**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Silene legionensis* Lag.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Silene marizii* Samp.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / CR (LRE), NT (IUCN)

Notes: Extremely rare and critically endangered species in Spain. In the province of Ávila, we know only three populations (Collado del Mirón and the Villatoro and Menga passes) with a small number of individuals.

***Silene mellifera* Boiss. & Reut.**

Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Confirmed only from Gallegos de San Vicente (UPOS14284) and Bernuy Salinero (photographic testimony by A. Arribas).

***Silene muscipula* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from Arévalo (SALA168912; UPOS16840).

***Silene nocturna* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Silene nutans* L. subsp. *nutans

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Silene portensis* L. subsp. *portensis

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Silene psammitis* Link ex Sprengel subsp. *psammitis

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Silene scabriflora* Brot. subsp. *scabriflora

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Silene vulgaris* (Moench) Garcke subsp. *vulgaris

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Spergula arvensis* L.**

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Spergula morisonii* Boreau**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Spergula pentandra* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Spergularia capillacea* (Kindb.) Willk.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Spergularia heldreichii* Foucaud**

Mo / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2022a).

***Spergularia marina* (L.) Besser**

Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

***Spergularia media* (L.) C. Presl**

Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas et al., 2020).

***Spergularia purpurea* (Pers) G. Don fil.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Spergularia rubra* (L.) J. Presl & K. Presl**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Spergularia segetalis* (L.) G. Don f.**

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Stellaria alsine* Grimm**

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Stellaria apetala* Ucria (*S. pallida* (Dumort.) Crep.)**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Stellaria graminea* L.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Stellaria media* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Stellaria neglecta* Weihe**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Viscaria alpina* (L.) Don (*Silene suecica* (Lodd.)**Greuter & Burdet; *Lychnis alpina* L.)

Gr / Boreo-alpine / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

CELASTRACEAE***Euonymus europaeus* L.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Parnassia palustris* L.**

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

CERATOPHYLLACEAE***Ceratophyllum demersum* L.**

Gr / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The only population known from Ávila was collected in Urraca Miguel (MA721497).

CISTACEAE***Cistus albidus* L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cistus crispus* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cistus inflatus* Demoly (*C. psilosepalus* auct., non Sweet)**

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Cistus ladanifer* L. subsp. *ladanifer

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / (IUCN)

***Cistus lasianthus* Lam. subsp. *alyssoides* (Lam.)**Demoly (*Halimium lasianthum* (Lam.) Spach subsp. *alyssoides* (Lam.) Greuter)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cistus laurifolius* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Cistus monspeliensis* L.”

Notes: The references in the GBIF database for the province (Vallejo Bombín, 2020) are not supported by herbarium specimens. The nearest confirmed locality we have found is in San Vicente mountain range (province of Toledo).

***Cistus ocymoides* Lam. (*Halimium ocymoides* (Lam.) Willk.)**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Cistus populifolius* L. subsp. *populifolius

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Cistus salviifolius* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cistus umbellatus* L. subsp. *viscosus* (Willk.)**Demoly (*Halimium umbellatum* (L.) Spach *viscosum* (Willk.) O. Bolós & Vigo)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Fumana ericifolia* Wallr.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Although it is a basophile species that we know from Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS18366), there is a voucher collected by C. Vicioso in the Iruelas valley (MA171920).

***Fumana procumbens* (Dunal) Gren. & Godr.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Basic soils in the northern part of the province (Villanueva de Gómez; UPOS16927).

***Helianthemum aegyptiacum* (L.) Mill.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Helianthemum angustatum* Pomel**

Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in Cantazorras, Arévalo (SALA168931).

Helianthemum apenninum* (L.) Mill. subsp. *apenninum

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Helianthemum cinereum* (Cav.) Pers. subsp. *rotundifolium* (Dunal) Greut. & Burdet**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Helianthemum hirtum* (L.) Mill.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Helianthemum ledifolium* (L.) Mill.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Helianthemum salicifolium* (L.) Mill.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Helianthemum sanguineum* (Lag.) Lag. ex Dunal**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Tuberaria guttata* (L.) Fourr. (*Xolantha guttata* (L.) Raf.)**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Tuberaria lignosa* (Sweet) Samp. (*Xolantha tuberaria* (L.) Gallego, Muñoz Garm. & C. Navarro)**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Tuberaria macrosepala* (Salzm. ex Boiss.) Willk.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

CLEOMACEAE***Cleome violacea* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently collected in Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).**CONVOLVULACEAE*****Convolvulus arvensis* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Convolvulus lineatus* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We only know this species from Cantazorras and the surroundings of the Adaja river near Arévalo (SALA178846).

***Convolvulus meonanthus* Hoffmanns. & Link**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Like the previous species, it only inhabits Cantazorras (Arévalo; UPOS17446).

***Convolvulus sepium* (L.) R. Br. (*Calystegia sepium* (L.) R.Br.)**

Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Cressa cretica* L.**

Mo / Pluriregional / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Cuscuta approximata* Bab. subsp. *approximata

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Cuscuta epithymum* (L.) L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Cuscuta europaea* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Ipomoea purpurea* (L.) Roth**

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in Junciana (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).**CORNACEAE*****Cornus sanguinea* L. subsp. *sanguinea***

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province (Arenas de San Pedro and Arévalo, photographic evidence in UPOS).

CRASSULACEAE***Crassula tillaea* Lest.-Garl.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

***Crassula vaillantii* (Willd.) Roth**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Petrosedum amplexicaule* (DC.) Velayos subsp. *amplexicaule* (*Sedum amplexicaule* DC.)**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Petrosedum forsterianum* (Sm.) Grulich (*Sedum forsterianum* Sm.)**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Petrosedum sediforme* (Jacq.) Grulich (*Sedum sediforme* (Jacq.) Pau)**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province (Cardeñosa, Villanueva de Gómez; UPOS16924).

***Pistorinia hispanica* (L.) DC.**

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Sedum acre* L. subsp. *acre

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Sedum aetnense* Tineo subsp. *aetnense

Gr / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), NT (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known from Navacepedilla de Corneja (Carrasco & Estrada, 1987; MACB1885) and Narrillos de San Leonardo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

***Sedum album* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Sedum andegavense* (DC.) Desv.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Sedum anglicum* Huds.**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Sedum arenarium* Brot.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Sedum brevifolium* DC.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Sedum caespitosum* (Cav.) DC.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Sedum candolleianum* G. López (*S. candollei* Raym.-Hamet; *Mucizonia sedoides* (DC.) D.A. Webb)**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Sedum dasyphyllum* L. subsp. *dasyphyllum

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: It is only known in the province from the slopes of Cinco Lagunas (Luceño *et al.*, 1989).

- Sedum gypsicola*** Boiss. & Reut.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Recently reported from Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).
- Sedum hirsutum*** All. subsp. ***hirsutum***
Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Sedum lagascae*** Pau
Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)
- Sedum maireanum*** Sennen
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
“*Sedum mucizonia* (Ortega) Raym.-Hamet”
Notes: Despite Castroviejo & Velayos (1997) included Ávila in *Flora iberica*, we have not found any records of this species for the province, nor in nearby locations in neighboring provinces.
- Sedum pedicellatum*** Boiss. & Reut. subsp. ***pedicellatum***
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Sempervivum vicentei*** Pau
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Umbilicus heylandianus*** Webb & Berthel.
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)
Notes: This species is rare in the province, where it has been only found in Junciana (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020) and La Moraña (F.J. de Sande, pers. comm.).
- Umbilicus rupestris*** (Salisb.) Dandy
Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

CUCURBITACEAE

- Bryonia dioica*** Jacq. (*B. cretica* L. subsp. *dioica* (Jacq.) Tutin)
Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Cucumis myriocarpus*** Naud.
Mo / introduced
- Ecballium elaterium*** (L.) A. Rich. subsp. ***elaterium***
Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

CYTINACEAE

- Cytinus hypocistis*** (L.) L.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

DIPSACACEAE

- Cephalaria leucantha*** (L.) Roem. & Schult.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Dipsacus fullonum*** L.
Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)
“*Knautia arvensis* (L.) Coulter”
Notes: The records of this taxon are likely due to confusion with *K. subscaposa* (cf. Devesa, 2007a).
- Knautia nevadensis*** (BM. Winkl. ex Szabó) Szabó
Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)
- Knautia subscaposa*** Boiss. & Reut.
Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
- Lomelosia simplex*** (Desf.) Raf.
Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
Notes: The only population we know from the province grows in Villafranca de la Sierra (SALA125674).
- Lomelosia stellata*** (L.) Raf.
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)
- Pterocephalidium diandrum*** (Lag.) G. López
Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Known from Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS16926) and Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS16919).

“*Scabiosa atropurpurea* L.”

Notes: The records from Ávila (Estrada Sánchez, 1986; Fuertes Lasala, 1989b; Navacepedilla de Corneja and Puerto de Menga, respectively) have not been confirmed by Devesa (2007b). In both localities, *S. columbaria* subsp. *columbaria* is common.

Scabiosa columbaria L. subsp. ***affinis*** (Gren. & Godr.) Nyman

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Considered in Ávila by Devesa (2007b). The plants found by F. de Sande in Maello, from which we have seen photographs of the infructescences, appear to belong to this subspecies.

Scabiosa columbaria L. subsp. ***columbaria***

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Much more common than the previous subspecies in a large part of the province.

Succisa pratensis Moench

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Succisella carvalhoana (Mariz) Baksay

Gr / Iberian endemism / VU (C and L), VU (LRE), EN (IUCN)

Notes: The voucher UPOS18058, from Candededa, evidence the presence of this Iberian endemism in the province.

Succisella microcephala (Willk.) Beck

Gr / Iberian endemism / VU (C and L), VU (LRE), NE (IUCN)

DROSERACEAE

“*Drosera intermedia* Haynes”

Notes: We do not have any bibliographic record or voucher confirming the presence of this species in the province, as mentioned by Paiva (1997).

Drosera rotundifolia L.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

ELATINACEAE

Elatine hexandra (Lapierre) DC.

Gr? / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The only record from Ávila seems to come from the vicinity of Ávila city (Willkomm & Lange, 1874-1880). As far as we know, there are no vouchers from the province.

ERICACEAE

Arbutus unedo L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Arctostaphylos uva-ursi (L.) Spreng.

Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Calluna vulgaris (L.) Hull

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Erica arborea L.

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Erica australis L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Erica scoparia L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Erica tetralix L.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Erica umbellata L.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Monotropa hypopitys* L.**

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A nemoral species that inhabits forests of *Pinus sylvestris* and *P. pinaster*. We are aware of only four populations: El Hornillo (Sánchez-Mata *et al.*, 1991) and Arenas de San Pedro (pers. obs.) on the southern slope of the main Gredos mountain range, and Hoyos del Espino (pers. obs.) and Hoyocasero (Luceño & Vargas, 1986) in the northern slope; the latter has not been observed subsequently. Although it is not classified as a threatened plant, we believe that its rarity in the province warrants administrative attention due to its limited and fluctuating populations.

***Pyrola chlorantha* Sw.†**

Gr / Circumboreal

Notes: Collected only once from the Hoyocasero Pine Forest by Bourgeau (P456711).

***Pyrola minor* L.**

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Although the plant does not have any protection category, attention should be paid to the only and exiguous population (10 individuals) that survives in the Navarredonda de Gredos pine forest (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

***Vaccinium myrtillus* L.**

Gr, Ma / Boreo-alpine / LC (IUCN)

EUPHORBIACEAE***Chrozophora tinctoria* (L.) Raf.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Euphorbia angulata* Jacq.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Euphorbia chamaesyce* L. subsp. *chamaesyce (*Chamaesyce canescens* (L.) Prokh. subsp. *canescens*)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Euphorbia exigua* L. subsp. *exigua

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

***Euphorbia exigua* subsp. *merinoi* M. Lainz**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cited only from La Adrada (Lázaro Bello, 2011; MA827536).

Euphorbia falcata* L. subsp. *falcata

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Euphorbia helioscopia* L. subsp. *helioscopia

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Euphorbia maculata* L. (*Chamaesyce maculata* (L.) Small)**

Gr, Mo / introduced

Notes: Known only in the province from El Barco de Ávila (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

***Euphorbia matritensis* Boiss.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed by the specimen UPOS12825, collected in Lanzahita.

Euphorbia nevadensis* Boiss. & Reut. subsp. *nevadensis

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Euphorbia nicaeensis* All. subsp. *nicaeensis

Gr? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We are unaware of the material studied by Benedí *et al.* (1998) to include “Av” in *Flora iberica*. It might be the specimen LEB7781 that we haven't been able to examine.

***Euphorbia nutans* Lag. (*Chamaesyce nutans* (Lag.) Small)**

Gr / introduced

Notes: From Ávila, it is known solely from Candeleda (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

***Euphorbia oxyphylla* Boiss.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Euphorbia pepus* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Euphorbia prostrata* Aiton (*Chamaesyce prostrata* (Aiton) Small)**

Gr / introduced

Notes: Cited exclusively from La Adrada (Lázaro Bello, 2012) and recently collected in Candeleda.

***Euphorbia segetalis* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Confirmed for the vicinity of Candeleda (UPOS17580).

***Euphorbia serrata* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Euphorbia sulcata* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from Arévalo (SALA168937).

***Mercurialis ambigua* L. fil.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Mercurialis elliptica* Poir.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from Candeleda (UPOS16772).

***Mercurialis tomentosa* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Known only from Villarejo del Valle (MA732999).

***Ricinus communis* L.**

Gr / introduced

FABACEAE***Acacia dealbata* Link**

Gr / introduced

***Adenocarpus argyrophyllus* (Rivas Goday) Caball.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Adenocarpus aureus* (Cav.) Pau**

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Adenocarpus complicatus* (L.) J. Gay**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Adenocarpus hispanicus* (Lam.) DC.**

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Adenocarpus lainzii* (Castrov.) Castrov.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

“*Adenocarpus telonensis* (Loisel.) DC.”

Notes: Even though it was considered for Ávila by Castroviejo (1999), we have not found references nor herbarium specimens from the province. Considering the Iberian southern distribution of this taxon, we believe that its presence in the province should be discarded.

***Anthyllis cornicina* L. (*Hymenocarpus cornicina* (L.) Vis.)**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Anthyllis lotoides* L. (*Hymenocarpus lotoides* (L.) Vis.)**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Anthyllis montana* L.”

Notes: We have not found any voucher to justify the presence of this plant in Ávila according to *Flora iberica* (Benedí, 2000). This species is known to

occur exclusively in the eastern half of the Iberian Peninsula.

Anthyllis vulneraria L. subsp. ***gandogeri*** (Sagorski) W. Becker ex Maire

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Anthyllis vulneraria* subsp. *maura* (G. Beck) Maire”

Notes: The provincial records (Rivas Martínez & Cantó, 1985; Estrada Sánchez, 1986, and Molina Moreno, 1992) were not considered by *Flora iberica* (Benedí, 2000).

Anthyllis vulneraria subsp. ***sampaioana*** (Rothm.) Vasc.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed by the voucher UPOS11744 collected in Hoyos del Espino.

Astragalus alopecuroides L. subsp. ***alopecuroides*** Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Astragalus cymbaearpos Brot.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only known specimen from the province was collected in Junciana (UPOS11676).

Astragalus devesae A. González & G. López Gr / Iberian endemism / Endangered (C and L), CR (LRE), CR (IUCN)

Notes: Endemism of Ávila whose distribution is limited to Padiernos, Collado del Mirón, and near Ávila city.

Astragalus glaux L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the Arévalo area (UPOS16949, UPOS17442).

Astragalus glycyphyllos L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Astragalus granatensis Lam.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Astragalus hamosus L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Astragalus incanus L. subsp. ***nummularioides*** (Desf.) Maire

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Astragalus monspessulanus L. subsp. ***gypsophilus*** Rouy

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Astragalus pelecinus (L.) Barneby subsp. ***pelecinus***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Astragalus stella L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only provincial record comes from Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

Bituminaria bituminosa (L.) C.H. Stirt.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Coronilla dura Cav. (*C. repanda* subsp. *dura* (Cav.) Cout.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Coronilla juncea L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Coronilla lotoides W.D.J. Koch (*Coronilla minima* subsp. *lotoides* (W.D.J. Koch) Nyman)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Coronilla minima L. subsp. ***minima***

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Coronilla scorpioides (L.) W.D.J. Koch

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only provincial record comes from Arévalo (UPOS16945). Also observed in Arevalillo.

Cytisus multiflorus (L'Hér.) Sweet

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Cytisus oromediterraneus (G. López & C.E. Jarvis)

Rivas Mart., T.E. Díaz, Fern. Prieto, Loidi & Penas

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Cytisus scoparius (L.) Link subsp. ***scoparius***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Cytisus striatus (Hill) Rothm.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Dorycnopsis gerardi (L.) Boiss.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Echinopartum barnadesii (Graells) Rothm.

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Echinopartum ibericum Rivas Mart., Sánchez Mata & Sancho

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Erophaca baetica (L.) Boiss. subsp. ***baetica***

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ervilia hirsuta (L.) Opiz (*Vicia hirsuta* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Ervilia monanthos (L.) Opiz (*Vicia articulata* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Ervum gracile DC. (*Vicia parviflora* Cav.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Ervum pubescens* DC. (*Vicia pubescens* (DC.) Link)”

Notes: We have not found herbarium specimens nor bibliographic records from Ávila or nearby areas to support the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Romero Zarco, 1999).

Ervum tetraspermum L. (*Vicia tetrasperma* (L.) Schreb.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Genista anglica L.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Genista carpetana Leresche ex Lange

Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Genista cinerascens Lange

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Genista falcata Brot.

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Genista florida L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Genista hirsuta Vahl subsp. ***hirsuta***

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Genista hispanica* L. subsp. *hispanica*”

Notes: From the province, we only have seen two herbarium specimens identified as *G. hispanica*. One of them, collected in Piedrahita in 1762 (BC-Bernadés 80) and cited by Ibáñez *et al.* (2009), may have been used by Talavera (1999) to include the province in the Iberian distribution of subsp. *hispanica*. On the other hand, we have seen another specimen collected by Bernades (MA58713) with a label that reads “Guadalupe (Cáceres),” and Talavera correctly identified it as *G. hispanica* subsp. *hispanica*. The second specimen (W2017-12814), collected by P. Escobar between La Herguijuela and the Peña Negra mountain pass, and identified as *Genista hispanica* subsp. *occidentalis*, shows elongated and lax racemes, as well as flowers with bracts several mm long and a keel much longer than the standard, indicating that it is *G. tournefortii* Spach, which is relatively common in that area. In our opinion, considering i) that it is a predominantly calcareous species, ii) that we have not observed anything resembling *G. hispanica* in the numerous visits to the mentioned localities, and iii) that the

Bernades' specimens mentioned represent a significant disjunction from the Iberian range of subsp. *hispanica*, we believe that these materials may suffer from a labelling error. Therefore, we think that the presence of this species in the province should be rejected.

Genista scorpius (L.) DC.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in La Moraña (San Pascual, UPOS12726; Arévalo, photographic evidence in UPOS).

Genista tinctoria L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Genista tournefortii Spach subsp. *tournefortii*

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Genista tridentata L. subsp. *lasiantha* (Spach)

Greuter (*Pterospartum tridentatum* (L.) Wilk. subsp. *lasianthum* (Spach) Talavera & P.E. Gibbs)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Glycyrrhiza glabra (L.) DC.

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The Iberian populations of this species are considered by some authors (Bariego, 2016; POWO) as introduced. Rare in Arévalo (UPOS18359).

Hippocrepis carpetana Lassen

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Hippocrepis commutata Pau

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Lathyrus angulatus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus aphaca L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus cicera L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus filiformis (Lam.) J. Gay

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The only evidence of the presence of this species in the province comes from the basic soils of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Lathyrus hirsutus L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus latifolius L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus linifolius (Reichard) Bässler

Gr? / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Cited from the Villatoro mountain pass (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a), we have not found the plant after numerous searches in the locality; nor we have been able to see herbarium evidence of the mentioned citation; however, its presence in the province is not discarded, as it inhabits all neighbouring provinces.

Lathyrus niger (L.) Bernh.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus nissolia L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lathyrus oleraceus Lam. subsp. *biflorus* (Raf.)

Schaefer (*Pisum sativum* L. subsp. *elatius* (M. Biev.) Asch. & Graebn.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Lathyrus oleraceus Lam. subsp. *oleraceus* (*Pisum*

sativum L. subsp. *sativum*)

Gr / introduced

Lathyrus pratensis L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

"*Lathyrus setifolius* L."

Notes: Cited from Muñogalindo and Padiernos (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a), we have not been able to find it in either of those locations, nor have we found herbarium specimens to confirm the citations.

Lathyrus sphaericus Retz.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lotus carpetanus Lacaita (*L. corniculatus* L. subsp. *carpetanus* (Lacaita) Rivas Mart.)

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Lotus castellanus Boiss. & Reut.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Lotus conimbricensis Brot.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Lotus corniculatus L.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Lotus delortii Timb.-Lagr. (*L. corniculatus* L. subsp. *delortii* (Timb.-Lagr.) Nyman)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Lotus dorycnium L. subsp. *dorycnium* (*Dorycnium pentaphyllum* Scop.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Lotus hispidus Desf. ex DC.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from the municipality of Candeleda (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Lotus maritimus L. (*Tetragonolobus maritimus* (L.) Rothm.)

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Lotus parviflorus Desf.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Some populations are known in the main chain of Gredos (UPOS10865, Junciana; UPOS10672, El Losar del Barco).

Lotus pedunculatus Cav.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Lotus tenuis Willd. (*L. glaber* Mill.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Lupinus albus L.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Lupinus angustifolius L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Lupinus bicolor Lindl.

Gr / introduced

Notes: A species native to North America for which several populations with numerous individuals have been recently found in the southwest of the province (Junciana, El Losar del Barco, and El Barco de Ávila; Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022b).

Lupinus gredensis Gand.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Lupinus hispanicus Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Lupinus luteus L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Medicago arabica (L.) Huds.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Medicago lupulina L.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Medicago minima (L.) L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Medicago monspeliaca (L.) Trautv. (*Trigonella monspeliaca* L.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Medicago orbicularis (L.) Bartal.

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The presence of the species in the province is confirmed by the specimen UPOS13120, collected in El Oso. It also inhabits the area of Arévalo.

Medicago polyceratia (L.) Trautv. (*Trigonella polyceratia* L.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Medicago polymorpha L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Medicago rigidula (L.) All.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Medicago sativa L. subsp. **sativa**

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Melilotus albus Medik.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Melilotus indicus (L.) All.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020), it also inhabits Candededa.

Melilotus officinalis (L.) Pall.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Cited from the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a) and Junciana (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

Onobrychis humilis (Loefl.) G. López

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Onobrychis viciifolia Scop.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Ononis broteriana DC.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Ononis fruticosa L. (incl. subsp. **microphylla** (DC.)

O. Bolòs, Vigo, Masalles & Ninot)

Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not been able to see the specimen on which the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Devesa, 2000) is based, nor we do know of provincial records.

Ononis natrix L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only herbarium specimens we are aware of, come from Arévalo and Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS13134).

Ononis pinnata Brot.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Ononis pusilla L. subsp. **pusilla**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ononis spinosa L. subsp. **spinosa**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Ononis spinosa subsp. **australis** (Sirj.) Greuter & Burdet

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ornithopus compressus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ornithopus perpupillus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Ornithopus pinnatus (Mill.) Druce

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ornithopus sativus Brot. Subsp. **sativus**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Ornithopus sativus subsp. **isthmocarpus** (Coss.) Dostál

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Retama sphaerocarpa (L.) Boiss.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Robinia pseudoacacia L.

Gr / introduced

Spartium junceum L.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Notes: Cultivated in medians and ditches and occasionally naturalised.

Styphnolobium japonicum (L.) Schott (*Sophora japonica* L.)

Gr / introduced

Notes: Subspontaneous in Arenas de San Pedro (J.A. Sáez, pers. comm.).

Trifolium angustifolium L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium arvense L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium bocconeii Savi

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Trifolium campestre Schreb.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium cernuum Brot.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium cherleri L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium diffusum Ehrh.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium dubium Sibth.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium fragiferum L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium gemellum Willd.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium glomeratum L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium hirtum All.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium hybridum L.

Gr / introduced

Trifolium incarnatum L. subsp. **incarnatum**

Gr / introduced

Trifolium lappaceum L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Trifolium leucanthum M. Bieb.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed by the herbarium specimens SALA33543 and UPOS17445, collected from Langa and Villanueva de Gómez, respectively.

Trifolium ligusticum Balb. ex Loisel.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cf. Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, (2022a).

Trifolium medium L. subsp. **medium**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium michelianum Savi

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from the Villafranca mountain range (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Trifolium micranthum Viv.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium montanum L.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cited from Arevalillo (Muñoz Rodríguez, 1995).

Trifolium ochroleucon Huds.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium ornithopodioides L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, it is known from Salobral (Muñoz Rodríguez, 1995), Papatrigo (SALA90395), Madrigal de las Altas Torres (SALA90458), and San Juan de la Encinilla (SALA90384).

“*Trifolium pallidum* Waldst. & Kit.”

Notes: Cited by García Muñoz (2009) from Vadillo de la Sierra. The herbarium specimen (MA721485) that served as the basis for this reference contains a specimen of *T. ochroleucon*.

Trifolium phleoides subsp. ***willkommii*** (Chabert) Muñoz Rodr.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium pratense L. subsp. ***pratense***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium repens L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC(IUCN)

Trifolium resupinatum L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium retusum L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium scabrum L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium stellatum L.

Gr, Ma? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium striatum L. subsp. ***striatum***

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium strictum L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium subterraneum subsp. ***oxaloides*** Nyman

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have been unable to find an herbarium specimen or a bibliographic record justifying the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Muñoz Rodríguez *et al.*, 2000). We have collected numerous populations of the species in the province, and all the material belongs to the typical subspecies. Therefore, the presence of this race in Ávila should be confirmed.

Trifolium subterraneum L. subsp. ***subterraneum***

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Trifolium suffocatum L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed from Arévalo (SALA168923).

Trifolium sylvaticum Gérard ex Loisel.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium tomentosum L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trifolium vesiculosum Savi

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Recently collected in the municipality of San Pascual (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Ulex europaeus L. subsp. ***europaeus***

Gr / introduced

Notes: Although it is a native taxon to the Iberian Peninsula, the Gredos populations are considered introduced.

Vicia amphicarpa L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently collected in the basic clays near Arévalo (SALA178956).

Vicia angustifolia L. subsp. ***angustifolia***

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Vicia benghalensis L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. We only know it from the basic clays near Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18066).

Vicia dasycarpa Ten.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Vicia disperma DC.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Vicia eriocarpa (Hauskn.) Halácsy

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Vicia faba L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break.

Vicia lathyroides L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Vicia lentoides (Ten.) Coss. & Germ. (*Lens nigricans* (M. Bieb.) Godr.)

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Vicia lutea L. subsp. ***lutea***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Vicia monantha subsp. ***calcarata*** (Desf.) Romero Zarco

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. We have recently observed it on calcareous soils in the municipality of Arévalo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Vicia narbonensis L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province, where two populations are known. La Adrada (Lázaro Bello, 2012) and Cardeñosa (UPOS16929).

Vicia onobrychioides L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

“*Vicia orobus* DC.”

Notes: Neither Romero Zarco (1999) nor we have found herbarium evidence to support the provincial citations (Rivas Martínez *et al.*, 1986; Sánchez Mata, 1989) of this taxon.

Vicia pannonica subsp. ***striata*** (M. Bieb.) Nyman (*V. pannonica* subsp. *purpurascens* (DC.) Arcang.)

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, it is only known from the vicinity of Arévalo (Cantazorras, UPOS17443).

Vicia peregrina L.

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in Ávila, we have recently observed it in ditches near the cemetery of Arévalo (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Vicia pyrenaica Pourr.

Gr / European orophyte / LC (IUCN)

Vicia sativa L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Vicia sepium L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Vicia tenuifolia Roth

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Vicia villosa Roth

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / introduced

Notes: The numerous citations from Ávila have not been confirmed by Romero Zarco (1999), but its presence in Ávila is probable since it is naturalised in the provinces of Cáceres and Madrid.

FAGACEAE

Castanea sativa Miller

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Quercus faginea Lam. (incl. subsp. *broteroi* (Cout.) A. Camus)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In the province this species is only known from the Tiétar valley.

Quercus pyrenaica Willd.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Quercus robur L.

Gr? / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The photographs published on iNaturalist from the Ramacastañas area (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/237476402>) do not conclusively confirm the species in the province. The apparently glabrous leaf underside suggests it might be *Quercus robur*, but it is also possible that it is an introgressive hybrid of *Quercus pyrenaica* with *Quercus faginea*. The presence of *Quercus robur* in southern Ávila would not be surprising, as it is well-known in the northeast of Cáceres, but should be confirmed.

Quercus rotundifolia Lam.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Quercus suber L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

FRANKENIACEAE

Frankenia pulverulenta L. subsp. **pulverulenta**

Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

GENTIANACEAE

Blackstonia acuminata (W.D.J. Koch & Ziz) Domin subsp. **acuminata**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Species recently found in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18337).

Blackstonia perfoliata (L.) Huds. subsp. **perfoliata**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Centaurium majus (Hoffmanns. & Link) Ronninger (*Centaurium grandiflorum* (Pers.) Ronniger subsp. **majus** (Hoffmanns. & Link) Z. Díaz)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Centaurium maritimum (L.) Janch

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Centaurium tenuiflorum (Hoffmanns & Link) Janch.

Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas, 2020).

Cicendia filiformis (L.) Delarbre

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Gentiana boryi Boiss.

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), VU (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Gentiana lutea L. subsp. **aurantiaca** M. Laínz

Gr, Ma? / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: To this subspecies belongs the populations with orange flowers after studies by González-López *et al.* (2014), Losada *et al.* (2015) and Sobral *et al.* (2015).

Gentiana lutea L. subsp. **lutea**

Gr, Ma / European orophyte / With regulated use (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Gentiana pneumonanthe L.

Gr / eurAsian / NE (IUCN)

Schenkia pusilla (Lam.) Luceño, comb. nov.

≡ *Gentiana pusilla* Lam., Encycl. 2: 645 (1788), basionyme.

≡ *Cicendia pusilla* (Lam.) Griseb., Gen. Sp. Gent.: 157 (1838).

≡ *Exaculum pusillum* (Lam.) Caruel in Parl., Fl. Ital. 6: 743 (1886).

Gr / NT (IUCN)

Notes: While *Exaculum pusillum* is the most widely accepted name for this taxon (POWO, 2024), its taxonomic proximity to the genus *Schenkia* is beyond doubt after the recent study on the cytogenetic and molecular evolution of the tribe Chironieae (Gentianaceae; Díaz Infante *et al.*, 2023). This taxonomic proximity was previously noted (Díaz Infante, 2012). The phylogenetic tree presented in Díaz Infante *et al.* (2023) groups the two samples of *Exaculum pusillum* into a sister clade of samples of *Schenkia elegans* from the campus of the University Pablo de Olavide in Seville. These two clades are, in turn, the sister group to another that includes samples of the Eurasian *Schenkia spicata* and the Australian *S. clementii*, themselves sisters of the clade that includes the samples of *S. elegans* from El Almendro (Huelva). Based on this data and the robust cytogenetic study carried out, the authors conclude that *S. elegans* is an allopolyploid derived from *Exaculum pusillum* and *Schenkia spicata*. These authors advocate for the inclusion of *Schenkia elegans* in an independent monotypic genus, thus describing the new genus *Valdesiana*. However, while acknowledging the excellence of the results by Díaz Infante *et al.* (2023), we believe that their taxonomic conclusions are excessively analytical. For biogeographical and morphological reasons, it seems more parsimonious and appropriate to accept a broad concept of *Schenkia*, which includes the accepted species of this genus (Eurasia, Australia, and Japan; cf. POWO, 2024), the American species recently grouped into the genus *Zeltnera*, and the monotypic genus *Exaculum*, distributed throughout the Western Mediterranean basin.

Schenkia spicata (L.) G. Mans.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The voucher UPOS15065 confirms the presence of this species in the province, that was reported from El Oso by Martín García *et al.* (2014).

GERANIACEAE

Erodium aethiopicum (Lam.) Brumh. & Thell.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Erodium botrys (Cav.) Bertol.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Erodium brachycarpum (Godr.) Thell.

Gr? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cited by Molina Moreno (1992) from the Iruelas valley, we are not aware of any herbarium evidence to confirm this record. The presence of this taxon in the southern slope of Gredos is quite likely, as we have collected it in La Iglésuela, on the boundary between the provinces of Toledo and Ávila.

Erodium carvifolium Boiss. & Reut.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Erodium ciconium (L.) L'Hér.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in Ávila is confirmed by the specimen UPOS17441, collected in Cantazorras (Arévalo).

Erodium cicutarium (L.) L'Hér.

Gr, Ma, Mo / NE (IUCN)

Erodium malacoides (L.) L'Hér.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Erodium moschatum (L.) L'Hér.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare or scarcely collected in the province (Candeleda and Arévalo).

Geranium columbinum L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium dissectum L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium divaricatum Ehrh.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium lucidum L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium molle L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium purpureum Vill.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium pusillum L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium pyrenaicum Burn. subsp. ***lusitanicum*** (Samp.) S. Ortiz

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Geranium robertianum L.

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Geranium rotundifolium L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Geranium sanguineum L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Geranium sylvaticum L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

GROSSULARIACEAE

Ribes rubrum L.

Gr / introduced

Ribes uva-crispa L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Martiherrero (García Muñoz, 2009); Mingorria (photographic evidence in UPOS).

HALORAGACEAE

Myriophyllum alterniflorum DC.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

HELIOTROPIACEAE

Heliotropium europaeum L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Heliotropium supinum L.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

HYDRANGEACEAE

Philadelphus coronarius L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in Lanzahíta (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.)

HYPERICACEAE

Hypericum androsaemum L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

"*Hypericum hyssopifolium* Chaix"

Notes: Cited by Rivas Goday *et al.* (1959) from the stretch between Arenas de San Pedro and Candeleda, but there is no herbarium evidence to support the presence of this taxon in Ávila. Ramos Núñez (2006) also questioned this citation. Given its Iberian distribution, we provisionally excluded this species from Ávila.

Hypericum humifusum L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Hypericum linarifolium Vahl

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Hypericum montanum L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Hypericum perforatum L. subsp. ***perforatum***

Gr, Ma, Mo Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Hypericum perforatum subsp. ***veronense*** (Schrank) H. Lindb. (*H. perforatum* subsp. *angustifolium* (DC.) A. Fröl)

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Hypericum tomentosum L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Hypericum undulatum Willd.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

JUGLANDACEAE

Juglans regia L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Palynological data (Carrión & Sánchez-Gómez, 1992; López Sáez *et al.*, 2014) demonstrated the native nature of the walnut tree in the Iberian Peninsula.

LAMIACEAE

Ajuga chamaepitys (L.) Schreb.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

"*Ajuga pyramidalis* subsp. *pyramidalis*"

Notes: As we recently clarified (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020), the plants in the Central System, considered by Llamas (2010) in *Flora iberica* as *A. pyramidalis* subsp. *pyramidalis*, belong to subsp. *meonantha*.

Ajuga pyramidalis subsp. ***meonantha*** (Hoffmanns. & Link) R. Fern.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Ajuga reptans L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Ballota nigra subsp. ***foetida*** (Vis.) Hayek

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Betonica officinalis L. (*Stachys officinalis* (L.) Trevis)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Cleonia lusitanica (L.) L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Clinopodium nepeta (L.) Kuntze subsp. ***nepeta*** (*Calamintha nepeta* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Clinopodium vulgare L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Galeopsis ladanum L. subsp. ***carpetana*** (Willk.) O. Bolòs & Vigo

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The materials from Ávila that we have studied (Los Caballeros gorge) fit this subspecies better. However, Lorda and Morales (2010) accept the presence of the subspecies *angustifolia* and *ladanum* in the province. We are unaware of the materials these authors have considered in their

treatment for *Flora iberica*, as there are only two known populations of the species in Ávila, the one that we have studied (González Canalejo *et al.*, 2004) and another in Prado de las Pozas (Caballero, 196; Rivas Martínez, 1963).

***Glechoma hederacea* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from Zapardiel de la Ribera (SALA135424).

Lamium album* L. subsp. *album

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Lamium amplexicaule* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Lamium bifidum* Cirillo**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Lamium hybridum* Vill.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Lamium maculatum* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Lamium purpureum* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Lavandula angustifolia* Mill.**

Gr / introduced

Notes: We are only aware of one naturalised population that originates from a former cultivation in the Villafranca mountain range.

“*Lavandula latifolia* Medik.”

Notes: The numerous records found in the GBIF database (<https://www.gbif.org>) are not very plausible. We are not aware of any voucher that justify the presence of this strictly calcicolous species in the province of Ávila.

***Lavandula pedunculata* (Mill.) Cav.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Lavandula stoechas* subsp. *luisieri* (Rozeira) Rozeira**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Lycopus europaeus* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Marrubium vulgare* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NT (IUCN)

***Melissa officinalis* L.**

Gr / introduced

***Melittis melyssophyllum* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Mentha aquatica* L.**

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Mentha arvensis* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Mentha cervina* L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NT (IUCN)

***Mentha longifolia* (L.) Huds.**

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Mentha pulegium* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Mentha suaveolens* Ehrh.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Nepeta caerulea* Aiton**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Nepeta cataria* L.**

Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known from Peñalba de Ávila (García Muñoz, 2009) and Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS16954). We have also observed it in Arévalo.

***Nepeta multibracteata* Desf.**

Gr / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L)

Notes: Rare in the province, only known from Navacedilla de Corneja (MACB19824, 19825), El Barco de Ávila (Ubera & Valdés, 1983) and Gavilanes. “*Nepeta nepetella* L. subsp. *aragonensis* (Lam.) Nyman”

Notes: We are not aware of the origin of the reference to Ávila by Aedo (2010) in *Flora iberica*. We have not found provincial vouchers nor records.

***Nepeta tuberosa* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province, it forms some populations on basic soils in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (Sánchez-Villegas, 2019).

***Origanum vulgare* L. subsp. *virens* (Hoffmanns. & Link) Bonnier & Layens**

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Phlomis herba-venti* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Phlomis lychnitis* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Prunella grandiflora* (L.) Scholler**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Prunella laciniata* (L.) L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Prunella vulgaris* L.**

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

***Pseudodictamnus hirsutus* (Willd.) Salmaki & Siadati (*Ballota hirsuta* (Willd.) Benth.)**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only reference in Ávila is supported by the voucher SALA23829, collected in Solana de Ávila, where it grows on the mortar of the walls.

***Rosmarinus officinalis* L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Salvia aethiopis* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Salvia pratensis* L.”

Notes: Cited by García Muñoz (2004) from the surroundings of Ávila city, but we have not found vouchers of this reference. It is a calcicolous species known in the northeastern quadrant of the Iberian Peninsula.

***Salvia verbenaca* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Scutellaria alpina* L. subsp. *alpina

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Scutellaria galericulata* L.**

Gr, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

***Scutellaria minor* Huds.**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Sideritis hirsuta* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Sideritis lurida* Lacaita subsp. *borgiae* (J. Andrés)**

Luceño, B. García Muñoz & A. González

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

***Sideritis montserratiana* Stübing, R. Roselló, Olivares & Perich**

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Stachys arvensis* (L.) L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Stachys germanica* L. subsp. *germanica

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

“*Stachys palustris* L.”

Notes: In the Iberian Peninsula this species is found in isolated localities in the north. The only provincial reference is an old and generic mention (Willkomm & Lange, 1865-1870).

Teucrium capitatum* L. subsp. *capitatum

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Teucrium gnaphalodes* L'Hér.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In Ávila, this taxon is only known from the municipality of Mombeltrán (Ferrer-Gallego *et al.*, 2012; MA98324).***Teucrium oxylepis* Font Quer subsp. *gredense* P. Vargas & García Muñoz**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: An Ávila endemism of which only one small population is known in the Bohoyo gorge (Vargas & García Muñoz, 2008).

Teucrium scordium* L. subsp. *scordium

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Teucrium scorodonia* L.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Thymus bracteatus* Cutanda subsp. *bracteatus

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Thymus drucei* Ronninger (*T. praecox* subsp. *britannicus* (Ronniger) Holub)**

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Thymus mastichina* (L.) L. subsp. *mastichina

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Thymus pulegioides* L. subsp. *pulegioides

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Thymus zygis* L. subsp. *zygis

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

***Ziziphora granatensis* (Boiss. & Reut.) Melnikov subsp. *granatensis* (*Acinos alpinus* (L.) Moench subsp. *meridionalis* (Nyman) P.W. Ball)**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Ziziphora graveolens* (M. Bieb.) Melnikov (*Acinos rotundifolius* Pers.)**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only testimony of the presence of this species in the province comes from Arévalo (SALA168896).

LENTIBULARIACEAE***Utricularia australis* R. Br.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Utricularia minor* L.**

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / Preferential attention (C and L), EN (LRE), LC (IUCN)

LINACEAE***Linum austriacum* L. subsp. *collinum* (Boiss.) Nyman**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Linum bienne* Mill.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Linum catharticum* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Linum narbonense* subsp. *barrasii* (Pau) Mart. Labarga & Muñoz Garm.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Linum narbonense* L. subsp. *narbonense

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Linum radiola* L. (*Radiola linoides* Roth)**

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Linum strictum* L. subsp. *strictum

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Linum suffruticosum* subsp. *loefflingii* Mart. Laborda & Muñoz Garm.**

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Linum trigynum* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

LINDERNIACEAE***Lindernia dubia* (L.) Pennell**

Gr / introduced / LC (IUCN)

LYTHRACEAE***Lythrum borysthenicum* (Schrank) Litv. (*Peplis borysthenica* Schrank)**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Lythrum hyssopifolia* L.**

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

***Lythrum portula* (L.) D.A. Webb (*Peplis portula* L.)**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Lythrum salicaria* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Lythrum thymifolia* L.**

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in San Pascual (UPOS18360), Aldeaseca and Ávila city (photographic evidence in UPOS).

***Lythrum tribracteatum* Spreng.**

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the endorheic lagoons of La Moraña (Sánchez-Villegas, 2022a).

MALVACEAE***Abutilon theophrasti* Medik.**

Gr / introduced

***Alcea rosea* L.**

Gr, Mo / introduced

***Malva alcea* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Malva hispanica* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

"Malva moschata L."

Notes: There is no herbarium evidence confirming the presence of this species in the province. It has been cited from the Iruelas valley (Molina Moreno, 1992), where *M. tournefortiana* is abundant and often exhibits forms with shallowly divided leaves.***Malva multiflora* (Cav.) Soldano, Banfi & Galasso (*Lavatera cretica* L.)**

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

***Malva neglecta* Wallr.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Malva nicaeensis* All.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Malva parviflora* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Malva setigera* K.F. Schimp. & Spenn. (*Althaea hirsuta* L.)**

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Specimens SALA52475 and W2017-10546 confirm the presence of this taxon in the province.

***Malva sylvestris* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Malva tournefortiana* L.**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Malvella sherardiana* (L.) Jaub. & Spach**

Mo / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), VU (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Notes: This species has only been collected in Arévalo (SALA58099).

Tilia platyphyllos Scop.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We are aware of only one wild or naturalised individual in the riparian forests along the Adaja river, within the municipality of Villanueva de Gómez (UPOS17474).

MELIACEAE

Melia azedarach L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Frequently cultivated and occasionally naturalised (Lázaro Bello, 2012).

MENYANTHACEAE

Menyanthes trifoliata L.

Gr / Circumboreal / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

MOLLUGINACEAE

Glinus lotoides L.

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Mollugo cerviana (L.) Ser.

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Mollugo verticillata L.

Gr / introduced

MONTIACEAE

Montia arvensis Wallr. (*M. fontana* subsp. *chondrosperma* (Fenzl) Walters)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Montia fontana subsp. *amporitana* Sennen

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

MORACEAE

Ficus carica L.

Gr, Ma / introduced

MYRTACEAE

Myrtus communis L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

NITRARIACEAE

Peganum harmala L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: This species is known in the province only from the Arévalo area (UPOS16930).

NYCTAGINACEAE

Mirabilis jalapa L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

OLEACEAE

Chrysojasminum fruticans (L.) Banfi (*Jasminum fruticans* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Fraxinus americana L.

Mo / introduced

Notes: Native to North America. Sporadically crop break in La Moraña (UPOS17448).

Fraxinus angustifolia Vahl

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Fraxinus excelsior L. subsp. *excelsior*

Gr / introduced

Notes: Eurosiberian species common in the northern part of the Iberian Peninsula, with a few individuals in Arenas de San Pedro, probably introduced.

Ligustrum vulgare L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: For the province, we have only confirmed three populations: the Fuentes Claras reservoir, near Ávila city (UPOS14192), Amavida (photographic evidence in UPOS), and Villanueva de Gómez (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Olea europaea L. subsp. *europaea*

Gr / Pluriregional / DD (IUCN)

Phillyrea angustifolia L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Syringa vulgaris L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break.

ONAGRACEAE

Circaea lutetiana L. subsp. *lutetiana*

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Epilobium anagallidifolium Lam.

Gr / Boreo-alpine / NE (IUCN)

Epilobium angustifolium L. subsp. *angustifolium*

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Epilobium brachycarpum C. Presl

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Epilobium collinum C.C. Gmel.

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Epilobium hirsutum L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Epilobium lanceolatum Sebast. & Mauri

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Epilobium montanum L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Epilobium obscurum Schreb.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Epilobium palustre L.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Epilobium parviflorum Schreb.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Epilobium tetragonum L. subsp. *tetragonum*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Ludwigia palustris (L.) Elliott

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Oenothera biennis L.

Gr / introduced

Oenothera glazioviana Micheli

Gr / introduced

Oenothera rosea Aiton

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in the municipal area of Candeleda (UPOS16933).

OROBANCHACEAE

Bellardia trixago (L.) All. (*Bartsia trixago* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Bellardia viscosa (L.) Fisch. & C.A. Mey. (*Parentucellia viscosa* (L.) Caruel)

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Euphrasia hirtella Jordan ex Reut.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Melampyrum pratense L. subsp. **latifolium**
Schülb. & G. Martens†

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only testimony of the presence of this nemoral species in Ávila is a collection by Isern in 1855 in the Pinar de Hoyocasero (MA156282), where it has not been found again since then.

Odontitella virgata (Link) Rothm. (*Odontites tenuifolius* (Pers.) G. Don)

Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only testimony of the presence of this species in the province comes from Guimorcondo (MA776624).

Odontites vernus (Bellardi) Dumort.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Odontites viscosus (L.) Clairv. subsp. **australis**
(Boiss.) Jahand. & Maire

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known for the province only from Muñogalindo (MA721518, SALA110147).

Orobanche alba Steph. ex Widld.

Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche amethystea Thuill.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche castellana Reut.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche foetida Poir.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche gracilis Sm.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche minor Sm.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche rapum-genistae Thuill.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Orobanche santolinae Loscos & J. Pardo

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Parentucellia latifolia (L.) Caruel

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Pedicularis schizocalyx (Lange) Steininger

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Pedicularis sylvatica L. subsp. **lusitanica**
(Hoffmanns. & Link) Cout.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Phelipanche arenaria (Borkh.) Pomel (*Orobanche arenaria* Borkh.)

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Phelipanche lavandulacea (Rchb.) Pomel subsp. **lavandulacea** (*Orobanche lavandulacea* Rchb.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Phelipanche nana (Noë ex Rchb.) Soják (*Orobanche nana* Noë ex Rchb.)

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Phelipanche purpurea (Jacq.) Soják (*Orobanche purpurea* Jacq.)

Gr? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: It has been reported for the province only from the Menga mountain pass (Fuertes Lasala, 1989b). We have not found it in the field trips carried out, nor we have seen the specimen that served as the basis for the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Foley, 2001).

Phelipanche rosarina (Welw. ex Beck) Banfi, Galasso & Soldano (*Orobanche rosarina* Welw. ex Beck)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Rhinanthus minor L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

OXALIDACEAE

Oxalis acetosella L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the Zapatero peak (Luceño *et al.*, 2016).

Oxalis articulata Savigny

Gr, Mo / introduced

Oxalis corniculata L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Oxalis pes-caprae L.

Gr / Introduced

Notes: Invasive thermophilic species native to Namibia and South Africa that has naturalized extensively in the south of the Iberian Peninsula and has recently arrived on the southern slopes of Gredos. We know populations in the Jerte valley, Madrigal de la Vera and Guisando (UPOS18065). It is included in the Spanish catalog of exotic invasive species.

PAEONIACEAE

Paeonia broteroi Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Paeonia officinalis L. subsp. **microcarpa** Nyman

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

PAPAVERACEAE

Ceratocarpus claviculata (L.) Lidén subsp. **claviculata**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Chelidonium majus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Eschscholzia californica Cham.

Gr / introduced

Fumaria bastardii Boreau

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Fumaria capreolata L.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Fumaria muralis W.D.J. Koch subsp. **muralis**

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Fumaria officinalis L. subsp. **officinalis**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Fumaria officinalis L. subsp. **wirtgenii** (W.D.J. Koch) Arcang.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: The specimens UPOS13438, from Villanueva de Gómez, and UPOS 18057, from Arenas de San Pedro, belong to this subspecies.

Fumaria parviflora Lam.

Gr?, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known in the Arévalo area (photographic evidence in UPOS), this species was cited from the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a), but we have not found herbarium evidence confirming this record.

Fumaria reuteri Boiss.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Fumaria vaillantii (L.) Rudolph

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: known from Blascosancho (SALA99533). The voucher SALA178855, collected recently in Arévalo,

contains a specimen whose identification is in doubt, since it could be *F. parviflora*.

Glaucium corniculatum (L.) Rudolph
Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the Arévalo area (SALA105674).

Hypecoum imberbe Sm.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Hypecoum pendulum* L.”

Notes: The records from the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a) lack herbarium evidence and, given the abundance of *H. imberbe* in the area, these records are possibly confusions with this latter species. We provisionally reject the presence of this taxon in the province, although it could be found in the Arévalo area, as Rico Hernández & Romero Martín (1987) collected it in the neighbouring Segovian municipality of Martín Muñoz de la Dehesa.

Papaver dubium L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Papaver rhoeas L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Papaver somniferum L. subsp. ***somniferum***

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally crop break in the south of the province and the vicinity of Ávila city (A. Arribas, photographic evidence).

Platycapnos spicata (L.) Bernh.

Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. We are aware of its presence in Hoyo de Pinares and Arévalo (UPOS17439).

Roemeria argemone (L.) C. Morales, R. Mend. & Romero García (*Papaver argemone* L.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Roemeria hybrida (L.) DC. subsp. ***hybrida***

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Confirmed for the province from Arévalo (UPOS17440).

Roemeria sicula (Guss.) Galasso, Banfi, L. Sáez & Bartolucci (*Papaver hybridum* Lam.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Mirueña de los Infanzones (SALA137160) and Arévalo (F. de Sande, pers. comm.).

PASSIFLORACEAE

Passiflora caerulea L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Occasionally garden break.

PHYLLANTHACEAE

Flueggea tinctoria (L.) G.L. Webster

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from the banks of the Tiétar river in Candeleda (Sánchez-Mata *et al.*, 1991), Pedro Bernardo, and Lanzahíta (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.).

PHYTOLACCACEAE

Phytolacca americana L.

Gr / introduced

PLANTAGINACEAE

Anarrhinum bellidifolium (L.) Willd.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Antirrhinum graniticum Rothm.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Antirrhinum grosii Font Quer

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), EN (IUCN)

Antirrhinum meonathum Hoffmanns. & Link

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Callitriche brutia Petagna subsp. ***brutia***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Callitriche lusitanica Schotsman

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / EN (LRE), NT (IUCN)

Callitriche palustris L.

Gr / Boreo-alpine / Preferential attention (C and L), EN (LRE), LC (IUCN)

Callitriche stagnalis Scop.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Chaenorhinum minus (L.) Lange subsp. ***minus***

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Cymbalaria muralis P. Gaertn. B. Mey & Schreb. subsp. ***muralis***

Gr, Mo, Ma / introduced

Digitalis purpurea L. subsp. ***purpurea***

Gr / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Digitalis thapsi L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Gratiola linifolia Vahl

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Gratiola officinalis L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Linaria aeruginea (Gouan) Cav. subsp. ***aeruginea***

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Linaria alpina (L.) DC. subsp. ***alpina***

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Linaria amethystea (Vent.) Hoffm. & Link subsp. ***amethystea***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Linaria arvensis (L.) Desf.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Linaria bipunctata (L.) Chaz. subsp. ***bipunctata***

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, we know it from the municipalities of Hernansancho (UPOS16937) and Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas, 2020).

Linaria caesia (Pers.) F. Diétr.

Mo / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Linaria elegans Cav.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Linaria incarnata (Vent.) Spreng.

Ma? / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cited in Guimorcondo (Rivas Goday, 1958) and considered as part of Ávila's flora by *Flora Iberica* (Sáez, 2009), but we have not found any evidence of its presence in the province. However, we have collected the species in the northeast of Cáceres, near the provincial border with Ávila.

Linaria nivea Boiss. & Reut.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Linaria saxatilis (L.) Chaz.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Linaria simplex Willd. ex Desf.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Linaria spartea (L.) Chaz.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Linaria triornithophora (L.) Cav.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Linaria vettonica Luceño, Mazuecos & P. Vargas

Gr / Iberian endemism / CR (IUCN)

“*Linaria viscosa* L.) Chaz.”

Notes: The records from Ávila are confusions with *L. spartea* (cf. Fernández-Mazuecos *et al.*, 2018).

Littorella uniflora (L.) Asch.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Misopates orontium (L.) Raf.

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Plantago afra L.

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Plantago albicans L.

Gr?, Mo? / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Cited from the Muñozerro area (Molina & Izco, 1986) and the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989), but we have not found herbarium specimens to confirm its presence in the province.

Plantago alpina L.

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Plantago bellardii All. subsp. ***bellardii***

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Plantago coronopus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Plantago lagopus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Plantago lanceolata L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Plantago loeflingii Loefl. ex L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Scattered in the north of the province (Arévalo; SALA168953).

Plantago major L.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Some authors recognize two subspecies: the type, and subsp. *intermedia* (Gillib.) Lange, which are differentiated by leaf shape and the number of seeds per fruit. The materials we have seen from Ávila correspond usually to subsp. *intermedia*, although some individuals display intermediate characteristics between both subspecies.

Plantago maritima subsp. ***serpentina*** (All.) Arcang.

Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Plantago media L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Plantago sempervirens Crantz

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We are aware of two vouchers of this species in the province from Blascosancho and Hernansancho (UPOS16845 and UPOS16932).

Plantago subulata L. (*P. holosteum* Scop.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Plantago tenuiflora Walds. & Kit.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Species recently found in halophilic meadows of San Pascual (UPOS18362). It was collected a few years ago in the province of Valladolid (Pedrol *et al.*, in prep.).

Pseudomisopates rivasmartinezii (Sánchez Mata) Güemes

Gr / Iberian endemism / Endangered (C and L), CR (LRE), CR (IUCN)

Sibthorpia europaea L.

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Veronica alpina L.

Gr / Boreo-alpine / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A snowbed-inhabiting species with a boreo-alpine distribution, which in the Iberian Peninsula occurs in the high summits of the Pyrenees, Cantabrian Mountains, Sierra Nevada, and Iberian System. In the Central System, it is only known from the headwaters of the Hoyo Malillo cirque (western massif of Gredos; SALA132388, 132389). The population comprises only about 10 individuals, so despite not being included in any red list, we think that it should be protected.

Veronica anagallis-aquatica L. subsp. ***anagallis-aquatica***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Veronica anagalloides Guss. subsp. ***anagalloides***

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Veronica arvensis L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Veronica beccabunga L. subsp. ***beccabunga***

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Veronica chamaedrys L. subsp. ***chamaedrys***

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN).

Notes: Very rare in the province, where only one population is known, located in the Villafranca mountain range (Estrada Sánchez, 1986).

Veronica cymbalaria Bodard

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN).

Notes: Very rare in the province. Recently collected in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18358).

Veronica fruticans Jacq. subsp. ***cantabrica*** M. Laínz

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Veronica hederifolia L. subsp. ***hederifolia***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Veronica micrantha Hoffmanns. & Link

Gr / Iberian endemism / VU (C and L), VU (LRE), VU (IUCN)

Veronica montana L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. Known exclusively from Castañar del Tiemblo (SALA132388, 132389; UPOS17325).

Veronica nevadensis (Pau) Pau

Gr / Iberian endemism / LC (IUCN)

Veronica officinalis L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Veronica peregrina L. subsp. ***peregrina***

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to America. Naturalised in the Rosarito reservoir (UPOS15676).

Veronica persica Poir.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Veronica polita Fr. subsp. ***polita***

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited as a new record for Ávila (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Veronica praecox All.

Gr?, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: There does not appear to be herbarium evidence to confirm the citation of this plant from the Amblés valley (Fuertes Lasala, 1989b). However, its presence in the province is insured by the voucher SALA178843 collected in Cantazorras (Arévalo).

Veronica scutellata L.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Veronica serpyllifolia L. subsp. ***serpyllifolia***

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Veronica tenuifolia Asso subsp. ***javambrensis*** (Pau) Molero & J. Pujadas
Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)
Notes: Very rare in the province. Known only from Las Navas del Marqués (MA481410, SALA155091).

Veronica triphyllos L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Veronica verna L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

PLATANACEAE

Platanus orientalis L. var. ***acerifolia*** Aiton (*P. × hispanica* Münchh.)

Gr / introduced

Notes: Frequently cultivated in villages and towns. Naturalized in some gorges of the Tiétar valley.

PLUMBAGINACEAE

Armeria arenaria (Pers.) Schult. subsp. ***arenaria***

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The only voucher of this subspecies in Ávila comes from El Oso (UPOS16944).

Armeria arenaria subsp. ***segoviensis*** (Gand. ex Bernis) Nieto Fel.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Armeria arenaria subsp. ***vestita*** (Willk.) Nieto Fel.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: This species is endangered due to introgression with *A. transmontana* and *A. arenaria* subsp. *segoviensis* (Nieto Feliner, 1990). In the province, we only know one voucher from Poyales del Hoyo (MA145540).

Armeria bigerrensis (Pau ex Caballero) Rivas Mart. subsp. ***bigerrensis***

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Armeria caespitosa (Gómez Ortega) Boiss.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare on the summits of the central massif of Gredos, where it is being assimilated by introgression with *A. bigerrensis*; more common in Cueva Valiente, Zapatero peak and La Serrota.

“*Armeria castroviejoii* Nieto Fel.”

Notes: Considered by Nieto Feliner (1990) as present in Ávila, the vouchers MA145543 and MAF60599, collected by Lacaíta “inter Ávila et Peñaranda” include specimens identified by Nieto Feliner as *A. arenaria* subsp. *segoviensis* × *A. castroviejoii*. This author (pers. comm.) is not aware of any material of *A. castroviejoii* for the province. Therefore, we provisionally rule out the presence of this plant in Ávila.

Armeria rivasmartinezii Sard.Rosc. & Nieto Fel.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NT (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Armeria transmontana (Samp.) G.H.M. Lawr.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Plumbago europaea L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

POLYGALACEAE

Polygala microphylla L.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Polygala monspeliaca L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in Muñozerro (SALA177032).

Polygala serpyllifolia Hosé

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Polygala vulgaris L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

POLYGONACEAE

Fallopia baldschuanica (Regel) Holub

Gr, Mo / introduced

Fallopia convolvulus (L.) Á. Löve

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Fallopia dumetorum (L.) Holub

Gr / Eurasian / (IUCN)

Koenigia alpina (All.) T.M. Schust. & Reveal (*Polygonum alpinum* All.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Persicaria amphibia (L.) Delarbre (*Polygonum amphibium* L.)

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare. Las Cogotas reservoir (García Muñoz, 2004), Arevalillo, and the Adaja river (F. de Sande, pers. comm.).

Persicaria hydropiper (L.) Delarbre (*Polygonum hydropiper* L.)

Gr / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Persicaria lapathifolia (L.) Delarbre (*Polygonum lapathifolium* L.)

Gr, Ma?, Mo / Subcosmopolitan / LC (IUCN)

Persicaria maculosa Gray (*Polygonum persicaria* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Polygonum arenastrum Boreau

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Polygonum aviculare L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Polygonum bellardii All.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In the province, we only know it from San Pascual (UPOS16931).

Polygonum equisetiforme Sm.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: In Ávila, we only know it from San Pascual (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Polygonum rurivagum Jord. ex Boreau

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Rumex acetosa L. subsp. ***acetosa***

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Rumex acetosella L. subsp. ***angiocarpus*** (Murb.) Murb.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Rumex bucephalophorus L. subsp. ***gallicus*** (Steinh.) Rech. fil.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Rumex conglomeratus Murray

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Rumex crispus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Rumex cristatus DC.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Recently cited from the municipality of Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

Rumex induratus Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Rumex intermedius* DC.”

Notes: Molina Moreno’s (1992) record is likely a confusion with *R. papillaris*. We have visited the exact locality indicated, and there is common *R. papillaris*.

***Rumex longifolius* DC.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Rumex obtusifolius* L.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Rumex papillaris* Boiss. & Reut.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Rumex pulcher* L. subsp. *woodsii* (De Not.) Arcang.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Rumex roseus* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Rumex sanguineus* L.**

Gr? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We have not seen herbarium materials supporting the records from southern Ávila (Rivas Martínez *et al.*, 1986; Sardinero Roscales, 2004).

***Rumex scutatus* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from the slope of Cinco Lagunas (González Canalejo, 1980).

***Rumex suffruticosus* Willk.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

PORTULACACEAE***Calandrinia ciliata* (Ruiz & Pav.) DC.**

Gr / introduced

Notes: Native to America. Naturalised in the Rosarito reservoir (UPOS15675).

***Portulaca oleracea* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

PRIMULACEAE***Androsace elongata* L. subsp. *breistrofferi***

(Charpin & Greut.) Molero & J.M. Monts.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the surroundings of Ávila city (MA90925).

***Androsace maxima* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from the Amblés valley (Sánchez-Villegas, 2020).

Androsace vitaliana* (L.) Lapeyr. subsp. *aureliiLuceño (*Androsace centriterica* (Kress) Kress)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Lysimachia arvensis* (L.) U. Manns & Anderb.**(*Anagallis arvensis* L. subsp. *arvensis*)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Lysimachia ephemerum* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Recently reported for Arenas de San Pedro and Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

***Lysimachia linum-stellatum* L. (*Asterolinon linum-stellatum* (L.) Duby)**

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Lysimachia minima* (L.) U. Manns & Anderb.**(*Anagallis minima* (L.) E.H.L. Krause)

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known from Mengamuñoz (Rivas Martínez, 1985).

***Lysimachia monelli* (L.) U. Manns & Anderb.**(*Anagallis monelli* L.)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Lysimachia tenella* L. (*Anagallis tenella* (L.) L.)**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Lysimachia vulgaris* L.**

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Primula acaulis* (L.) L. subsp. *acaulis

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Primula intricata* Gren. & Godr. subsp. *bergidensis* (Kress) Kress**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Kress (1997) considered the plants from the Central System as *P. elatior* subsp. *lofthousei*; however, a recent study (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, in preparation) shows that the populations in the Central System should be included in subsp. *bergidensis*, described a few years ago in the Montes de León (Kress, 2016).

***Primula veris* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

RANUNCULACEAE***Aconitum lycoctomum* L. (*A. vulparia* Rchb. subsp. *neapolitanum* (Ten.) Muñoz-Garm.)**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Aconitum napellus* subsp. *lusitanicum* Rouy (incl. *A. napellus* subsp. *castellanum* Molero & C. Blanché)**

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Actaea spicata* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Adonis aestivalis* L. subsp. *squarrosa* (Steven)**

Nyman

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Adonis annua* L.**

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known from the Arévalo area (SALA168996) and the surroundings of Ávila city (photographic evidence in UPOS).

***Adonis flammea* Jacq.**

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known from the Arévalo area (SALA168933, 168447).

***Anemone nemorosa* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. The only known location in the Iberian Central System is in the vicinity of San Martín del Pimpollar (MA740143; UPOS12902).

***Anemone palmata* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Aquilegia dichroa* Freyn**

Gr? / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: This species was reported between Arenas de San Pedro and Candeleda (Rivas Goday *et al.*, 1959), but there is not any herbarium material testifying its presence in Ávila, although it would not be surprising, since it is well known from the western parts of Gredos: Candelario, Salamanca (UPOS12025), and Jerte and Ambroz valleys, Cáceres (photographic evidence in UPOS).

***Aquilegia hispanica* Willk.**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Aquilegia vulgaris* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Caltha palustris* L.**

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

***Ceratocephala falcata* (L.) Pers.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Present in Cantazorras (Arévalo; photographic evidence in UPOS).

Clematis vitalba L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Delphinium ajacis L. (*Consolida ajacis* (L.) Schur)

Gr / introduced

Delphinium bithynicum Griseb. (*Delphinium hispanicum* Costa; *Consolida hispanica* (Costa) Greuter & Burdet; *C. orientalis* auct., non Schrödinger)

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Delphinium fissum Waldst. & Kit. subsp. ***sordidum*** (Cuatrec.) Amich, E. Rico & J. Sánchez.

Gr / Iberian endemism / Endangered (C and L), EN (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the Villatoro mountain pass (Ramírez Rodríguez *et al.*, 2016).***Delphinium gracile*** DC.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Delphinium halteratum Sm. subsp. ***verdunense*** (Balbis) Graebn. & P. Graebn.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently reported for the province (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).***Delphinium pubescens*** DC. (*Consolida pubescens* (DC.) Soó)

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the Arévalo area (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).***Ficaria ambigua*** Boreau (*Ficaria verna* subsp. *fertilis* (Laegaard) Stace)

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Most of the studied materials from Ávila belong to *F. verna*, common in riverside forests of Gredos that were altered due to human activities. *F. ambigua* also lives in these environments but in better-preserved conditions. In the province, we only know it from Junciana (UPOS16904).***Ficaria verna*** Huds. (*Ranunculus ficaria* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Helleborus foetidus L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

“*Helleborus viridis* L. subsp. *occidentalis* (Reut.) Schiffn.”

Notes: The provincial records date back to the 19th century (Willkomm & Lange, 1874–1880) and have not been confirmed by herbarium evidence.

Myosurus minimus L.

Gr, Mo / Circumboreal / (IUCN)

Nigella damascena L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Collected in Berrocalejo de Aragón (UPOS16960) and observed in Sotillo de la Adrada and Lanzahita (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.).

Nigella gallica Jord.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Pulsatilla alpina (L.) Delarbre subsp. ***apiifolia*** (Scop.) Nyman

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus abnormis Cut. & Willk.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus aconitifolius L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus amplexicaulis L.

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus arvensis L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus baudotii Godr.

Mo / Eurasian / (IUCN)

Notes: We only know it from El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).***Ranunculus bulbosus*** L. subsp. ***aleae*** (Willk.) Rouy & Foucaud

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus cherubicus (J. Sánchez Rodr. M.J. Elías & M.A. Martín) Fern. Prieto, Sanna, M. Pérez & Cires subsp. ***cherubicus***

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), DD (LRE), NE (IUCN).

Notes: An endemic taxon to Gredos with only six known populations in the central and western massifs.

Ranunculus flammula L.

Gr, Ma / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Ranunculus gramineus L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus hederaceus L.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Ranunculus lateriflorus DC.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. Junciana (photographic evidence in UPOS), Solosanco (SALA41231) and Rasueros (SALA49380).

Ranunculus longipes Cutanda

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from Junciana (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019) and also known from Candeleda (UPOS17641).***Ranunculus muricatus*** L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus nodiflorus L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus ollissiponensis subsp. ***alpinus*** (Boiss & Reut.) Grau

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Of the province it is known only from the Zapatero Peak (MA740142). However, in the central massif of Gredos, individuals with intermediate characteristics between this race and subsp. *ollissiponensis* can be observed.***Ranunculus ollissiponensis*** Pers. subsp. ***ollissiponensis***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus ololeucos J. Lloyd

Gr / Atlantic / DD (IUCN)

Ranunculus omiophyllus Ten.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: We have not found bibliographic references or herbarium materials that justify the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Cook, 1986). Nevertheless, the presence of this species in the province is quite likely because it is not scarce in the southeast of Salamanca, very close to the border with Ávila (Pizarro Domínguez & Sardinero Roscales, 2002).***Ranunculus ophioglossifolius*** Vill.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. La Adrada (MAF174233), Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS12913), Losar del Barco (UPOS12971), and Candeleda (UPOS11964).

Ranunculus paludosus Poir. subsp. ***paludosus***

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Ranunculus parviflorus L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Uncommon in the province. Collected in Becedas (UPOS11523) and Junciana (UPOS11655). Also observed in Arévalo.

Ranunculus peltatus Schrank

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Ranunculus penicillatus (Dumort.) Bab.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

"Ranunculus platanifolius L."

Notes: The material from the western massif of Gredos (Puerto Castilla; SALA1282) that served as the basis for the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (López González, 1986) belongs to *R. aconitifolius*, which is quite common in that section of the mountain range. We have also reviewed the specimen VIT88991, collected in Candelario (Salamanca), and it also contains a specimen of *R. aconitifolius*. Therefore, we discard the presence of *R. platanifolius* in the province.

Ranunculus repens L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Ranunculus saniculifolius Viv.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Ranunculus sceleratus L.

Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Rare in the province. We recently collected it at Laguna del Hoyo (El Oso; UPOS13203).

Ranunculus trichophyllus Chaix subsp. *trichophyllus*

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Ranunculus trilobus Desf.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Thalictrum minus subsp. *saxatile* Ces. (*Th. minus* L. subsp. *matritense* (Pau) P. Monts., *Th. minus* subsp. *pubescens* Arcang.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Thalictrum speciosissimum L. subsp. *speciosissimum*

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Trollius europaeus L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

RESEDACEAE**Reseda gredensis** (Cutanda & Willk.) Müll. Arg.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Reseda lutea L. subsp. *lutea*

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Reseda luteola L. subsp. *luteola*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Reseda phyteuma L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known in the province from the surroundings of Ávila city (SALA128787), as well as in La Moraña.

Reseda virgata Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Sesamoides purpurascens (L.) G. López subsp. *purpurascens*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

"*Sesamoides purpurascens* subsp. *suffruticosa* (Lange) Kunze"

Notes: The references to Ávila from the Amblés (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a) and Iruelas (Molina Moreno, 1992) valleys are confusions with *S. purpurascens*.

RHAMNACEAE**Frangula alnus** Mill. subsp. *alnus*

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Rhamnus cathartica L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

ROSACEAE**Agrimonia eupatoria** L. subsp. *eupatoria*

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Agrimonia procera Wallr.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Alchemilla alpina L.

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The specimens attributed to this taxon are sometimes challenging to distinguish from *A. saxatilis* since the leaves mostly have 5 leaflets, although some individuals have 6 or, very rarely, 7. In our opinion, the best character to distinguish both taxa is the relative length between the flowering culms and the petiole of the basal leaves. In the province, we know it from Sierra de Béjar (SALA167307; UPOS16095) and Zapatero peak (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Alchemilla atropurpurea S.E. Fröhner

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The reference to Ávila province of this taxon in *Flora iberica* (Fröhner, 1998) is based on the voucher MA304922, collected by A. González Canalejo in La Herguijuela (Villafranca mountain range) in 1974; however, despite the numerous surveys we have conducted in the wet meadows and peat bogs of this mountain range, we have been unable to locate the species.

Alchemilla coriacea Buser

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Alchemilla saxatilis Buser

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Alchemilla serratisaxatilis S.E. Fröhner

Gr / Iberian endemism / DD (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Alchemilla straminea Buser

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Alchemilla transiens (Buser) Buser

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Amelanchier ovalis Medik. subsp. *ovalis*

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Aphanes arvensis L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Aphanes australis Rydb.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Aphanes cornucopioides Lag.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Aphanes microcarpa (Boiss. & Reut.) Rothm.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Aria edulis (Willd.) M. Roem. (*Sorbus aria* (L.) Crantz.)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Sporadic in some northern Gredos valleys.

Comarum palustre L. (*Potentilla palustris* (L.) Scop.)

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Cornus domestica (L.) Spach (*Sorbus domestica* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: A very rare tree in the province. The only herbarium specimens we are aware of, were collected in the Mijares mountain pass (SALA68593) and Serranillos (SALA68595).

Crataegus monogyna Jacq.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Dryocallis rupestris (L.) Soják subsp. *rupestris* (*Potentilla rupestris* L.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Filipendula ulmaria (L.) Maxim.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Filipendula vulgaris Moench

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Fragaria vesca L. subsp. *vesca*

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Fragaria x ananassa (Weston) Duchesne

Gr / introduced

Geum hispidum Fr.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Geum rivale L.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Geum sylvaticum Pourr.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Geum urbanum L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Karpatiosorbus latifolia (Lam.) Sennikov & Kurtto
(*Sorbus latifolia* (Lam.) Pers.)

Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A very rare species in Ávila. It has only been recorded from Las Navas del Marqués (Baonza, 2004) based on the specimen EMMA7299.

Malus domestica (Borkh.) Borkh.

Gr / introduced

Malus sylvestris (L.) Mill.

Gr / Eurasian / DD (IUCN)

Notes: Uncommon in the Tiétar valley (UPOS18062).

Potentilla argentea L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Potentilla asturica Rothm.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Potentilla erecta (L.) Raeusch.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Potentilla micrantha Ramond ex DC.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the Villafranca mountain range (Estrada Sánchez, 1986).

Potentilla pensylvanica L.

Gr, Mo / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Potentilla pyrenaica DC.

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Potentilla recta L.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Most of the provincial records are likely misidentifications of *Potentilla asturica*. The only voucher we know in the province is from Arévalo (SALA99600). It is a species that prefers human-altered sites. We also confirm its presence in the Jerte valley (SALA94941).**Potentilla reptans** L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Potentilla verna L. (*P. neumanniana* Rchb.)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. It has only been collected in Villanueva del Campillo (SALA9087; UPOS12840) and Blascosancho (UPOS18365).

Poterium hybridum L. (*Sanguisorba hybrida* (L.) Font Quer)

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Poterium sanguisorba L. subsp. *sanguisorba*
(*Sanguisorba minor* Scop. subsp. *minor*)

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

“*Poterium sanguisorba* subsp. *balearica* (Nyman) Stace (*Sanguisorba minor* subsp. *balearica* (Bourg. ex Nyman) Muñoz Garm. & C. Navarro)”Notes: The only citation in Ávila (Molina Moreno, 1992), not supported by an herbarium specimen, is likely a confusion with the subsp. *minor*.**Poterium verrucosum** Link ex Don (*Sanguisorba verrucosa* (Link ex Don) Ces.)

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Prunus avium L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Prunus cerasus L.

Gr / introduced

Prunus domestica L.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Prunus dulcis (Mill.) D.A. Webb

Gr / introduced

Prunus insititia L.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Wild plum is very rare in Ávila. Citations from Arenas de San Pedro (Rivas Goday *et al.*, 1959) and the Villatoro mountain pass (Fuertes Lasala, 1989a) are likely misidentifications of *P. spinosa*, which is common in those areas. It can also be confused with naturalised plum trees. In Ávila, it is only known from the riparian forests along the Adaja river, in the municipality of Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).**Prunus laurocerasus** L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalized in riparian forests of Arenas de San Pedro and Lanzahíta (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.).

Prunus lusitanica L. subsp. *lusitanica*

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / VU (C and L), VU (LRE), VU (IUCN, at European level)

Notes: *Prunus lusitanica* forests are relics of a time when the climate in the area was subtropical. The species was first recorded in the Santa María gorge (Gómez Ortega, 1784) and has since been found in other locations on the southern slopes of Gredos (Vargas & Luceño, 1987; López Sáez, 1995).**Prunus padus** L. subsp. *padus*

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Prunus spinosa L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Pyrus bourgaeana Decne.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Pyrus communis L.

Gr / introduced

Rosa agrestis Savi

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Rosa arvensis Huds.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from Castañar del Tiemblo (Zamora & Jiménez-Mejías, 2013).

“*Rosa blondaeanana* Ripart ex Déségl.”

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Silvestre & Montserrat (1998) considered *R. blondaeanana* as a microspecies of dog-roses that is characterized by being glabrous plants with biserrate folioles and glandular pedicels; however, some authors (Bakker *et al.*, 2019; POWO, 2024) consider these plants as hybrids between *R. canina* s.s. and *R. rubiginosa* L. (*R. x nitidula* Besser). In any case, we have visited the localities of Avila (Navacepedilla de Corneja and Valle de Iruelas) from where *R. blondaeanana* has been reported (Estrada Sánchez, 1986; Molina Moreno, 1992) and what we have found is *R. pouzinii* Tratt., since these plants show abundant glands on the margins of the leaflets, and more scattered on the midrib of the underside.

Rosa caesia Sm. (*R. coriifolia* Fr.)

Gr / Eurasian / (IUCN)

Notes: According to Silvestre & Montserrat (1998), *R. caesia* and *R. coriifolia* would be two different microspecies, the former with “glandulose pedicels or sepals” and the latter without; however, this seem to be a rather variable character (cf. Klášterský, 1968), so recent works (Kurtto, 2009; POWO, 2024) consider *R. coriifolia* as a synonym of *R. caesia*. In the province this species is known from Villafranca mountain range (UPOS17552, 17566) and Hoyos del Espino (UPOS14397).

Rosa canina L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Rosa corymbifera Borkh.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: *R. squarrosa* and *R. corymbifera* are the most common species of the genus in the province.

Rosa deseglisei Boreau

Gr? / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: This plant have been recorded by Sardinero Roscales (1994) from several localities in the province and considered as present in Ávila by Silvestre & Montserrat (1998), but we have not be able to find this species in these localities; nevertheless we have observed individuals of the *Rosa canina* group with hairy folioles, glandulose pedicels and reflexed sepals at maturity, features characterising the Boureau’s plant, but these specimens also show some glands in the midrib and/or scattered by the lower side of the folioles, which show simple-double mixed denticulation. We interpret these morphotypes as hybrids between *R. micrantha* and *R. corymbifera*, both present in these areas. Our materials from Junciana (UPOS13119 and 18353) also clearly show a transition in characters between *R. micrantha* and *R. corymbifera*, and they inhabit close to typical individuals of these species.

Rosa dumalis Bechst. (*R. vosagiaca* Déségl., nom. superfl.)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: On the one hand, Bakker *et al.* (2019) considered the name *R. dumalis* Bechst. as applicable to the hybrid between *R. squarrosa* (A. Rau) Boreau and *R. vosagiaca* Déségl., and that the correct name for glabrous plants with wholly styles almost hiding the disc, wide orifice, eglandular folioles and sepals erect or patent, persistent at maturity of the fruit should be *R. vosagiaca*. However, Reichert (2021) showed that *R. vosagiaca* Déségl. is an illegitimate name (nom. superfl.) and that the neotype designated by Loos (1996) fits well with Bechtein’s protologue. Consequently, we believe that the correct name for this plant should be *R. dumalis*. On the other hand, Silvestre and Montserrat (1998) considered that *R. vosagiaca* is a different species from *R. dumalis*, given that the former would have leaflets with simple denticulation whereas the latter would show biserrate leaflets. If Silvestre and Montserrat (1998) were right, the correct name of the plants with simple denticulation should be *R. reuteri* (Godet) Reut. (cf. Reichert, 2021). Since the materials from Ávila that we have studied show a high variability for this character, we consider *R. vosagiaca* to be synonymous with *R. dumalis*.

Rosa foetida Herrm.

Gr / introduced

Notes: Naturalised in Ávila city (García Muñoz, 2004).

Rosa gallica L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: The plant reported from Arenas de San Pedro by Sánchez-Villegas *et al.* (2020) under the name of *R. pimpinellifolia* L. (*R. spinosissima* L.), actually belong to *R. gallica* L., a species widely cultivated and naturalized in the past that is getting rarer in the Iberian Peninsula (Silvestre & Montserrat, 1998).

Rosa glauca Pourr.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: A rose known in the Iberian Central System only from Hoyo Malillo (Sierra de Béjar; Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Rosa micrantha Sm.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Rosa pouzinii Tratt.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Although not explicitly mentioned for the province, this rose is common on both sides of Gredos (e.g. Navalanguilla, UPOS11139; Candeleda, UPOS11738).

Rosa rubiginosa L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. We recently collected it at Puerto Castilla (UPOS16907, 18354, 18355, 18356). This species is frequently confused with the common *R. micrantha*, from which it is differentiated by its woolly styles, its disc orifice wider than 1.1 mm and its erect or patent sepals, always present at the maturity of the fruit.

Rosa squarrosa (A. Rau) Boreau

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We include under this name the glabrous dog-rose plants that have reflexed and caducous sepals at fruit maturity, eglandulose pedicels and hypanthium, glabrous or slightly hairy styles, broad disc with orifice up to 1(1.1) mm wide and leaflets of the fertile branches with double denticulation, usually with a few glands scattered on the margins, petiole, raquis and/or midrib on the lower side.

“Rosa tomentosa Sm.”

Notes: The provincial records of this Eurosiberian species (Sánchez Mata, 1989) are likely confusions with other species with hairy leaves and their hybrids. None of the numerous materials collected in the cited localities (Navalsauz and between Navarredondilla and Navatalgordo) and other areas of the province belong to this species.

Rosa villosa L.

Gr / Eurasian / DD (IUCN)

Rubus aetnicus Weston (*R. canescens* auct., non DC.)

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited as *R. canescens* from the southern slopes of Gredos (Sánchez-Villegas, 2019).

Rubus carpetanus Vicente Orell. & A. Galán

Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: a recently described blackberry from the Sierra de Guadarrama (Vicente-Orellana & Galán-de-Mera, 2020) that reaches Avila only in Peguerinos.

Rubus castellarnau Pau

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The vouchers MA535021 and MA558265, collected between Becedas and San Bartolomé de Béjar, were identified by Monasterio Huelín.

Rubus castroviejo Mon.-Huelin

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently reported from the western massif of Gredos (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Rubus hoyoqueseranus Pau

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Microspecies of the *Corylifolii* section, whose taxonomic value should be clarified through systematic studies.

Rubus idaeus L.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN).

Notes: Very rare in megaphorbic communities in the highlands of Gredos.

Rubus praecox Bertol.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Common in riparian forests along the Tormes river, near El Barco de Ávila (UPOS17580). Also collected in basic soils in the municipality of Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS13078).

Rubus radula Weihe

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Quite common in the western part of the northern slopes of Gredos, reaching considerable altitudes (up to 2050 m asl).

Rubus ulmifolius Schott

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Rubus vagabundus Samp.

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Sporadic in the northern slopes of Gredos (MAF143841; UPOS12351).

Rubus vigoii R. Roselló, Perich & Stübing

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Relatively common in the western part of the northern slopes of Gredos.

Sanguisorba officinalis L.

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Sorbus aucuparia L. subsp. *aucuparia*

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

“*Torminalis glaberrima* (Gand.) Sennikov & Kurtto (*Sorbus torminalis* (L.) Crantz.)”

Notes: We are not aware of the herbarium specimen on which Aedo & Aldasoro (1998) based the inclusion of Ávila in the Iberian distribution of this species. We are familiar with an old record from the Pinar de Hoyocasero (Teixidor y Cos, 1871) mentioned by Colmeiro (1873). Currently, it no longer inhabits that forest; what we observed a few decades ago was *Aria edulis*. Finally, the presence of *Torminalis glaberrima* in the Arenal river (Calleja Alarcón, 2006) seems implausible, and there is no herbarium specimen to support it.

RUBIACEAE

Asperula arvensis L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Its presence in the province is confirmed by the specimen UPOS16922, collected in La Colilla, near Ávila city.

Crucianella angustifolia L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Crucianella patula L.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We are aware of only two vouchers from the province, both from Arévalo (SALA135376, 177106).

Cruciata glabra (L.) Ehrend. (incl. subsp. *hirticaulis* (Beck.) Natali & Jeanm.)

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Cruciata pedemontana (Bellardi) Ehrend.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Cynanchica aristata (L. f.) P. Caputo & Del Guacchio. subsp. *scabra* (J. Presl. & C. Presl. ex Lange) Nyman (*Asperula aristata* L. f. subsp. *scabra* (J. Presl. & C. Presl. ex Lange) Nyman)

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Galium album Mill. (*G. mollugo* L. subsp. *erectum* Syme)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Galium aparine L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Galium broterianum Boiss. & Reut.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Galium divaricatum Lam. (*G. parisiense* L. subsp. *divaricatum* (Lam.) Rouy & E.G. Camus)

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Galium lucidum subsp. *fruticescens* (Cav.) O. Bolòs & Vigo

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We are aware of only one population in the Adaja hills (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

Galium lucidum All. subsp. *lucidum*

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Galium mollugo L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited in the province (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Galium palustre L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

Galium papillosum Lapeyr. subsp. *papillosum*

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

“*Galium papillosum* subsp. *helodes* (Hoffmanns. & Link) Ortega Oliv. & Devesa”

Notes: The only mention from Ávila comes from Navacedilla de Corneja (Estrada Sánchez, 1986); however, it doesn't seem to be supported by an herbarium specimen. What we have found in the area is the subsp. *papillosum*.

Galium parisiense L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Galium rotundifolium L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. We have recently confirmed that a small population persists in the Pinar de Hoyocasero (UPOS16906).

Galium saxatile L.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Galium scabrum L.

Gr / Mediterranean / Preferential attention (C and L), NE (IUCN)

Galium spurium L. subsp. *spurium* (*G. aparine* subsp. *spurium* (L.) Hartm.)

Gr / Pluriregional / NE (IUCN)

Galium tricornutum Dandy

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently reported from El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019). Also present in the Arévalo area.

Galium verrucosum Huds. Subsp. *verrucosum*

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently collected in Arenas de San Pedro (UPOS18059).

Galium verum L. subsp. *verum*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Rubia peregrina L. subsp. *peregrina*

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Rubia tinctorum L.

Gr, Mo / introduced

Notes: Confirmed from Villafranca de la Sierra (SALA124787).

Sherardia arvensis L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

RUTACEAE

Dictamnus albus L.

Gr / Eurasian / Preferential attention (C and L), LC (IUCN)

Haplophyllum linifolium (L.) G. Don subsp. *linifolium*
Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only from the Arévalo area (MA862041, SALA135378).

Ruta montana (L.) L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

SALICACEAE

Populus alba L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Populus nigra L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Populus tremula L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Salix alba L.

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Salix atrocinnerea Brot.

Gr, Ma / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Sx fragilis L. (*S. alba* L. x *S. euxina* I.V. Belyaeva)

Gr, Mo / introduced / NE (IUCN)

Salix purpurea L.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Salix salviifolia Brot.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Salix triandra L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Salix viminalis L.

Gr / introduced

SANTALACEAE

Arceuthobium oxycedri (DC.) M. Bieb.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Osyris alba L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Thesium humifusum DC.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Viscum album subsp. *austriacum* (Wiesb.) Vollm.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

SAPINDACEAE

Acer monspessulanum L. subsp. *monspessulanum*

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

Acer negundo L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: We have seen it naturalised in the municipality of Candeleda.

Acer platanoides L.

Gr / introduced

Acer pseudoplatanus L.

Gr / introduced

Aesculus hippocastanum L.

Gr / introduced

Notes: We know it naturalised in El Barco de Ávila.

SAXIFRAGACEAE

Micranthes stellaris (L.) Galasso, Banfi & Soldano subsp. *stellaris* (*Saxifraga stellaris* L.)

Gr / Circumboreal / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga carpetana Boiss. & Reut. subsp. *carpetana*

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga dichotoma Willd.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga fragosoi Sennen

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga granulata L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga pentadactylis Lapeyr. subsp. *almanzorii* P. Vargas

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga pentadactylis subsp. *willkommiana* (Boiss. ex Willk.) Rivas Mart.

Gr, Ma / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Saxifraga tridactylites L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited from Lanzahíta (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

SCROPHULARIACEAE

Buddleja davidii Franch.

Gr / introduced

Limosella aquatica L.

Gr, Ma / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Scrophularia bourgeana Lange

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Scrophularia canina L. subsp. *canina*

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Scrophularia lyrata Willd.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Scrophularia reuteri Daveau

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Scrophularia scorodonia L.

Gr / Atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Verbascum lychnitis L.

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Only known from the Arenas de San Pedro and Candeleda areas (photographic evidence in UPOS).

Verbascum pulverulentum Vill.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Verbascum rotundifolium Ten. subsp. *haenseleri* (Boiss.) Murb.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Verbascum simplex Hoffmanns. & Link

Gr?, Ma?, Mo? / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We were not able to find the voucher specimen that led to the reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Benedí, 2009). There are no vouchers of this species in MA or SALA, and we are not found any reference for the province.

Verbascum sinuatum L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited in the province (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2019).

Verbascum thapsus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Verbascum virgatum Stokes

Gr, Mo? / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: The record from Arévalo (Rivas Martínez *et al.*, 1986) needs to be confirmed.

SIMAROUBACEAE

Ailanthus altissima (Mill.) Swingle

Gr, Ma / introduced

Notes: Naturalised and invasive in many areas on the southern slopes of Gredos (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.).

SOLANACEAE

Datura ferox L.

Mo / introduced

Notes: Locally abundant in the municipality of El Oso (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2020).

Datura stramonium L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

Hyoscyamus albus L.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Hyoscyamus niger L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Lycium barbarum L.

Mo / introduced

Solanum dulcamara L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Solanum nigrum L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Solanum lycopersicum L.

Gr / introduced

“*Solanum villosum* Mill.”

Notes: Reported by Willkomm & Lange (1865–1870) and García Muñoz (2004) from the vicinity of Ávila city, but we have not found herbarium evidence confirming its presence in the province. There is also no reference to Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Sobrino Vesperinas & Sanz Elorza, 2012).

THYMELAEACEAE

Daphne gnidium L.

Gr, Ma / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Thymelaea passerina (L.) Coss. & Germ.

Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently cited as a new record for Ávila (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

Thymelaea procumbens A. Fern. & R. Fern.

Gr / Iberian endemism / Preferential attention (C and L), NT (LRE), NE (IUCN)

Thymelaea pubescens (L.) Meisn. subsp. ***pubescens***

Mo / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

Thymelaea sanamunda All.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We attribute the glabrous plants collected by B. García Muñoz in El Polvorín (Ávila city; UPOS5214) to this binomial.

ULMACEAE

Ulmus glabra Huds.

Gr / Eurasian / VU (IUCN, at European level)

Ulmus minor Mill.

Gr, Mo / Eurasian / DD (IUCN)

Ulmus pumila L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / introduced

URTICACEAE

Parietaria judaica L. subsp. ***judaica***

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Parietaria lusitanica L. subsp. ***lusitanica***

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Urtica dioica L. subsp. ***dioica***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Urtica urens L.

Gr, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

VALERIANACEAE

Centranthus calcitrapae (L.) Dufr.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Centranthus ruber (L.) DC. subsp. ***ruber***

Gr / introduced

“*Valeriana montana* L.”

Notes: The plants mentioned by Font Quer (1925) from Morezón and Los Conventos gorge, which served as the basis for including Ávila in *Flora iberica* (Vázquez Pardo *et al.*, 2007), belong to forms with slightly divided cauline leaves of *V. tripteris*. Moreover, at both locations, individuals with entire, three-lobed, or intermediate cauline leaves can be found. Moreover, *V. montana* prefers basic soils and limestone crevices. Therefore, we reject the presence of *V. montana* in Ávila and the Iberian Central System.

Valeriana officinalis L. subsp. ***officinalis***

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: Very rare in the province. Known exclusively from Pinar de Hoyocasero (MA774539).

Valeriana tripteris L.

Gr / European orophyte / NE (IUCN)

Valeriana tuberosa L.

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Valerianella coronata (L.) DC.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Valerianella discoidea (L.) Loisel.

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known exclusively from the Arévalo area (UPOS16941). The records from Gredos (Sánchez Mata, 1989) of this calcicolous plant belong to *V. coronata*.

Valerianella eriocarpa Desv.

Gr / Mediterranean-atlantic / NE (IUCN)

Notes: We only know it from Pinar de Hoyocasero (UPOS11458).

Valerianella locusta (L.) Laterr. subsp. ***locusta***

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

Valerianella microcarpa Loisel.

Gr / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Known only in the south of the province (Cuevas del Águila, Ramacastañas; MA646580).

VERBENACEAE

Aloysia citrodora Paláu (*Lippia triphylla* (L'Hér.) Kuntze)

Mo / introduced

Notes: A species native to South America that has naturalized on the banks of the Adaja river, in the municipality of Villanueva de Gómez.

Verbena officinalis L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Verbena supina L.

Gr, Mo / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

VIBURNACEAE

Sambucus ebulus L.

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Sambucus nigra* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Viburnum lantana* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Viburnum opulus* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Viburnum tinus* L.**

Gr / Mediterranean / LC (IUCN)

VIOLACEAE***Viola arvensis* Murray**

Gr?, Mo? / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Notes: None of abundant Ávila materials studied fit the characters of *V. arvensis*, but rather those of *V. kitaibeliana*. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that we have frequently observed an overlap of the characters used to distinguish both taxa.

***Viola canina* L.**

Gr / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

***Viola kitaibeliana* Schult.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

***Viola langeana* Valentine**

Gr / Iberian endemism / NE (IUCN)

***Viola odorata* L.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / LC (IUCN)

Viola palustris* L. subsp. *palustris

Gr / Circumboreal / LC (IUCN)

***Viola parvula* Tineo**

Gr / Mediterranean orophyte / NE (IUCN)

***Viola riviniana* Rchb.**

Gr, Ma / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

***Viola suavis* M. Biev.**

Mo / Mediterranean / NE (IUCN)

Notes: Recently found in Villanueva de Gómez (Sánchez-Villegas *et al.*, 2022a).

VITACEAE***Vitis rotundifolia* Michx.**

Gr / introduced

Notes: Recently found as naturalized in Lanzahíta (J.A. López Sáez, pers. comm.).

Vitis vinifera* L. subsp. *vinifera

Gr, Ma / introduced

***Vitis vinifera* subsp. *sylvestris* (C.C. Gmel.) Hegi**

Gr / Eurasian / NE (IUCN)

ZYGOPHYLLACEAE***Tribulus terrestris* L.**

Gr, Ma, Mo / Pluriregional / LC (IUCN)

Assessment of the flora of Ávila

The number of accepted taxa in this checklist is shown in Table 1, considering the major groups of vascular plants. It should be noted that these numbers include the 34 taxa whose presence in the province remains doubtful, but not the 55 taxa that have been previously cited for the province and that we consider should be discarded. As can be seen, allochthonous taxa (introduced by human activity and, at least, sporadically naturalized) represent 8.3% of the flora of Ávila (Table 2).

The number of taxa of the 15 most biodiverse families and 17 most biodiverse genera of the flora of Ávila is shown in tables 3 and 4.

In Table 2, the floristic spectrum of the province of Ávila is shown. See Aizpuru *et al.* (1999) for a precise definition.

Finally, it is interesting to note that of the 18 endemisms found in Gredos mountain range, five of them are exclusive to the province of Ávila (Table 5).

Conservation status of the flora of Ávila

The number of threatened taxa found in the flora of Ávila, as well as the threat category in which they are included, depend on the scale at which we are focusing. As we move from a global scale (IUCN Red List of Threatened Species) to a more regional scale (List of Threatened Species of Castilla y León), the number of species included in these lists increases. Thus, we find between 14 and 24 taxa included in some threat category, and between 6 and 8 taxa categorized as Near Threatened. (Table 6).

Table 1. Number of taxa (species + subspecies) of the major vascular plant groups.

	Native	Introduced	Total
Clubmosses	6	0	6
Ferns	37	1	38
Gymnosperms	9	2	11
Angiosperms	1760	162	1922
Primitive lineages of angiosperms	3	0	3
Monocots	384	34	418
Dicots	1373	128	1501
Total taxa	1812	165	1977

Table 2. Chorological spectrum of the province of Ávila.

Chorological element	Number of taxa	%
Atlantic	58	2.9
Mediterranean-Atlantic	114	5.8
Eurasian	545	27.6
Boreo-Alpine	13	0.7
European Orophyte	32	1.6
Mediterranean	584	29.5
Mediterranean Orophyte	20	1.0
Iberian endemism	231	11.7
Circumboreal	66	3.3
Pluriregional	128	6.5
Subcosmopolitan	21	1.1
Introduced	165	8.3

Table 3. Number of taxa (species + subspecies) of the 15 most biodiverse families.

Family	Number of taxa
Asteraceae	222
Poaceae	204
Fabaceae	172
Caryophyllaceae	107
Rosaceae	81
Brassicaceae	80
Apiaceae	72
Plantaginaceae	68
Lamiaceae	63
Ranunculaceae	58
Cyperaceae	52
Boraginaceae	45
Orchidaceae	31
Juncaceae	29
Crassulaceae	24

Table 4. Number of taxa (species + subspecies) of the 17 most biodiverse genera.

Genus	Number of taxa
<i>Trifolium</i>	38
<i>Ranunculus</i>	28
<i>Carex</i>	27
<i>Festuca</i>	26
<i>Juncus</i>	23
<i>Silene, Veronica</i>	22
<i>Vicia</i>	20
<i>Euphorbia</i>	17
<i>Galium, Myosotis</i>	16
<i>Rosa, Rumex, Sedum</i>	15
<i>Allium, Linaria, Taraxacum</i>	14

Table 5. Endemisms and subendemisms of Gredos mountain range in a broad sense (including the three mountain ranges mentioned above plus the San Vicente mountain range in Toledo). Those highlighted in bold are endemisms exclusive to the province of Ávila.

Endemisms	Subendemisms
<i>Antirrhinum grosii</i>	<i>Armeria arenaria</i> subsp. <i>segoviensis</i>
<i>Armeria bigerrensis</i> subsp. <i>bigerrensis</i>	<i>Centaurea janeri</i> subsp. <i>janeri</i>
<i>Armeria rivas-martinezii</i>	<i>Centaurea nigra</i> subsp. <i>carpetana</i>
<i>Asphodelus oblongicarpus</i>	<i>Conopodium bunioides</i>
<i>Astragalus devesae</i>	<i>Doronicum carpetanum</i> subsp. <i>carpetanum</i>
<i>Centaurea avilae</i>	<i>Echium salmaticum</i>
<i>Doronicum carpetanum</i> subsp. <i>kuepferi</i>	<i>Fritillaria pyrenaica</i> subsp. <i>falcata</i>
<i>Dianthus gredensis</i>	<i>Hippocrepis carpetana</i>
<i>Echinopartum barnadesii</i>	<i>Iberodes brassicifolia</i>
<i>Festuca vettonica</i>	<i>Leucanthemopsis boissieri</i>
<i>Linaria vettonica</i>	<i>Ranunculus ollissiponensis</i> subsp. <i>alpinus</i>
<i>Pseudomisopates rivas-martinezii</i>	<i>Reseda gredensis</i>
<i>Ranunculus cherubicus</i> subsp. <i>cherubicus</i>	<i>Scrophularia bourgaeana</i>
<i>Santolina oblongifolia</i>	<i>Succisella microcephala</i>
<i>Saxifraga pentadactylis</i> subsp. <i>almanzorii</i>	<i>Tephrosieris balbisiana</i> subsp. <i>coincyi</i>
<i>Scrophularia reuteri</i>	
<i>Sedum lagascae</i>	
<i>Teucrium oxylepis</i> subsp. <i>gredense</i>	

Table 6. Number of taxa (species + subspecies) included in any red list at international (IUCN), national (LRE) and regional (C and L) level.

Red List	Threat Category	Number of taxa	% of the total species in the province
UICN	Near Threatened (NT)	8	0.40
	Vulnerable (VU)	4	0.20
	Endangered (EN)	7	0.35
	Critically Endangered (CR)	3	0.15
LRE	Near Threatened (NT)	6	0.30
	Vulnerable (VU)	12	0.61
	Endangered (EN)	7	0.35
	Critically Endangered (CR)	4	0.20
C and L	With regulated use	3	0.15
	Preferential attention	48	2.43
	Vulnerable	9	0.45
	Endangered	7	0.35

Discussion

Assessment of the flora of Ávila

In Table 7, the number of taxa and floristic density (number of taxa/km²; Marugán, 1989) is shown for the provinces of Ávila (8050.15 km²), Burgos

(14292 km²; Alejandre et al., 2016a), Madrid (8028 km²; López Jiménez, 2015), La Rioja (5045 km²; Alejandre et al., 2016b), Soria (10306.42 km²; Carlos Molina, pers. comm.), Toledo (15369 km²; Sanz Elorza, 2006), and Zamora (10561 km²; Bariego, 2016).

Table 7. Number of taxa and floristic density in the provinces of Ávila (AV), Burgos (BU), Madrid (M), La Rioja (RI), Soria (SO), Toledo (TO) and Zamora (ZA).

	AV	BU	M	RI	SO	TO	ZA
Clubmosses (Lycopodiophytina)	6	7	6	4	5	3	5
Ferns (Polypodiophytina)	38	65	57	57	48	30	47
Gymnosperms (Spermatophytina-Pinopsida)	11	12	33	14	16	11	15
Angiosperms (Spermatophytina-Magnoliopsida)	1921	2469	2614	2136	2422	1699	2094
Total	1977	2553	2710	2211	2491	1743	2161
Floristic density	0,2455	0,1786	0,3376	0,4382	0,2417	0,1134	0,2046

As it can be deduced from these data, the number of taxa in Ávila is lower than in Madrid, Burgos, La Rioja, Soria, and Zamora, while it is only higher than in Toledo. However, concerning floristic density, Ávila is in third place among the seven provinces mentioned, just behind La Rioja and Madrid. This is a clear indicator of the high diversity of vascular plants in the province of Ávila, despite the predominant lithology resulting in acidic soils (Luceño et al., 2016). Nevertheless, it is important to note the significant contribution to this high density made by the basic soils of La Moraña region, the band of diabasas that crosses the centre of the province and the basic soils of certain areas of the Tiétar valley and the surroundings of Arévalo. Another factor that significantly contributes to the richness of the Ávila flora is the wide altitudinal range of an essentially mountainous province, whose land ranges from 295 m asl in the lower reaches of the Tiétar to 2591 m asl on the Almanzor peak.

Regarding the chorological elements of the province (Table 4), the most prominent are the Mediterranean elements (29.6%), followed by the Eurasian (27.6%) and the Iberian endemic taxa (11.7%). The geographical location of the province makes the predominance of the Mediterranean elements over the Eurasian ones logical. These percentages are quite similar to those published for the province of Zamora (26.4% of taxa belonging to the Mediterranean elements, 21.9% to the Eurasian and 11.3% to the Iberian endemics; Bariego, 2016), and does not differ significantly from those published by Luceño & Vargas (1991) for the Gredos mountain range as a whole. It is worth noting that the percentage of allochthonous taxa reaches 8.3% of the total, a value which, although higher than desirable, is below that of provinces such as Zamora (11.3%; Bariego, 2016) or Madrid (9.7%; López Jiménez, 2015), just slightly above the percentage obtained for the entire Gredos mountain range (Luceño & Vargas, 1991).

Finally, it is interesting to highlight that the province of Ávila has five exclusive endemisms (Table 5), which contrasts with the absence of endemisms in

Madrid, even though the latter has 734 more taxa than Ávila.

Threatened flora

The uniqueness of the flora of Ávila is reflected in the relatively high number of taxa included in red lists of threatened flora. At regional level, the list of species is quite complete thanks to the checklist of Protected Flora of Castilla y León, created by "Decreto 63/2007". This checklist not only covers vulnerable or endangered species, but also includes those with uses that are considered in needs of regulation, and taxa of special interest. It is this last category that includes the highest number of taxa (48), out of a total of 67 included in the checklist. On a broader scale, if we compare the Spanish Red List (Moreno, 2008) with the Red List of threatened species compiled by the IUCN at the global level, the number of taxa included are mostly the same, although the national Red List includes more taxa in the category of Vulnerable.

Comparing with the flora of nearby provinces, the high percentage of species from the province of Ávila included in the Spanish Red List is remarkable. In the province of Toledo, despite having just 233 taxa less than Ávila, only two taxa are included in the Spanish Red List (Table 8), one of them as Endangered (EN; *Vella pseudocytisus* subsp. *pseudocytisus*) and the other as Critically Endangered (CR; *Thymelaea lythroides*). Regarding the flora of Madrid, it is notable that despite having around 734 taxa more than the province of Ávila (2710 taxa compared to the 1977 found in Ávila), the percentage of threatened species according to the Spanish Red List is twice in Ávila (1.16%) compared to that of Madrid (0.66%). In absolute numbers, this is equivalent to 23 threatened taxa in Ávila compared to 18 in Madrid. Considering that in most cases the inclusion of a species within any of the threat categories is determined by a restricted distribution or being represented by very small populations, the discussed data support the uniqueness/exclusivity of the flora of the province of Ávila in comparison with neighbouring provinces. However, it should be

Table 8. Comparison of the number of threatened taxa at national level (LRE) with other floras of different provinces of Spain, indicating the number of taxa and the percentage of the total in brackets.

	Ávila	Madrid	Toledo
Total number of taxa (species + subspecies)	1977	2710	1743
Vulnerables (VU)	12 (0.61 %)	10 (0.37 %)	0
Endangered (EN)	7 (0.35 %)	6 (0.22 %)	1 (0.06 %)
Critically Endangered (CR)	4 (0.20 %)	2 (0.07 %)	1 (0.06 %)

noted that numerous contributions to the flora of Madrid have been made in recent years, so the data in the Madrid checklist (López Jiménez, 2015) should be taken with caution.

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Authorship contribution

M.L. directed the work, participated in most of the field trips and herbaria studies and wrote the first draft; R.S.-V. and B.Q. de la P. participate in most of the field trips and herbaria studies, and wrote the first draft; M.S.-V. participate in most of the field trips; E.M. participate in writing the first version of the manuscript and carried out the conservation study; F.J.S.V., J.L.R.F. and A.A.M. participated in several field trips and reviewed the draft; P.B., E.R., V.J.M, and J.A.L.S. provided numerous records and evidences of little-known plants, and revised the draft.

Conflict of interest

None.

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